

GETTING IT RIGHT FOR CARE EXPERIENCED TEENAGE PARENTS

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Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the
University of the West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Philosophy.

DECLARATION

I declare that the work submitted for this thesis is my own account of my research and that the material has not been submitted for any degree or diploma at any other tertiary education institution.

Acknowledgement has been appropriately provided where reference has been made to the work of others.

Susan Patricia Kayes

Signature:

Date: 23rd November 2023

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DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated with love to the memory of my parents

Tom and Teresa and my nephew David.

It is also dedicated to Louise.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I wish to offer my sincere gratitude to the care experienced teenage parents who agreed to share their perceptions and experiences. Thank you for your trust and your honesty in sharing your story with me.

Many thanks to the health and social care professionals who took the time out of their busy day to be involved in the study. My thanks also to senior managers within the health and social care partnership areas who helped make the study happen.

I am very grateful to my supervisors Professor Jean Rankin, Dr Ruth Astbury and Dr Laura McMillan for their support, patience, guidance and encouragement.

Finally, to my partner Nigel, my children Laura and David, my brother Brian and my other siblings, friends and colleagues for their practical support and their belief in my ability to complete this journey.

ABSTRACT

Background:

Early parenthood is associated with increased adverse social and health outcomes for mother/baby compared to pregnancies or parenting at an older age. If young people have experience of being in care, they have an increased prevalence of becoming teenage parents. This study was conducted in two Health and Social Care Partnerships in Scotland. The aim of the study was to explore how care experienced teenage parents (CEP) are supported to reduce the challenges associated with both leaving care and becoming a teenage parent.

Method:

This research design included collective case studies (n=6) of care experienced mothers involved in the Family Nurse Partnership Programme. The study was conducted within two health and social care partnerships in Scotland. The cases included 6 CEP, 6 Family Nurse and 3 Significant Others. Qualitative data was collected using semi-structured interviews with the case study participants (n=15). A focus group was then conducted with child and family social work staff (n=9) who were experienced in supporting teenage CEP, to gain a wider multidimensional perspective.

Analysis:

Analysis was conducted using a thematic analysis framework. Findings included three themes with associated sub themes: Trauma: Shadows of Childhood, Relationships: Networks and Transitions.

Findings:

The extent to which teenage CEP are supported was explored. Each CEP had experience of multiple chronic/complex childhood traumatic events which profoundly impacted their emotions, behaviours, poor coping strategies and quality of life. Related issues included experiencing sexual abuse and childhood neglect, feelings of shame and self-blame, numbing of feelings with triggers re-igniting negative memories and fear. These experiences impacted on the CEP's mental health and increased risk-taking behaviours. Transitions through life events created major implications for the mothers to cope with, such as living with poverty and finding a suitable living

environment. The relationships CEP had with individuals/groups impacted on their lives. Relationships with birth families could be complex due to historical issues of childhood sexual abuse and/or neglect. The CEP had low levels of social support. Multi-agency working sought to help the CEP to overcome some of the challenges they faced to keep them and their child safe. However, child protection processes for their own children complicated relationships with some professionals and a few of the situations were associated with deteriorating mental health, anxieties, fears and stigma in the CEP.

Stigma, accessibility and acceptability of services, as well as the fear of being judged or scrutinised, prevented some CEP from engaging with resources that were there to help them. Despite the challenges faced, the CEP were motivated to parent well and shared plans for the future for themselves and their children.

Recommendations:

Based on the research findings, specific sexual health and relationships education and interventions are required to reduce the high incidence of unplanned teenage pregnancy and rapid repeat pregnancy. There is also a need to raise awareness and increase understanding of the experiences of care experienced teenage parents in relation to the impact on them of childhood-related trauma, their relationships, transition to parenthood, leaving care and potential homelessness and living in undesirable accommodation.

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations

Antenatal	The period from conception to birth.
CSA	Child sexual abuse.
CEL 16	Chief Executive Letter to Health Boards regarding implementing care experienced children's health assessments.
CEP	Care experienced parent/s.
FN	Family Nurse.
FNP	Family Nurse Partnership.
IPV	Imitate partner violence.
Gestation	The number of weeks the woman has been pregnant (from the last menstrual period).
GIRFE	Getting it Right for Everyone. A proposed multi-agency national health and social care approach building on best practice and the evidence of GIRFEC to provide support from young adulthood to end of life care.
GIRFEC	Getting it Right for Every Child. A national approach in Scotland to improve outcomes and well-being of our children and young people by offering the right help at the right time.
Kinship care	Kinship care is when a child is looked after by their extended family or close friends if they cannot remain with their birth parents
Maternal Anaemia	A condition of lower than normal red blood cells or haemoglobin during pregnancy which is associated with poor maternal and infant health outcomes.
Morbidity	The incidence of injury or complications.
Pre-eclampsia	Pre-eclampsia is a health condition that can adversely affect some pregnant women and their unborn child usually during the second half of pregnancy (from 20 weeks) or soon after delivery.
Preterm labour	Birth of infant before 37 weeks gestation.

RRP	Rapid repeat pregnancy.
SO	Significant other in the CEP's life.
SW	Social Worker.
WHO	World Health Organisation.

Chapter 1. Introduction

This chapter discusses the prevalence of teenage pregnancies from a global perspective and includes information from both developing and developed countries. Associated health and psychosocial consequences for early parenthood relating to both the mother and their child are described. The focus then considers teenage pregnancy from the UK and Scotland context and includes a brief outline of the increased risks of teenage pregnancy for care experienced young people. The theoretical framework that underpins this study is described. The policy and legislative context in Scotland, and my personal journey which led me to undertake this current study, are also included.

1.1 Global issues of teenage pregnancies

The World Health Organisation (WHO) (2020) states that over recent decades teenage pregnancy has become a major public health concern worldwide in both developing and developed countries. Whilst globally, teenage pregnancy rates have steadily declined by 48% between 1960 and 2019 (World Bank Group, 2021). Sully *et al.* (2020) estimate that in low and middle class income countries approximately 50% of the 21 million pregnancies of adolescents, aged 15–19 years, were unintended.

Teenagers who have not benefitted from education may have pursued early marriage and/or motherhood due to limited employment opportunities (WHO, 2020). In the developing world, 25% of young females are married before they are age 18 and nearly 40% of the pregnancies are intended (UNFPA, 2017; WHO, 2020). Approximately 218 million women have been unable to plan their families due to barriers to obtaining modern family planning resources (Sully *et al.*, 2020). Teenagers may also become pregnant due to their own misunderstanding about pregnancy, or their reduced cognitive, emotional and behavioural difficulties in effectively using contraception (WHO, 2015; UNFPA, 2017).

Teenage pregnancy and birth rates are higher in East Asia, Mexico and the countries in Sub-Saharan Africa. In these countries, teenage marriage and parenthood are perceived as the norm, with most teenage pregnancies likely to be intended (Sedgh *et al.*, 2015; Bongaarts, 2016). During 2015-2020, more than one in four young women

before the age of 18 gave birth in sub-Saharan Africa (UNICEF, 2021). Chi *et al.* (2015) discovered the consequences of two post-conflict countries in sub-Saharan Africa resulted in reduced access to maternal and reproductive health services, demonstrated a high prevalence of teenage pregnancy, concealed abortions and increased maternal and newborn morbidity and mortality.

1.2 Health risks related to teenage mothers

For some teenagers, pregnancy is a desired and positive choice (Kreager *et al.*, 2010; Brand *et al.*, 2014) however, for many their pregnancy is unintended (Rubin and East, 1999; Seamark and Lings, 2004). Regardless of the intention, most teenage parents and their children are challenged by a range of socio-economical and adverse health outcomes that are directly associated with their age and their personal circumstances at conception (Hobcraft and Keirnan, 1999; Kearney, 2010; WHO, 2015; Norton *et al.*, 2017).

Difficulties during pregnancy, childbirth and abortions are the main causes of mortality, morbidity and ongoing health problems for 15 to 19-year-old girls globally (Neal *et al.*, 2012; Chandra-Mouli *et al.*, 2013; WHO, 2021). Across the world, approximately 830 females die each day from avoidable causes related to pregnancy and childbirth, with young adolescents experiencing a greater risk of complications and death due to pregnancy than other women (WHO, 2021). Parra-Pingel *et al.* (2017) stated that adolescent mothers are more likely to suffer from pre-eclampsia and Kawakita *et al.* (2016) found a significantly greater risk of maternal anaemia and preterm delivery in adolescents. Norton *et al.* (2017) discovered that of the 22.5 million teenage parents in 60 different countries, approximately 4.1 million had rapid repeat second pregnancies that caused the young mothers and their children to experience additional health risks. Mayor (2004) and Kirchengast (2016) argued that it is inaccurate to suggest there are additional health risks for all teenage pregnancies. They indicate the health risks mainly relate to economically deprived young mothers under 15 years of age who are less likely to be physically developed enough to sustain a healthy pregnancy.

According to the United Nations Fund for Population Activities (Loaiza and Liang, 2013):

'Pregnancies among girls less than 18 years of age have irreparable consequences. It violates the rights of girls, with life-threatening consequences in terms of sexual and reproductive health, and poses high development costs for communities, particularly in perpetuating the cycle of poverty. Existing evidence strongly disputes the rationale of traditional cultural practices such as child marriage. It supports immediate action to enforce laws protecting the rights of children and particularly of girls; guarantee education and health needs; and eliminate the risks of violence, pregnancy among girls less than 18 years of age, HIV infection, and maternal deaths and disability' (Loaiza and Liang, 2013, p. 3).

1.3 Children of teenage mothers

Children of teenage mothers are more likely to have lower than average birth weight (Manlove *et al.*, 2008; Marvin-Dowle *et al.*, 2018), higher mortality, preterm delivery (Payne, 2001; Vallone and Hoffman, 2003; Platt, 2014; Kawakita *et al.*, 2016) and significant neonatal conditions (Marvin-Dowle *et al.*, 2018). Vallone and Hoffman (2003) and Platt (2014) found that teenage mothers are vulnerable to pregnancy denial, resulting in missed screening tests, undetected foetal abnormalities, and the risks of unassisted delivery for mother and child. These children also have a 63% increased likelihood of living in poverty compared to babies born to mothers in their 20s (Scottish Government, 2014b). They are reported to have poor language development (Keown *et al.*, 2001; Towson *et al.*, 2019), increased hospital attendance due to accidental injury (Peckham, 1993), live in poor-quality housing (Cooke and Owen, 2007; Fitzpatrick *et al.*, 2021), experience poor nutrition, lower educational achievement, develop a criminal history as they move into adulthood (Coyne *et al.*, 2013) and higher unemployment (Jaffee *et al.*, 2001). Furthermore, Payne (2001) found children of teenage parents are more likely to experience parental childhood abuse.

1.4 Violence and abuse

Sexual abuse is a known causative factor for teenage pregnancy, with more than a third of teenagers in some countries disclosing that their first sexual encounter was coerced (Silverman *et al.*, 2001; Silverman and Raj, 2014). Many partners of childbearing teenagers are adults (Lindberg *et al.*, 1997). In Lindberg *et al.*'s, (1997)

study 40% of 15-year-old mothers had a baby with a partner aged 20 or older. This finding of older males being the father of teenage pregnancies was also evidenced by Pires *et al.* (2021) who found teenage mother's partner's age difference ranged up to 23 years. Adult males having sexual relationships with adolescents is problematic as many of these relationships may be abusive or coercive (Klein, 2005). Young *et al.* (2011) and Noll and Shenk (2013) found young parents are twice as likely to have been sexually abused in childhood. Lamont (2010) found that postpartum women impacted by sexual abuse have a reduced parenting capacity and are at higher risk of poor mental health due to repressed memories of the abuse resurfacing.

Intimate partner violence (IPV) during pregnancy can have serious consequences for the mother and unborn child (Huth-Bocks, *et al.*, 2002). Globally, IPV in pregnancy ranges between 4% and 12% (WHO, 2011). Domestic abuse plays a significant role in maternal and perinatal mortality and morbidity (Amaro *et al.*, 1990; Quinlivan *et al.*, 2001, Donovan *et al.*, 2016). IPV is also strongly correlated with child abuse (McGuigan and Pratt, 2001). A study by Barter *et al.* (2009) demonstrated that some teenage girls, especially those with a family history of abuse or with an older boyfriend, are at severe risk of harm from their partner's violence. Intimate partner violence can result in depression and post-traumatic stress disorder as well as a range of physical health ailments (Adam *et al.*, 2011).

1.5 Teenage pregnancies in the developed world

In the developed world, the teenage pregnancy rate is highest in New Zealand (18 per 1,000), the United States (17 per 1,000) and the UK (12 per 1000) (Naring and Yaron, 2014). The Netherlands, Slovenia, Sweden, France and Italy rates are lower (5 per 1000). Singapore and Switzerland have a particularly low teen pregnancy rate (3 per 1000) (Naring and Yaron, 2014). This is attributed to sex education programs, free family planning services and low-cost emergency contraception being widely available (Naring and Yaron, 2014). In the 1970s, the Netherlands, Sweden and Germany had similar teenage pregnancy rates to the UK (Sedgh *et al.*, 2015); however, these countries have significantly reduced their rates over the last 30 years. (Sedgh *et al.*, 2015). The prevention of teenage pregnancies and teenage motherhood is a priority for public health in most developed, and increasingly in developing, countries (Kirchengast, 2016). Cook and Cameron (2017) found that despite a significant decline

in teenage pregnancies since 1999, the UK still has the highest teenage pregnancy rate in Western Europe. With a link between poverty and teenage pregnancy (Sully *et al.*, 2020), it is unclear why the United Kingdom teenage pregnancy rates remain so high compared to its Western European neighbours.

1.6 Teenage pregnancies in the United Kingdom

Reducing unintended teenage pregnancy remains a priority in the United Kingdom (UK) and evidence shows that teenage conceptions in England and Wales have continued to decline between 1993 and 2019, from 42 per 1,000 women to 16 per 1,000 women (Nuffield Trust, 2022). The teenage pregnancy rate in Scotland also continues to fall and in 2020 equated to 23.9 per 1,000 women in 2020 (Public Health Scotland, 2022). Table (1.1) illustrates the decline in the number of live births to teenage mothers in the UK from 2016 to 2018.

		England	Wales	Scotland	Northern Ireland
Live births to teenage mothers under twenty years in the UK	2018 (rate/1,000 aged 15-19 years)	11.80	14.27	11.59	11.92
	2017 (rate/1,000 aged 15-19 years)	12.48	16.51	12.96	12.37
	2016 (rate/1,000 aged 15-19 years)	13.55	16.93	13.51	13.78

Table 1.1 Live births to teenage mothers in the UK.

In England, Wales and Scotland, termination of pregnancies have gradually risen and are now slightly higher than births (Public Health England, 2018; Public Health Scotland, 2022). All UK countries have described a reduction of the inequality gap in the rate of teenage births between young people living in the most and least deprived areas (Public Health England, 2018; Public Health Intelligence Unit, 2019; Public Health Scotland, 2022). However, the risk of teenage parenthood for young women living in the areas of highest deprivation during 2020, was still five times higher than those in the least deprived areas (44.9 compared to 9 per 1,000) (Public Health Scotland, 2022).

1.7 Education and employment

Adolescent pregnancy and having a young child often results in young parents leaving education (Atkinson *et al.*, 2014; Scottish Government, 2016; Action for Children, 2019). Action for Children (2019) analysed the Next Steps data set (a longitudinal study following the lives of people born in England during 1989-90) conducted a literature review and facilitated focus groups to achieve a better understanding of young parents' lives. Action for Children (2019) compared young parents to their non-parenting peers and found only 11% of young parents attended higher education in comparison to 45%. Moreover, 33% of young parents were in 'skilled work', compared to 51% of their peers. Young parents in employment are also more disadvantaged when compared with older parents. Under-21s do not benefit as much from the minimum wage as their older colleagues, which appears to ignore the adult responsibilities of young parents (Action for Children, 2019). This contributes to the 54% of young parents who are living in poverty (New Policy Institute, 2015).

1.8 Psychosocial consequences for teenage parents

Until the mid-20th century, it was considered desirable for late adolescents to be married and become parents (Duncan, 2005). As teenage pregnancies peaked during the 1950s and 1960s, concerns about the negative health consequences and the associated costs to society, resulted in early pregnancies being widely viewed as socially unacceptable and a public health issue (Duncan, 2005; Weed *et al.*, 2014). The framing of teenage pregnancy prevention as a public health concern has been challenged by Lawlor *et al.* (2002), who consider that it is the social economic factors within society that have led to poor outcomes.

With the continued public health focus on the prevention of teenage pregnancies, teenage parents can encounter hostile attitudes and be adversely impacted by Government policies that have not considered their needs (Yardley, 2008). Teenage mothers often encounter discrimination in the form of negative comments within their community (Yardley, 2008). Buchanan and Jardine (2020) evidenced that for some young mothers age-related stigma from professionals, other mothers, family and wider society created a fear of judgement, which resulted in some of the teenage mothers failing to participate in support groups or community activities.

Young mothers themselves can add to the stigma by voicing negative moral judgments of other teenage mothers, whilst portraying themselves as exemptions to the teenage mother stereotype (Yardley, 2008; Jones *et al.*, 2019). Teenage mothers are at a higher risk of postpartum depression in the first three years after giving birth (Jenkins, 2012). This can result in impaired parenting practices and can have long-term consequences for both the mother and her child (Murray *et al.*, 1996; Jenkins, 2012). Whitehead (2001) argued it is not teenage motherhood that impacts on their mental health, but instead, it is the stigma of being a teenage parent which leads to isolation and social exclusion for the young mothers, thus impacting on both their mental and physical health. Moreover, young mothers can be reluctant to seek mental health service support due to their concerns about social work being informed (Jenkins, 2012).

Evidence highlights pregnancy can be a motivating factor for mothers to overcome obstacles such as abuse and poverty (Olds *et al.*, 1997; Buchanan and Jardine, 2020). However, for teenage parents without family support or other means of social capital to draw from, these women have been more likely to view motherhood as a further source of stress, rather than a motivating factor for change (Brown and Bloom, 2009). Nearly 1 in 5 young parents are isolated from their peers and rarely or never see any friends (Action for Children, 2019). Barlett *et al.* (2015) evidenced that having social support moderated the risk of infant neglect and young mothers who had frequent access to support had greater parenting empathy.

With a high number of young women having an unplanned pregnancy and living in homeless accommodation, they can become even more isolated due to the rule of no overnight visitors, including their partner. This has the potential to exclude fathers from parenting (Gorton, 2000). Delays in accessing suitable accommodation, especially at a late stage in pregnancy, has led to some young mothers feeling obliged to accept housing in very poor condition or in an area distant from social supports (Cooke and Owen, 2007).

1.9 Teenage fathers

Opinions of young fathers have often been negative, based on the notion that young parents' relationships frequently end within the first few years after the child's birth and the father's relationship with the child will not be sustained (Smeeding *et al.*, 2011).

Studies also suggest that more fathers regret the pregnancy than the mothers (Corkindale *et al.*, 2009). In a UK study, Jaffee *et al.* (2001) identified that young absent fathers were often raised in stressful circumstances, had conduct problems during childhood and had poor social and psychological adjustment in young adulthood. The study concluded that some absent fathers struggled to develop healthy partnerships and to become a nurturing father (Jaffee *et al.*, 2001).

The common assumption that young fathers are irresponsible is further reinforced for those who are young offenders, who are frequently viewed as a risk rather than an asset for their children (Maxwell *et al.*, 2012). There is a significant correlation between young offenders and teenage fatherhood (Elster *et al.*, 1987; Bullis *et al.*, 2004). Aggression and/or a long history of anti-social offending has been highly associated with a range of negative indicators, including the inability to provide sensitive and responsive parenting (Kiselica, 2011). However, not all young offenders have histories of violence. Bronte-Tinkew *et al.* (2009) and Neale *et al.* (2015) challenged the notion that young offender fathers are necessarily a risk to their child, and recommended the need to recognise the adolescent father's developmental potential to make positive changes and to fulfil his ability to parent.

Clayton (2016) found that young fathers may not have participated in the care of their children due to factors they could not control. Teenage fathers are reported to have frequently faced resistance from the mother or the mother's family (Neale and Lau-Clayton, 2011). They lacked the means to contribute financially and lived within poor housing; all of which created barriers to them accessing their child (Lemay *et al.*, 2010). The UNCRC, Article 9 (3) (UNICEF, 1989) states children whose parents do not live together have the right to stay in contact with both parents, unless this might harm the child. Although teenage fathers might have wished to be involved in the lives of their children (Clayton, 2016), they often lacked the financial means to do so. Teenage fatherhood is associated with low educational achievement, reduced economic stability and employment, as well as increased relationship difficulties (Coley and Chase-Lansdale, 1998; Clayton, 2016). According to Clayton (2015), a young father's financial struggles may have caused relationship difficulties for the expectant parents. The financial demands of fatherhood were found to have resulted in the teenage fathers giving up education in preference for unskilled work and reduced their chances for obtaining a more rewarding career (Clayton, 2015).

Lamb and Lewis (2010) stated that young fathers performed similar roles to that of young mothers, through offering security, love, interest and boundaries. Capaldi *et al.*'s (2002) and Lamb and Lewis's (2010) studies reported that the quantity and quality of father-child interactions during the early childhood years can result in fewer adolescent behavioural problems, better emotional regulation and improved language and cognitive functioning for their children. Evidence shows that the more fathers engaged with their babies, the more likely their relationships with their children continued irrespective of divorce or separation (Haux and Platt, 2021). Other studies have shown little or no positive effect on a father's involvement with their child, with the benefit to the child being materialised via the father-mother relationship (Amato and Rezac, 1994; Flouri, 2006). Supportive partners have been shown to improve mother's finances and increase their psychological well-being, thus maternal benefits correspondingly enhanced the child's experiences (Black *et al.*, 2002).

Birth registration applies to the child's fundamental right to a legal identity, name and nationality and the international conventions. Article 24(2) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (1966) documents the child's right to be registered immediately after birth. Graham *et al.* (2007) found that 7% of all births registered in the UK have only the mother named on their birth certificate. Graham *et al.* (2007) considered that an omission to record the father's name was mainly accidental, stating that teenage mothers had a more complicated bureaucratic procedure to encounter and may not understand the process. Dallas *et al.* (2000) argued, that contrary to unintentional errors in the child's birth registration process, at times significant conflicts in the parents' relationships resulted in an attempt by the mother to ensure the father had no contact rights with the child in the future. Separated young men (Neale *et al.*, 2015) discussed the emotional pain of the mothers not allowing them to see their child and how the child was used by the mothers to manipulate them.

Jaffee *et al.* (2001) considered that young absent fathers will continue to experience difficulties in being a positive father unless UK policy initiatives to encourage two-parent families also support young fathers. Accessibility of effective services for young fathers is limited and many fathers have been unable to access any fathers' groups and feel unwelcome at general parenting services (Cundy, 2012). Health professionals working in maternity services understandably focus on the mother and child's health.

Pollock *et al.* (2005) reported that the young men's experiences of antenatal care in maternity units often reinforced their feelings of being irrelevant to the pregnancy. Failures to involve the father during pregnancy missed the opportunity to provide support that could improve long term outcomes for both the parents and the child (Cundy, 2012). Furthermore, many young fathers found it hard to access information about their legal rights (Fagan and Kaufman, 2015).

A UK study by Bacchus *et al.* (2004) found 23% of the 200 female participants attending maternity services had been impacted by intimate partner violence at some point in their lives. Furthermore, a small UK study by Wood and Barter (2015) (n=16) aimed to explore the experiences of teenage mother's relationships with their partners and discovered one-third of young mothers reported experiencing physical violence from their partner. Violence during pregnancy and following birth has particularly negative effects for mothers and their children (Bacchus *et al.*, 2014; Wood and Barter, 2015). Professionals needed to balance their assessment of the father as a risk, versus the father as a positive resource, Ashley *et al.* (2006) asserted that practitioners were often reluctant to engage with young fathers and other studies have evidenced that young fathers are often completely overlooked in teenage parenting work (Burgess, 2007, Clayton, 2015). This premise can obscure the potential that young fathers, with sufficient support, can make a positive contribution to their child's well-being (Lamb and Lewis, 2010).

Klein (2005) discovered research on teenage parents mostly focussed on mothers, causing fewer resources to be invested into teenage fathers (Klein, 2005). Research into supporting young fathers is restricted due to the difficulties associated with recruitment of young fathers (Gelder, 2002).

1.10 Early parenthood in care experienced population

The term 'care experienced' refers to someone who has been, or is presently, in care (e.g. children's residential homes, kinship care, foster care, secure care) or has a background of being 'looked after' during their childhood or adolescence (Scottish Government, 2021(c)). The evidence frequently found care experienced young people in care or leaving care were at significantly higher risk of experiencing early parenthood than their peers without care experience histories (Bradshaw *et al.*, 2014; Roberts *et al.*, 2018).

Risk factors associated with teenage parenthood, as previously discussed, include: socio-economic deprivation; restricted participation in education and low educational attainment. Research has shown that as a group, care experienced young people probably satisfied most, if not all, of the above risk criteria (Hobcraft and Kieran, 1999). Care experienced young people are at increased risk of substance misuse (Williams and Parker, 2001; Alderson *et al.*, 2017) as they have often experienced parental substance misuse and may view excessive drugs and/or alcohol use as 'normal' (Neale, 2002; Newburn and Pearson, 2002; Ward, *et al.*, 2003). Research has evidenced that alcohol misuse and early sexual experimentation has been associated with sex that is regretted, abusive or violent (Ingham, 2002).

Young people who left school without qualifications are at a higher risk of becoming teenage parents (Winter *et al.*, 2016). Evidence demonstrated that care experienced children and young people, for a complexity of reasons have experienced disruption in their education (Scottish Government, 2021c).

Scott and Hill (2006) reflected that CEP experiences and backgrounds made them particularly vulnerable to poor physical and mental health outcomes. Care experienced young people are more likely to have left their care setting before the age of 18 and are likely to be impacted by social isolation and reduced social supports. For many children and young people, the experience of being in care has been protective as they have needed to be kept safe from parental abuse or neglect (Oakley *et al.*, 2018). Alternatively, the experience and distress of having been taken into care can intensify emotional and behavioural issues (Reimer, 2010; Independent Care Review, 2020a). Poor emotional well-being has also been found to have contributed to an increased risk of unintended pregnancy and can be a precursor to negative perinatal and postpartum outcomes (Hall *et al.*, 2015). A lack of parental relationship has also been linked to sexual risk-taking among young people (Gramkowski *et al.*, 2009).

Teenage pregnancy rates in care experienced young people are also increased as they may have been exposed to a higher risk of sexual exploitation and abuse (King and Van Wert, 2017). Young people who are care experienced may have experienced traumatic events such as sexual abuse and exploitation, which could have distorted their understanding of sex and healthy relationships (King and Van Wert, 2017). Care experienced teenagers appeared to face barriers in finding and using services relevant

to their needs, including a lack of knowledge and barriers to safe sex practices (Bucknall and Bick, 2019).

Lack of social supports can result in CEP being overwhelmed by stressors and healthy parenting practices being disrupted. Teenage parenthood and childhood abuse evident in the parents' personal history have been identified as risk factors for the future abuse of their own children (Calder *et al.*, 2012). This results in CEP being identified and referred early to social work services by health services during the antenatal period. The literature review in chapter 2 provides a detailed account of the current evidence regarding CEP challenges and opportunities.

1.11 Improving outcomes for teenage parents and children

Brand *et al.* (2014) stated early and effective intervention for teenage parents may smooth their transition to motherhood and be the key to breaking the cycle of deprivation. Bradshaw *et al.* (2014) highlighted the importance of education to reduce the likelihood of higher unemployment and lower income for teenage parents. Other research demonstrated access to good antenatal care (Horgan *et al.*, 2011); home visiting programmes; access to parenting education (Olds *et al.*, 1997); access to smoking cessation supports (Radley *et al.*, 2013); improved housing (Cook and Cameron, 2017) ; social support (Ramey *et al.*, 2000); early educational interventions for disadvantaged children (Ramey *et al.*, 2000) and clinic-based healthcare programmes for teenage mothers and their children, all contributed to improved health, improved child development, well-being and financial outcomes for the young parent and their child (Public Health England, 2018).

Teenage pregnancy within the developing and developed world remains a public health concern (WHO, 2020). Teenage parents are more likely to have not engaged in education which has led them to be at increased risk of poverty (Action for Children, 2019). Teenage parenthood has also been linked to poor emotional well-being and social isolation. Some studies have evidenced an increased risk of IPV in teenage relationships. Higher rates of infant mortality, behavioural difficulties and increased risk of childhood accidents have been documented. Evidence demonstrated CEP face many of the identified risk factors of becoming a teenage parent and without sufficient social support and resources there is the chance the CEP could struggle to successfully parent their child. Government policy and a public health focus on

teenage pregnancy has been criticised as being unsupportive and increasing stigma (Duncan, 2005).

1.12 Policy and legislative context in Scotland

Over recent decades, a range of policy and legislation has been implemented which aims to improve the protection and welfare of vulnerable children and young people in Scotland.

The policy 'Getting it Right for Every Child' (GIRFEC) (Scottish Government, 2022a) is an evidence based, national commitment to work with families in a strength and rights-based approach to support all children, young people and families, ensuring they receive the appropriate support when it is needed. GIRFEC (Scottish Executive, 2005, Scottish Government, 2022a) aims to achieve better integration and a unified approach to delivery of services, so that children and young people's well-being needs are met. GIRFEC and the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child is applicable to everyone under 18 (Scottish Government, 2022a).

The National Practice Model is used in GIRFEC, which provides a shared framework and approach to identification, assessment and analysis of a child or young person's developmental and well-being needs.

Figure 1.1 National Practice Model

The well-being indicators of Safe, Healthy, Achieving, Nurtured, Active, Respected, Responsible, and Included are based on the 54 Articles of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) (UNICEF, 1989).

The My World Triangle was influenced by the bioecological model of Bronfenbrenner and Ceci. (1994). The bioecological model provides insight as to how children's development is directly impacted by their relationships with their parents/carers, school, community and wider societal and cultural influences (Scotland Government, 2022a). The bioecological model is discussed further in section 1.13 page 19.

The Resilience Matrix enables practitioners to analyse important information when there are well-being concerns or complex situations and risks to a child or young person. It supports the identification of resilience, adversity, vulnerability and protective factors in order to understand the strengths or challenges the child or young person is facing. Resilience is a complex issue that is intertwined with their parents, families and wider environments and neighbourhoods. The matrix supports practitioners to assess how well a child or young person is coping with difficult situations. Careful assessment of the child or young person is needed to ensure that negative coping strategies are not being used in an attempt to hid their internal distress

(Hill *et al.*, 2007). Following assessment support is planned to strengthen the protective factors and resilience and to minimise adversity and vulnerabilities (Scotland Government, 2022a).

Full GIRFEC implementation throughout Scotland appears to be varied (Scottish Government, 2022a). The Scottish Government has recently refreshed the GIRFEC values for practitioners with an increased focus on children's rights, child and young person's well-being, strength-based working, early intervention, and working in partnership with parents. Whilst there is a focus in the current guidance for practitioners on the various roles (e.g. Named Person, Lead Professional) the non-statutory multi-agency coordinated plan to meet the wellbeing needs of children, young people their families have still to be embedded in practice (CELCIS, 2021, Scottish Government, 2023).

Getting it Right for Everyone (GIRFE) builds on the GIRFEC framework and is a proposed multi-agency approach to health and social care support and services from young adults to end of life care (Scottish Government, 2023a). GIRFE aims to provide early intervention, a focus on individual care needs, a holistic approach to physical and mental health, collaborative working and enable effective and proportionate information sharing. This ensures human rights are embedded in practice (Scottish Government, 2023a). Pathfinders are currently engaging with people with lived experience of the five thematic areas: people in prisons; people in addiction services; patients registered at deep end GP surgeries; older people and frailty; families with multiple and/or complex needs and young people in transition from GIRFEC to GIRFE. From summer 2025, GIRFE pathways will be nationally implemented so that individuals with multiple and/or complex needs will be supported to have their needs met. Young people and their families with complex needs should therefore expect to experience a smooth transition from GIRFEC to GIRFE (Scottish Government, 2023a).

The *Early Years Framework* (Scottish Government, 2009b) recognises the importance of promoting early brain development for children.

“The period between pregnancy and 3 years is increasingly seen as a critical period in shaping children's life chances, based on evidence of brain formation, communication and language development, and the impact of relationships formed during this period on mental health. “It is therefore also

a critical opportunity to intervene to break cycles of poor outcomes.” (Scottish Government, The Early Years Framework, 2009b, p. 8).

The *Pregnancy and Parenthood in Young People Strategy* (Scottish Government, 2016a) aims to improve the opportunities available to minimise the cycle of deprivation associated with pregnancy in young people under 18, and to provide extra support for young parents, especially those who are care experienced, up to age of 26 in line with the Children and Young People (Scotland) Act 2014 (Scottish Government, 2014a).

The *Family Nurse Partnership Programme* (FNP) is an evidence-based, home visiting programme offered to first time parents aged 19 or under, and eligible 20 to 24 year olds in some areas, until their child reaches 2 years. FNP is delivered in Scotland under a licence provision that is held by the Scottish Government (2019). The aim of the FNP programme is to improve the following outcomes: pregnancy and birth; child health and development and the family’s economic stability. (Scottish Government, 2022c). Children with an adolescent mother have particularly high poverty rates and are identified as one of the priorities for supporting families in the Tackling Child Poverty Delivery Plan (Scottish Government, 2018).

Under the *Children (Scotland) Act 1995*, 'looked-after children' (care experienced children) are defined as those in the care of their local authority. Children may become looked-after (care experienced) for various reasons, including abuse or neglect at home; disabilities that require special care; unaccompanied minors seeking asylum, those who have been illegally trafficked into the UK; or who have been involved in the youth justice system.

The *Looked After Children and Young People: We Can and Must Do Better* (Scottish Executive, 2007) report underlined that the local authority, alongside other statutory and health services, should have the same aspirations and provision of care that any good parent would provide for their own children. In addition, the report highlighted the range of emotional, practical and financial support needed for looked-after young people as they transition to adulthood and independent living. Better Health, Better Care: Action Plan (Scottish Government, 2007) advised that NHS Boards needed to demonstrate that they have a particular focus on care experienced children who, as a group, are known to be the most vulnerable in terms of health and well-being.

Staying Put Scotland (Scottish Government, 2013) was produced to ensure that during transition to independent living, care experienced young people who are particularly vulnerable were provided with the right support to improve their outcomes. Response to this guidance for young people leaving care varied widely and was dependent on the local authority area they resided in (McGhee, 2017).

The *Children and Young People (Scotland) Act (2014)* (C and YP Act) (Scottish Government, 2014a) established a list of public bodies to become 'Corporate Parents' to children and young people looked after by the local authority. The C and YP Act (Scottish Government, 2014a) recognises the need to strengthen the support for families and introduced legislation affecting all children's universal services with the aim of meeting all children's well-being needs. Three main parts of the Act directly relate to the children in care population. Part 9 specifies how corporate parents should promote CEP interests and provide opportunities for them (Scottish Government, 2014a). Furthermore, the legislation aims to strengthen support offered to looked-after children, young people and care leavers to ensure they have the same opportunities available as other children and young people. Part 10 of the C and YP Act (Scottish Government, 2016b) further outlines that young people who leave care after the age of 16 can receive further local authority support (aftercare) up until they reach age 26. Health and Social Care Partnerships will be encouraged to provide continuing support to CEP and will also have to provide guidance and assistance to care leavers up to the age of 26 where this is required. Part 11 of the Act addresses the Continuing Care law which enables young people at the age of 16 residing either in foster, residential or kinship the right to remain in that or a similar care placement until they reach 21 years of age. However, it remains unclear how this would be achieved when a CEP becomes pregnant. Clarity is required about how the Scottish Government will ensure that there is provision available for ongoing supported accommodation to meet the needs of teenage parents leaving care.

The impact of the C and YP Act (Scottish Government, 2014a) for improving outcomes for children and young people requires further evidence. The proposal of a Named Person acting as a clear point of contact for every child from birth until the age of 18 being incorporated into statute was overruled by the Supreme Court in 2016 due to concerns that proposals around information-sharing breached the right to privacy and a family life under the European Convention on Human Rights (Council of Europe,

1950). Criticism of the C and YP Act (Scottish Government, 2014a) is aimed at the lack of evidence to support the legislation. Mellon (2015) considers that more should be done by corporate parents to support and reduce poor outcomes for children in care, rather than intervening in families where the vast majority of parents are doing their utmost for their children.

The *Quality Framework for Children and Young People in Need of Care and Protection* (2018) supports multi-agency evaluation to ensure agencies meet the needs of children and young people, including children looked-after and leaving care. Scotland has almost 15,000 children in its 'care system', many of whom have had distressing and often traumatic experiences (Independent Care Review, 2020). Whilst there is a range of legislation and previous policy documents, the perception of available support for care experienced young people is mixed. It was discovered that 45% of care experienced young people were critical of their pathway planning process to prepare them for leaving care. Despite the many challenges care leavers encountered, over 50% of young people had not engaged with their throughcare or aftercare support worker (Dixon *et al.*, 2015; Independent Care Review, 2020). According to Hill (2013) and the Independent Care Review (2020) data on CEP people remains very weak, as many studies are historical, making it is more difficult to understand the needs of the population or to be able to reflect on any improvements. More still needs to be done to demonstrate improvements in the life chances of looked-after children, young people and care leavers through jointly fulfilling responsibilities as corporate parents (Independent Care Review, 2020).

House moves for young people are to be expected as they progress in their life course development, but for CEP house moves may be due to less positive reasons and can result in homelessness (Biehal and Wade, 1999). Wade and Dixon (2006) found the impact of poor mental health, offending behaviour, substance misuse and going missing from care all add to the difficulties CEP had in their adjustment to this transition. The Care Inspectorate (2020) highlighted the need for specialist services to coordinate the development of leaving care policies and services to direct appropriate support to care experienced young people in regards to their housing, life skills and financial support. However, practice to address these concerns has varied considerably in the different local authorities (Scottish Government, 2022a).

The Promise report (The Independent Care Review, 2020) reflected what over 5,500 care experienced children and adults, families and the workforce told the Care Review. *The Promise* (Independent Care Review, 2020) describes the need to help families stay safely together with the appropriate workforce, improved assets within the community and increased capacity across the whole of the care system. *The Promise Youth Justice* report (Promise Scotland, 2020) aims to address the youth justice needs and seeks to reduce the criminalisation of care experienced young people. *The Promise Implementation Plan* (Scottish Government, 2022b) notes that children being raised in poverty are more likely to be named on the child protection register and removed from their families. *The Promise Implementation Plan* (Scottish Government, 2022b) alongside the Scottish Government (2021b) *Covid Recovery Strategy* and the *Tackling Child Poverty Delivery Plan 2022-26* (Scottish Government, 2022c), plans to break the cycle of child poverty. As part of the Promise implementation, *The Plan 21-24* (The Promise Scotland, 2021) children and young people with experience of care are eligible for support through the amended *Education (Additional Support for Learning) (Scotland) Act 2009*. Furthermore, schools are responsible for ensuring that care experienced young people progress to positive further education or employment opportunities (Scottish Government, 2021c).

The Promise is to be fully implemented by 2030 (The Promise Oversight Board, 2022). Although progress is being made, it is recognised that the pace of progress and scale of improvements needs to be increased and that robust evaluation is needed to monitor the change (McGhee, 2017; The Promise Oversight Board, 2022).

There have been some wide range policy intentions over recent decades to address the issues that care experienced children and young people have encountered, but according to McGhee (2017) there is a considerable gap between policy ambitions and consistent improvements in practice.

1.13 Theoretical framework - Bronfenbrenner's Bioecological System

The bioecological model is one of the most accepted explanations regarding the influence of social environments on human development (Bronfenbrenner and Ceci, 1994). Bronfenbrenner and Ceci (1994) focussed on the environment which was explicitly or implicitly considered to be a crucial mechanism in the child and young person's development. The Bioecological Model influenced the My World Triangle

which is central to the GIRFEC National Practice Model (see section 1.12 page 13). It is based on the concept that a child and young person's development is influenced by the relationships with parents, then school and community environment ('What I need from the people who look after me') and finally relationships with the wider society and culture ('My Wider World'). There is an influential interaction between relationships and environments as well as the child and young person's development and resilience. A broad overview of five systems within the model is illustrated in Figure 1.2

Figure 1.2 Bronfenbrenner's Bioecological Systems theoretical model.

Bronfenbrenner's bioecological model perceives the individual's environment as five discrete, but inter-related systems: the microsystem, the mesosystem, the exosystem, the macrosystem and the chronosystem (see Table 1.2). The most influential level for a child or young person is the microsystem. This level incorporates the most immediate environmental settings which have an impact on the developing child or young person, such as family and school.

	Systems	Description/Explanation of Systems
1.	Microsystem	Composed of the groups who have direct contact with the individuals i.e. family, partners, foster carers, family nurses, teachers, social workers
2.	Mesosystem	Focuses on the relationships between the groups from the microsystem to the exosystem; such as interconnections between residential/foster carers, and school systems/ social work systems
3.	Exosystem	Relates to factors of the bioecological systems that affect an individual's life indirectly. Examples include neighbourhood violence, which may indirectly affect the individual. Another example could be the kind of training of teachers, social work and health services, which in turn impacts on the care received.
4.	Macrosystem	Contains those cultural and elements that affect the individual and everyone around them. i.e. socioeconomic status or the stigma of teenage pregnancy
5.	Chronosystem	This refers to the stage of life that the individual is in or situations they are going through. i.e. transitions, life events, teenage brain development

Table 1.2 Five Systems: Bronfenbrenner's bioecological systems theoretical model Bronfenbrenner and Ceci (1994).

Due to changes in the GIRFEC policy (Scottish Government, 2022) during the writing of this thesis and a criticism that, unlike the bioecological model, GIRFEC does not consider the influence of public policy and national laws that influence children and young people's health, this current research is underpinned by Bronfenbrenner's bioecological systems theoretical model (as mentioned in section 1.12 page 13). Positive outcomes for care experienced young people transitioning from care are influenced by professional practice, social supports and social structures within their environment (Pinkerton, 2021). The bioecological model was used as the theoretical framework for this study as it considers how the impact of social environments can be applied to the CEP development. The model supports exploration of how formal and informal supports within their community setting (micro, meso and exosystem) enable or impede CEP transition to setting up home and becoming a parent. CEP require access to various resources to meet their social, parenting and developmental needs in order to achieve their life goals. The framework also provides the opportunity to consider how practitioners are enabled to support the CEP needs through national

policy and legislation and to understand how culture (macrosystem) influences the micro, meso and exosystem, the individual's historical perspective and also the biographical context (chronosystem) (Boon *et al.* 2012).

Christensen (2010) criticises Bronfenbrenner for not having included resilience into his theory. Resilience considers that individuals have the capacity to overcome obstacles through their capacity to be optimistic, goal-orientated, persistent and optimistic (Engler, 2007 cited in Christensen, 2010). Christensen suggests this would have provided a greater understanding of how some people have overcome traumas in their lives. Boon *et al.* (2012) argued that Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory has assisted in benchmarking social resilience through practitioners identifying, targeting and reviewing interventions.

1.14 My personal journey

My interest in research of care experienced young people started when I was employed as a team leader for health visitors and school nurses from 2002 until 2013. The school nursing team were responsible for assessing the health needs assessments of looked after young people in residential children's homes as per the CEL 16 (2009) guidance (Scottish Government, 2009a). I became aware from the school nurses and from visiting the young residents themselves that the young people had very little knowledge about sexual health and relationships, or that the knowledge they held was inaccurate. Unfortunately, some of the young women were taking personal risks with their sexual health and some perhaps due to having been sexually abused themselves as children, normalised the risks and appeared unable to implement safe boundaries. Anecdotally the support workers in the children's residential homes felt very unsure about whether it was acceptable within their organisation for them to discuss sexual health and relationship topics with the young residents. Research in the area was limited and as part of my Master's in Child Care and Child Protection programme, I conducted a mixed methods research study into the area of residential workers' understanding and support to care experienced young peoples' sexual health and relationships needs.

In 2013, when working as a Family Nurse Supervisor with first-time teenage parents I again worked with some of the same care experienced young people I had met in my previous role. Within the Family Nurse Partnership programme there was a high

percentage of CEP. The teenage parent's challenges and successes during their time of transitioning out of care and becoming a parent, with little social support, was highlighted to me during supervision with the family nurses.

As a paediatric nurse, health visitor and mother, reducing inequalities and the subject of child development/teenage brain development, social support networks, and child and maternal health are areas of particular interest to me. I recognise the need for research to gain meaningful insight into the experiences of CEP. By undertaking a PhD, I was keen to explore what looked after teenage parents perceived to be supportive or challenging when transitioning out of care and becoming a parent.

1.15 Structure of the thesis

The presentation of the thesis takes the reader through each step of the study. This introductory section has provided a broad overview of the background, setting the context for this research. This includes the global prevalence of teenage pregnancy and how national policy and legislation seeks to improve the outcomes for looked after children and young people, the psychosocial impact of becoming a teenage parent, the particular health and social challenges for CEP, and the implications for both teenage parents and their children. This chapter has presented an overview of my personal journey and my interest in exploring in detail care experienced adolescents' experiences of being cared for within the care system and their transition from leaving care and becoming parents.

Chapter 2 provides a review of the literature. The review initially focused on literature exploring the reasons for the higher incidences of teenage pregnancy in care experienced young people. Thereafter, a more detailed review of the literature is provided to consider what social supports are in place for CEP and what challenges are encountered during their transition to parenthood and leaving their care setting.

Chapter 3 presents the methodology chosen for the research design and the methods used to conduct the study including the key ethical considerations requiring to be addressed in the research design. Chapter 4 presents the main findings from the study along with details of the process for data analysis. Interpretation of the findings are explained and supported through the use of a selection of direct quotes from study participants. Chapter 5 provides the discussion of the research findings in the context

of the available body of literature. Chapter 6 presents reflexivity, the challenges, strengths and limitations of the study, implications of the findings for practice, recommendations for practice, policy and areas for future research. The reference list is documented in Chapter 7. Appendices provide additional information and evidence to increase the reader's understanding of the study in Chapter 8.

Chapter 2. Literature review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the narrative literature review conducted in a structured approach to contextualise and inform the study. The literature was examined to understand any relevant outcome or findings, to identify any conflict or debate and to identify gaps in the body of literature to inform the focus and research design of the current study.

2.2 Literature review process

A comprehensive search strategy is required to gather the appropriate literature (Gray, 2018). The Population, Intervention, Comparison (where applicable), Outcome(s) and Study design (PICOS) model was used as a search strategy tool to identify appropriate qualitative and quantitative literature (Erisken and Frandson, 2018) and to develop the literature review question: How are care experienced teenage parents who are in or have left care establishments supported?

Literature was critically reviewed to elicit what is already known and to investigate gaps in an evidence base in relation to factors that support or challenge looked after teenage parents (CEP) in or leaving care. Databases CINAHL, APA PsycArticles, SocINDEX, Medline, SAGE and Science Direct were searched and Boolean operators applied.

Search terms (see Table 2.1) were combined with Boolean operators of AND, BUT, and OR and the selection based on the relevance to the population of care experienced pregnant/ parents.

Search Terms

Looked after	Teenage mother
Foster care	Teenage fathers
State care	Teenage parent
Kinship care	Teenage pregnancy
Care leaver	Young parent
Residential care	Young father
Out of home care	Adolescent mothers
Care Experienced	Young mothers

Table 2.1 Literature review search terms.

The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989) signified a change in terms of how Children's Rights are supported, protected and promoted globally, which in turn has influenced international legislation and policy. A decision to only include research studies from this date and to include a range of relevant legislation and policy documents in the review was therefore made. Abstracts were considered for their relevance and full-text papers sourced as required (Polit and Beck, 2012). Reference lists within the literature supported the identification of seminal authors and a further range of relevant papers. Research that solely aimed to prevent teenage pregnancy in care settings were excluded. Studies that did not specifically aim to research the experiences of care experienced teenage parents (CEP) were only included when their experiences were represented in the study.

Due to the scarcity of UK literature, research from other countries with similar child welfare systems were included if the studies were written in English. Most of these studies were conducted in the USA, with studies from England, Sweden, Canada, Australia, Argentina and Spain also included.

Studies from a positivist and interpretivist approach were included to gain greater insight to the phenomenon, the effectiveness of any previous interventions and to understand the perceptions of CEP and relevant professionals of the challenges and supports within the CEP's environment. This review includes research mainly from an interpretivist perspective, with methods mostly involving individual interviews and focus groups. The majority of the research focused on the views of young care experienced mothers. The search strategy is documented in Appendix 1 (section 8.1).

The Critical Appraisals Skill Programme (CASP) (Long *et al.*, 2020) tools were used to support appraisal of the literature. A total of 126 studies were included in the final review. From the literature review, table 2.2 illustrates the following range of themes and sub themes which emerged.

Table 2.2 Key themes identified from the review.

The search and review were initially conducted at the beginning of the study and repeated August 2022 to capture any recent studies.

2.3 Epidemiology

Mezey *et al.*'s (2015) literature review highlighted that despite teenage pregnancy rates are falling in the UK, there has been no similar decline for care experienced young people. It is frequently identified within the literature that young people in care still become parents earlier than their peers (Biehal *et al.*, 1994; Gelder, 2002; Courtney *et al.*, 2011; Purtell *et al.*, 2019; Bermea *et al.*, 2020; Gill *et al.*, 2020).

2.3.1 Pregnancy rates in CEP

Population data on birth rates for CEP is not routinely collected (Dworsky, 2015; Fallon and Broadhurst, 2015; Purtell *et al.*, 2020). Although approximations have varied, most studies indicate that female CEP exhibit birth rates significantly higher than their peers in the general population (Pecora *et al.*, 2003; Vinnerljung *et al.*, 2007; Svoboda *et al.*, 2012; Matta Oshima *et al.*, 2013; Putman-Hornstein *et al.*, 2015; Brannstrom *et al.*, 2016; Gardner *et al.*, 2017; Shpiegel *et al.*, 2017; Combs *et al.*, 2018a; Shpiegel and

Cascardi, 2018; Eastman *et al.*, 2019b; King *et al.*, 2019; Purtell *et al.*, 2020; Allik *et al.*, 2021).

A UK study using a mixed method approach by Roberts *et al.* (2019) investigated supports provided to care experienced young parents in which social care professionals and the parents participated. Roberts *et al.* (2019) revealed the average age for becoming a parent was 19 years for males and females. Similar findings of increased rates of teenage pregnancy were identified in a national audit in Wales by Craine *et al.* (2014). The authors audited the records of 800 care experienced young women and compared their pregnancy rates to 72,980 non-care experienced teenagers. Craine *et al.* (2014) found a conception rate of 5% in 14–17 years olds in care, compared to 0.8% in non-care experienced young people.

A longitudinal USA study by King and Van Wert (2017) aimed to predict factors associated with early childbirth. They identified that from 30,339 care experienced adolescents 18.3% (5,567) gave birth to their first child before their 20th birthday. Another large-scale longitudinal USA study by Courtney *et al.* (2011) evidenced that by late adolescence, 139 (62%) of the male participants and 238 (71%) of the female participants had at least one child. In Australia, Purtell *et al.*'s (2019) longitudinal study of young people leaving care found that 20% of 126 participants had been pregnant and 15% had children.

The above research suggests that early childbirth for the care experienced population has a high prevalence in many countries within the developed world.

2.3.2 *Predisposing factors*

This section describes the multifactorial reasons for the high prevalence of early pregnancy in care experienced young people.

There is evidence that CEP have reduced school enrolment rates and a high incidence of school exclusion (Tyrer *et al.*, 2005; Barn and Mantovani, 2007) and this impacts on their sexual health and relationship education (Corlyon and McGuire, 1999; Tyrer *et al.*, 2005; Chase *et al.*, 2006; Barn and Mantovani, 2007; Maxwell and Chase, 2008; Connolly *et al.*, 2012; Pecora *et al.*, 2003; King *et al.*, 2014; Mezey *et al.*, 2015; Aparicio, 2017; Albertson *et al.*, 2018; Font *et al.*, 2019; King *et al.*, 2019).

Access to reliable contraception can also be challenging for young people in care (Connolly *et al.*, 2012; Albertson *et al.*, 2018; Combs *et al.*, 2018a). Systematic barriers to reliable contraception and sexual health education were identified by Connolly *et al.* (2012) in their review of the literature. Connolly *et al.* (2012) found fear of judgement, emotional well-being, placement instability and age when entered care impacted on their sexual health. King *et al.*'s (2019) descriptive study in the USA reviewed data from 18,090 young women who had experienced care during 1999-2010. King *et al.* (2019) demonstrated that CEP, impacted by unstable care placements and a history of having absconded from their care setting, increased their vulnerability and risk of an unintended pregnancy. Sexual risk-taking behaviours is linked to sexual and physical abuse (Combs *et al.*, 2018b) and it is considered that young people in care would particularly benefit from increased sexual health advice and support (Ahrens *et al.*, 2013; Crowne *et al.*, 2012; King *et al.*, 2019).

A lack of trusting relationships with a dependable adult to discuss sexual health and relationships with (Aparicio, 2017; Matta Oshima *et al.*, 2018) has been attributed to high CEP pregnancy rates. Additional research has shown that social care practitioners have lacked a clear sexual health policy in their workplace and were often reluctant to discuss sexual health and relationships (Barn and Mantovani, 2007; Aparicio *et al.*, 2015; Aparicio, 2017; Albertson, 2018). Carers have also been found to lack knowledge about sexual health information and services (Chase *et al.*, 2003; Love *et al.*, 2005; Aparicio, 2017; Albertson *et al.*, 2018; Matta Oshima *et al.*, 2018; Rouse *et al.*, 2020). Albertson *et al.* (2018) discovered that access to contraception was further compounded by the carers not having the legal responsibility to access health care for the young person. Zarate-Alva *et al.*'s (2018) study, conducted in Spain, argues contraception information, advice and access was not the issue, but it was the CEP teenage brain development and low executive functioning of the participants that made their contraceptive use inconsistent.

Font *et al.*'s (2019) USA study reviewed administration data from child welfare systems in Wisconsin. Data relating to 71,824 vulnerable children included information on 4,040 females in foster care. The data was compared to other vulnerable teenagers who had not been removed from their families. Font *et al.* (2019) found a significant intergenerational link to teenage pregnancy. The study used hazard ratios (HR) for teenage pregnancy and evidenced that pregnancy rates for CEP were higher prior to

foster care and also shortly after leaving foster care following rehabilitation back to their parents' care (HR =3.94 prior to foster care entry and HR=3.03 on rehabilitation home to family following foster care versus HR =1.87 for young women within foster care). Foster care was seen as a protective factor against teenage pregnancy; however, a further finding by Font *et al.* (2019) was that for every move during their time in care, the risk of pregnancy for each placement move rose by 4%.

Corlyon and McGuire (1999) reported that poor self-esteem and the desire to be accepted, led care experienced young people to feel pressured to engage in early or unwanted sexual activity. Mendes's (2009) literature review evidenced that a history of sexual abuse, and the ensuing mental health difficulties, may have caused difficulties in successfully negotiating safe sexual relationships. Emotional well-being concerns were identified as a contributing factor in other studies too. Albertson *et al.*'s (2018) exploratory study conducted in three states, with 86 foster and kinship caregivers, explored barriers to preventing teenage pregnancies. Albertson *et al.*'s (2018) thematic analysis identified mental health difficulties further impacted on positive sexual health. Likewise, Coleman-Cowger *et al.*'s (2011) USA study aimed to compare care experienced young people receiving substance abuse treatment with young people who were not care experienced. The authors sought to understand if there were any differences between non-care experienced and care experienced young people's mental health, substance use and exposure to victimisation, and if these could be a predictor of pregnancy. Data on 17,124 adolescents included information on 366 (2%) of young people who had been in care. Coleman-Cowger *et al.* (2011) revealed that difficulties associated with substance use did not differ between the two groups. However, in the foster care sample, high mental distress scores predicted increased risks of pregnancy. The findings of Coleman- Cowger *et al.* (2011) could have been more robust had there been a more comparable size of CEP participants.

PettyJohn *et al.*'s (2021) USA cross-sectional survey of 136 female foster cared adolescent women in Pennsylvania appears to be the first study to explore the experience of reproductive coercion (RC) in this care experienced population. Reproductive coercion is defined by the researchers as the use of IPV, whereby the perpetrator controls the female's reproductive health and forces an unwanted pregnancy. PettyJohn *et al.* (2021) discovered reproductive coercion by older males

was experienced by nearly a third of the participants surveyed. Teenage pregnancy in foster care associated with RC, was found to be 5 times likelier than peers not exposed to IPV. Further evidence of reproductive coercion was also found in another USA study (Herrman *et al.*, 2016) who highlighted incidences of contraception sabotage.

The research in this section evidences a broad range of issues which increase the risks of teenage pregnancy for young people in or leaving care. Evidence has identified that most CEP pregnancies were unplanned (Chase *et al.*, 2006; Courtney *et al.*, 2011; Pecora *et al.*, 2003). However, other studies have identified there can be an explicit desire to become a young parent (Alberston *et al.*, 2018; Courtney *et al.*, 2020) and the reasons for this will be discussed further in the next section.

2.4 Being a Care Experienced Teenage Parent

Despite the majority of the research studies focusing on the negative aspects of early parenting amongst CEP, some research revealed that CEP are committed to being good parents, find joy in parenthood (Narendorf *et al.*, 2013; Aparicio *et al.*, 2015; Aparicio *et al.*, 2018) and find the transition to parenthood rewarding (Rutman *et al.*, 2002; Chase *et al.*, 2003; Knight *et al.*, 2006b; SmithBattle, 2007; Pryce and Samuels, 2010; Connolly *et al.*, 2012; Mendes *et al.*, 2014a; Radey *et al.*, 2016; Aparicio, 2017; Datta *et al.*, 2017; Schelbe and Geiger, 2017).

2.4.1 Benefits of early parenthood for CEP

Schelbe and Geiger's (2017) ethnographic study in the USA examined the parenting experience of 21 female CEP and 12 male CEP. The researchers discovered that despite the fear of services involvement and lack of support, parenthood was seen as an achievable and desirable goal with the participants feeling joy and pride in their children. Due to the small number of participants in the study from one county in the USA, and participants being predominantly from an African American background, the study's findings may not be transferable to other settings. Other studies have also shown similar positive perceptions of early parenthood by CEP, where having a child provided them with the opportunity to belong to a family unit, to have someone of their own to love and to be loved (Biehal and Wade, 1996; Knight *et al.*, 2006b; Pryce and Samuels, 2010). Likewise, Chase *et al.*'s (2006) UK interpretive study used structured in-depth interviews with 63 young males and females and revealed that CEP's earlier

experiences of exclusion and stigma resulted in them viewing their pregnancy positively.

According to Corlyon and McGuire (1999), CEP in the UK perceived early parenthood as compensation for a lack of care in their own lives, provided them with someone to care for (Chase *et al.*, 2006), reduced the fear of loneliness on leaving care (Biehal and Wade, 1996) and met their emotional needs (Connelly *et al.*, 2012). Some CEP thought that having a child would have provided them with unconditional love (Chase *et al.*, 2003; Barn and Mantovani, 2007; Maxwell *et al.*, 2011). In a small phenomenological UK study, Maxwell *et al.* (2011) interviewed 6 female CEP in 2 local authority leaving care teams in London. This study aimed to explore CEP's experiences of motherhood with particular focus on the mother–child relationship. Data was analysed using interpretative phenomenological analysis. The CEP described motherhood as being a positive and healing process and hoped they could give their child a better childhood than they themselves had experienced (Maxwell *et al.*, 2011). Similarly, Courtney *et al.*'s (2011) study examined female CEP's perceived needs and perceptions of their support levels. This large longitudinal study in the USA, found nearly a quarter of the 124 female CEP had intended to become pregnant to prove they could provide their own children with a happier childhood than their own. This is consistent with the findings of Pryce and Samuel's (2010) qualitative exploratory study, also set in the USA, which included 15 female CEP leaving care, who described becoming a parent as their first opportunity to experience a valuable relationship.

Schelbe and Geiger's (2017) USA research identified that the development of their mothering identity offered CEP the chance to gain increased confidence. Other studies confirmed the CEP felt an increased sense of control and stability in their lives (Knight *et al.*, 2006b; Barn and Mantovani, 2007; Rolfe, 2008; Narendorf *et al.*, 2013; Bermea *et al.*, 2019). Becoming a parent was seen as a chance to compensate for their own often poor experiences of being parented (Corlyon and McGuire, 1999; Chase *et al.*, 2006; Dworsky and Courtney, 2010).

In summary, the sense of having someone to love to compensate for their own negative childhood experiences, and the ability to build a new and purposeful identity as a parent, appears to influence CEP's choice to become a parent.

2.4.2 Aspirations to be a good parent

Research has frequently demonstrated that CEP are motivated to make lifestyle changes (Chase, *et al.*, 2006; Barn and Mantovani, 2007; Rolfe, 2008; Pryce and Samuels, 2010; Connolly *et al.*, 2012; Schelbe and Geiger, 2017; Aparicio, 2017; Bermea *et al.*, 2019). This section considers the CEP's drive to be a good parent.

Studies have shown that whilst CEP were initially affected by stress as they adjusted to parenting and confronted their own unmet childhood needs (Pryce and Samuels, 2010), they were also found to be motivated to provide a better future for themselves and their child (Pryce and Samuels, 2010; Schelbe and Geiger, 2017; Aparicio, 2017). The CEP in Rutman *et al.*'s (2001) Canadian qualitative research, overwhelmingly described their child as having saved them from their precarious circumstances and given them a life purpose.

Bermea *et al.*'s (2019) USA study was conducted in 4 different residential foster care settings to explore how 39 female CEP experienced pregnancy and parenthood. The study was implemented using a resiliency framework. Thematic analysis demonstrated that all CEP shared a determination to make positive lifestyle changes to enable their child to have a healthy future. The CEP benefitted from the social support from the other CEP living in residential foster care, which developed their resilience and prepared them for motherhood. Similarly, Aparico *et al.*'s (2018) small phenomenological study in the USA with 6 female CEP found similar findings of the CEP's motivation to provide their children with a positive childhood. Aparico *et al.*'s (2018) research used 18 in-depth qualitative interviews and employed Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis to explore the perspective of motherhood among CEP who had given birth as teenagers while living in foster care. The CEP discussed their commitment to ensure their children would not be abused or become part of the foster care system (Aparico, *et al.*, 2018). Radey *et al.*'s (2016) qualitative USA study of 15 CEP and 14 service providers found that, in an attempt to provide a better childhood for their child, CEP often overcompensated for their feelings of inadequacy by purchasing their children expensive items, despite their financial struggles.

Tyrer *et al.*'s (2005) UK interpretive study appeared to be one of the very few studies that aimed to explore the experiences of male CEP, to understand if their needs were recognised and if appropriate services were accessible. In this study 16 male CEP

between the ages of 15-23, who were all fathers in their teenage years participated along with 78 local authority and service providers; however, opportunistic sampling was used, which may have led to some bias with the findings being unrepresentative of male CEP not engaging with throughcare and aftercare services. The authors concluded that the CEP's desire to be a good father contrasted with the parenting stress of not being able to financially provide for their child and this often resulted in a poor or non-existent relationship with them. The study found that the male CEP felt that existing support services were too bureaucratic and inflexible to meet their parenting needs. Tyrer *et al.* (2005) has made a significant contribution to the experience of male CEP, due to the paucity of studies focusing on the need of young care experienced fathers.

Despite the many challenges, studies have shown that some CEP view being a teenage parent as a positive choice (Corlyon and McGuire, 1999; Wade, 2008; Chase *et al.*, 2006; Radey *et al.*, 2016; Aparicio *et al.*, 2018). There are few studies that capture the views and experiences of male CEP. Moreover, there is the need for further studies to consider, from both the CEP perspective and also wider children's service workers about what supports or challenges a CEP to be a 'good parent'.

2.4.3 Parenting skills

Consideration is given in this section as to how CEP are prepared for parenthood, their parenting knowledge and how they learned their parenting skills.

Aparicio's (2017) phenomenological study of 6 female CEP in the USA found the lack of positive parenting role models impacted on how the CEPs parented their child. A further study conducted in the USA by Courtney *et al.* (2011), used surveys to explore 359 CEP's knowledge about parenting and being a "good parent". Few CEPs in Courtney *et al.*'s (2011) study identified their social worker as a source of information; despite many of the CEP having described difficult relationships with their birth parents, 28% affirmed their biological parents taught them about parenting; 11% learned from their foster carer; 27% from a grandparent or other extended family member, and 14% received parenting information from a friend. In contrast, Radey *et al.*'s (2016) findings revealed that CEP did not learn parenting skills from their own parents. Radey *et al.* (2016) discussed how CEP were not supported in preparation for parenthood, with some young parents having only learnt about caring for a child

from their experiences of looking after younger siblings or babysitting. Similarly, other studies indicated that CEP's birth mothers were often viewed as being 'anti-role models' and served only as examples of how not to parent (Rolfe, 2008; Pryce and Samuels, 2010).

Connolly *et al.* (2012) and Aparicio *et al.* (2015) identified that a lack of role models increased the CEP's feelings of vulnerability, as most of the participants did not know how to provide a caring and safe environment for their children. However, Radey *et al.* (2016), indicated concerns that CEP showed a lack of awareness of child development and held unrealistic expectations about their child's behaviour. In addition, they sometimes wrongly linked the child's normal developmental behaviour as being a negative characteristic. Interestingly, Svoboda *et al.*'s (2012) USA systematic review of the evidence, indicated that despite reduced family support, CEP experienced similar parenting challenges in knowledge and skills in infant care and development as non-care experienced teenage peers.

Holtrop *et al.*'s, (2018) research highlighted the requirement for supporting CEP in their parenting to promote their child to form a secure attachment to the CEP. Geiger and Schelbe (2014) also highlighted that parenting interventions are considered a key resource for providing services and improving outcomes for CEP and their children. Schelbe and Geiger's (2017) study evidenced that the majority of CEP had spoken positively of having attended parenting classes to develop their skills and gain peer support. Several studies, however, indicated that CEP were reluctant to attend parenting groups (Courtney *et al.*, 2011; Aparicio, 2017; Aparicio *et al.*, 2018) or engage with supportive services (Chase *et al.*, 2006; Maxwell *et al.*, 2011; Siversns and Morgans, 2019). Aparicio *et al.* (2018) argued that becoming a nurturing parent could not be taught in an educational setting and that supportive social networks beyond their own immediate family was essential to help them gain confidence in their own parenting abilities. Other studies agreed that robust social support and positive relationships are essential for CEP during the critical period during pregnancy and following the birth of their child (Geiger and Schelbe, 2014; Aparicio *et al.*, 2015).

The lack of positive role models in the CEP life, and their increased vulnerability with low social support, suggests further research is needed to understand CEP's perceptions of how their parenting practice is supported.

2.4.4 *Fear of the cycle being repeated*

Due to their own experiences, CEP are often fearful of child protection services involvement (Radey *et al.*, 2016; Aparicio, 2017; Schelbe and Geiger, 2017). The fear of the 'care cycle' being repeated, of their own children going into care is a common theme emerging from the research (Knight *et al.*, 2006b; Rolfe, 2008; Pryce and Samuels, 2010; Shelbe *et al.*, 2016; Aparicio *et al.*, 2018; Dandy *et al.*, 2020). Some CEP can see parenthood as a new beginning and an opportunity to identify as a parent rather than a victim or survivor of abuse (Aparicio *et al.*, 2015). Female CEP (Biehal *et al.*, 1995; Maxwell *et al.*, 2011; Radey *et al.*, 2016) discussed that despite the CEP's intention to overcome intergenerational patterns of abuse and dependency, without support, CEP could become overwhelmed by motherhood, due to their unmet expectations, experience of domestic abuse as a mother and their poor mental health.

2.4.5 *Challenges to mental health*

CEP are more likely than their non-care experienced peers to have suffered from neglect and trauma and have an increased incidence of diagnosed mental health problems (Barn and Mantovani, 2007; Coleman-Gowger *et al.*, 2011; Narendorf *et al.*, 2013; Botchway *et al.*, 2014; Roberts *et al.*, 2017; Wilson *et al.*, 2017).

Bermea *et al.*'s (2019) study found CEP adjustment to pregnancy and becoming a new parent forced the CEP to confront their own traumatic childhood and increased their sense of loss and vulnerability. Narendorf *et al.*'s (2013) USA qualitative research interviewed 28 CEP who had experienced emotional problems. Most of the CEP were mothers (n = 20). The researchers aimed to understand the CEP's perspective of managing their mood and parenting. The CEP in Narendorf *et al.*'s (2013) study, highlighted that the side effects of their prescribed medications for low mood during pregnancy and in the post-natal stage caused some female CEP to discontinue treatments. The CEP discussed how their low mood caused them to emotionally withdraw or fail to provide basic care for their children and how the CEP's unregulated emotions negatively impacted on their child's wellbeing (Narendorf *et al.*, 2013).

There appears to be little research on how CEP who suffered childhood sexual abuse coped when they become mothers. Leeners *et al.*'s (2006) systematic review of 43 research papers found that sexual abuse survivors often suffered from low mood and

anxiety during pregnancy. Repressed emotions re-surfaced during pregnancy, birth and/or parenting of their infant. CEP may therefore find it difficult to manage their own emotional needs and that of their child. Furthermore, Eastman and Putnam-Hornstein (2019) found 68% of participants in their study of 2,094 mothers in foster care reported childhood sexual abuse. Studies considered that the CEP's mental health problems may require psychological support to successfully parent and to prevent the involvement of child protection services (Roberts *et al.* 2017; Eastman and Putnam-Hornstein, 2019).

A UK retrospective, cross sectional survey by Botchway *et al.* (2014) used the baseline questionnaire for the Millennium Cohort Study (MCS) and explored the sociodemographic and health outcomes of previous care experienced mothers. Mothers were identified via child benefit registers for children born during 2000-2002. The researchers identified 291 mothers who confirmed they had been in care before the age of 17 and they were compared to those mothers who were not care experienced. The authors used a validated malaise inventory tool (Rodgers *et al.*, 1999) to assess the mother's symptoms of depression. Botchway *et al.* (2014) revealed that CEP were more likely than the non-care experienced group to have symptoms of depression. However, the authors acknowledge a study limitation was that the findings may be unrepresentative of CEP, due to the significant number of CEP who did not participate in the Millennium Cohort study (MCS).

A large-scale USA study by Dworsky and DeCoursey (2009) reviewed the administrative data for 4,590 pregnant and parenting young people who had been in foster care during 1998 and 2006. In this study 84% were female (n = 3,855) and 16% were male (n = 735). Dworsky and DeCoursey (2009) found that one-third of the female CEP, and two-fifths of the male CEP, were identified as requiring mental health services. Similarly, Wilson *et al.* (2017) in a USA quantitative study, involved 42 female CEP, with an exclusion criteria of postnatal depression diagnosis. Twenty of the CEP had been cared for in non-kinship care, and 22 were CEP who had experienced kinship care. The authors used two validated tools to assess the CEP's relationship quality and depressive symptoms. In their findings 90% of CEP in kinship care felt supported by their family, as opposed to only 25% of the CEP not in kinship care. In addition, 80% of CEP not in kinship care met the clinical criteria for depression compared to the 36% of the CEP in kinship care. Wilson *et al.* (2017) suggested that

improved family relationships amongst the kinship care group produced positive health benefits, reduced loneliness and anxiety and increased feelings of optimism about their future. The findings showed overall 57% of the CEP were impacted by depression. Wilson *et al.* (2017) recommended with the majority of the CEP being assessed as clinically depressed, that consideration should be given to provide targeted preventative mental health interventions for CEP to promote their, and their children's emotional well-being.

Barn and Mantovani's (2007) U.K empirical study used a mixed methods design to explore the risks and vulnerabilities faced by a group of female CEP on leaving care. The data were collected in six English local authority social services departments and 55 ethnic minority female CEPs were involved. Findings from Barn and Mantovani's (2007) study found that nearly a third of the participants had emotional problems and disclosed that they self-harmed. As there is a high proportion of young people who do not engage with leaving care service (Farrugia, 2015), there may be the potential of bias in the study with non-engaging CEP's views being unrepresented. Furthermore, Barn and Mantovani, (2007) acknowledge the sample may not be representative due to a wide disparity of response from the local authority areas.

Roberts *et al.*'s (2017) mixed method study in Wales (n=596) analysed data from social work's child adoption records of young parents whose children had been placed for adoption. Male CEP (n=45) and female CEP (n=97) were identified. The researchers found that mental health difficulties were a concern for 87% of the CEP, with depression, self-harm, suicide attempts, and drug and alcohol dependency evidenced. The authors reflect that the CEP, despite their emotional needs being known during their time in care, did not receive the appropriate support to improve their outcomes. Roberts *et al.* (2017) acknowledge the potential for selection bias, as the analysis considers the findings of a particular subgroup of CEP.

According to Botchway *et al.* (2014) and Bermea *et al.* (2019) female CEP were often single parents and were frequently isolated from their peers as they dedicated most of their time to parenting (Bermea *et al.*, 2019). Female CEP often valued peer support from other CEP who have similar experiences (Haight *et al.*, 2009; Radey *et al.*, 2016; Bermea *et al.*, 2019). Conversely, Rutman *et al.* (2002) found care experienced young mothers often spoke critically of other CEP, in an attempt for them to be seen more

positively by their social worker. Radey *et al.* (2016) also found the participants, inadvertently served to perpetuate the stigma by viewing themselves as different from other CEP.

With a lack of support from family, professionals and partners, (Chase *et al.*, 2006; Pryce and Samuels, 2010; Bermea *et al.*, 2019), this negative view of, or from, their peers often only increased their isolation and lack of support. Self-stigma was also a concern in Ohene and Garcia's (2020) USA research, in which the authors recommended that children's services staff needed to be trained to support CEP to reduce the risks of self-stigma and encourage a sense of belonging and self-empowerment.

The above section discusses the impact of stigma, trauma and social isolation on CEP's mental health. Although the importance of post-partum mental health needs of CEP is recognised (Aparicio *et al.*, 2018) there appears to be few studies that explored the emotional and mental health needs of CEP in the post-natal period (Wilson *et al.*, 2017; Aparicio *et al.*, 2018).

2.4.6 Rapid repeat pregnancy

Rapid repeat pregnancies (RRP) are described as a further pregnancy within a year of a live birth and are associated with negative perinatal outcomes, (Courtney *et al.*, 2007) This section considers the reasons why CEP may be more likely to have an RRP.

It is known that CEP are more likely to have a higher incidence of RRP than their non-care experienced peers (Courtney *et al.*, 2007; Dworsky and Courtney, 2010; Putman and Hornstein, 2013; Finigan- Carr *et al.*, 2015; Aparicio *et al.*, 2018). Dworsky and Courtney's (2010) longitudinal research in the USA, using baseline and secondary interviews, noted a higher incidence of repeat pregnancies amongst CEP and by age 19, the figures for a second pregnancy for female CEP in comparison to their non-care experienced peers were higher at 46% and 34%, respectively.

Similarly, a study by Putnam-Hornstein and King (2014) in the USA deepens our understanding of the incidence of repeat CEP pregnancies, the impact of ethnicity and the age at which the CEP were first accommodated. Putnam-Hornstein and King (2014) analysed the linked birth and child protection records of 20,222 females in

foster care in California between 2003 and 2007. The percentage who gave birth before age 20 was 28.1%. Rates of first births by race/ethnicity showed Black and Latina girls had significantly higher rates of first births compared to Caucasian CEP. It was of interest to note that girls who had been in foster care before age 12 had significantly lower rates of being teenage first-time mothers. Among female CEP who had their first child before age 18, 41.2% had a further teenage birth (Putnam-Hornstein and King, 2014).

A phenomenological study in the USA by Aparicio *et al.* (2018) further contributed to the knowledge as to why female CEP wished to rapidly expand their family. Aparicio *et al.* (2018) used Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis to study the data from 6 female CEP. Despite the challenges the CEP encountered, they felt confident enough to manage to quickly extend their family. Aparicio *et al.*'s (2018) study established a third of the CEP had quickly experienced subsequent births after their first child, despite some not having had sufficient resources or parenting capacity to be able to care for their firstborn.

The section reviewed the evidence of what influenced CEP's rapid expansion of their families. Some studies have found a cultural influence (Putnam-Hornstein and King, 2014). PettyJohn *et al.* (2021) consider that planned pregnancies, unintended pregnancies and coerced pregnancies should be further explored to enable resources to be available to CEP to help them come to an informed decision about whether to rapidly expand their family. There appears to be a dearth of UK studies that have explored this important issue which can impact on both the CEP and their children's future outcomes.

2.5 Relationships

Although some literature considered the relational aspects of CEP's transitions (Cashmore and Paxman, 2007; Pryce and Samuels, 2010; Rolfe, 2008; Wilson *et al.*, 2017), few studies focus on CEP's experiences within their own relationships (Aparico, 2016). Dependable adults who can advocate on their behalf are an important resource and can increase the CEP's self-efficacy (Tyrer *et al.*, 2005; Bermea *et al.*, 2019).

2.5.1 Relationship with biological families

Becoming a parent has been seen as a means for the CEP to reconnect and strengthen previous and existing family relationships (Love *et al.*, 2005; Chase *et al.* 2006). For some CEP, becoming a parent can strengthen and reconnect families (Love *et al.*, 2005; Leve *et al.*, 2013). Increased family involvement has been viewed positively by some CEP, providing them with both practical and emotional support, particularly from their own birth mothers, and creating the potential to find new purpose in their previous relationships (Love *et al.*, 2005; Wade and Dixon, 2006). Research suggests that support for CEP, from biological or substitute parents, has had significant implications for minimising parenting stress (Biehal and Wade, 1996; Wade and Dixon, 2006; Haight *et al.* 2009). Wade and Dixon's (2006) UK study of 106 CEP found that since leaving care more than half the participants considered they had a 'strong' relationship with their close relatives. Similarly, Biehal and Wade (1996) and Haight *et al.* (2009) found aunts, grandparents or stepparents all had important roles to play in helping the CEP feel they 'belong'. Moreover, Biehal and Wade's (1996) UK qualitative, longitudinal study (N=74) found that CEP also had some support from brothers and sisters.

Aparicio *et al.* (2018) argued that effective family support systems were less likely to be in place for CEP when they made their transitions to parenthood. This finding was supported in Rutman *et al.*'s (2002) Canadian study who found the 11 CEP had often strained relationships with their birth families (Rutman *et al.*, 2002). Other authors have also found that re-engagement with birth families can be fleeting (Courtney and Dworksy, 2006; Aparicio *et al.*, 2015). A small Argentinian study by Coler (2018) (N=4) found birth families frequently brought further challenges and contradictory feelings. Despite CEP's optimism of strengthening their relationship with their birth parents, evidence demonstrates that CEP do not have a network of family support or dependable adults, particularly when exiting foster care (Biehal and Wade, 1996; Rutman *et al.*, 2002; Chase *et al.*, 2003; Max and Paluzzi, 2005; Wade and Dixon, 2008; Finegan-Carr *et al.*, 2015).

On leaving care, continued parental rejection towards the CEP created further distress for the CEP and Biehal and Wade (1996) recommended that CEP leaving care needed counselling to manage the stress caused by family relationships. Similar findings were

evidenced in another study by Goodkind *et al.* (2011) whose qualitative research sought to understand why care experienced young people left care before their 19th birthday and focused on their transition experiences. Goodkind *et al.* (2011) interviewed 45 young care experienced young people, 13 of whom were CEP. Difficulties in relationships with family members meant that their emotional needs were not met and this directly impacted on how they were able to respond to their own child's needs. The lack of acceptance by birth parents after re-establishing contact resulted in feelings of mistrust and increased withdrawal from others (Goodkind *et al.*, 2011).

Cashmore and Paxman's (2007) Australian longitudinal study found over 68% (n=28) of the participants had continued contacts with their birth family, whilst nearly 32% (n=13) experienced problems in their birth family relationships and had no contact. Radey *et al.* (2016) identified that some female CEP's received support from a foster parent, but rarely received support from their biological families. The dysfunctional relationships with birth families often further drained the young mothers' coping resources (Radey *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, Samuels and Pryce (2008) demonstrated that in an attempt to remain involved in their families' lives, CEP provided, rather than received, support to their birth parents. Purtell *et al.* (2020) found on occasions, child protection services intervened in the CEP re-engagement with their birth families, due to the continued risks and stressors the CEP's families posed.

In summary, despite the CEP's hopes of re-establishing relationships with their birth family, it appeared that in some cases the support was not available to them and family tensions could instead be an additional stressor. For some CEP the pattern of rejection caused further emotional distress. Furthermore, risks to the CEP from their own parents necessitated social work intervention to prevent biological birth families' involvement. Yet for some CEP, relationships can be restored with parents and wider family members. The potential for the CEP to receive emotional support from their parents as they adjust to parenthood deserves further attention.

2.5.2 *Relationship with partner*

As discussed in chapter 1 teenage parent's relationships have often been viewed as transient and unstable (Smeeding *et al.*, 2011). This section considers the relationships that CEP have with their partner.

Chase *et al.*'s, (2006) qualitative study (n=63) found CEP frequently planned to live with their partner earlier than their peers who had not been care experienced. Female CEP in Aparicio *et al.* (2015) mostly described their child's father and the extended paternal family as a source of support and an extension of their social networks. The CEP spoke of their determination, despite evidence of the partner often treating them with disrespect.

A descriptive USA study by Herrman *et al.* (2016) of 151 CEP, used baseline reporting and self-reporting to investigate pregnancy and IPV in this population. Herrman *et al.* (2016), discovered that due to the CEP and their partner's developmental stage, and the stress of pregnancy or parenthood, female CEP were frequently at a high risk of physical, emotional and sexual abuse and pregnancy coercion during pregnancy and post birth. Cashmore and Paxman (2007) study discovered that 11 of the 16 female CEP who participated in their study, had suffered violence in their relationship with their partner. Furthermore, Bermea *et al.*'s (2021) USA study highlighted that childhood trauma, relating to sexual abuse and domestic violence, have been linked to challenges in managing conflict resolution and violence in the CEP intimate relationships.

In some cases, female CEP are manipulated in relationships (Matta Oshima *et al.*, 2013; Aparicio *et al.*, 2015; Radey *et al.*, 2016). In Radey *et al.*'s (2016) USA qualitative study, carers often viewed the female CEP's relationships as being unhealthy. The carers noted that female CEP sought support from their child's father, but frequently found that his support was unreliable and inconsistent. A more recent USA study by Bermea *et al.* (2021) interviewed 12 staff who worked with female CEP in a residential foster care home. The study aimed to discover how CEP's history of trauma impacted on their romantic relationships. Bermea *et al.* (2021) found that CEP struggled to implement safe boundaries with their partners, which at times put their children at potential risk. A few of the CEP were unable to maintain a relationship with the child's father, due to child protection involvement or court rulings as a consequence of the CEP being victims of exploitation by older men or the child being conceived due to rape or incest (Bermea *et al.*, 2021). Another USA study by Matta Oshima *et al.* (2013) identified that female CEP's difficulties with their mental health made them susceptible to poor decision-making and to be negatively influenced by their male partners. Due to CEP's desire to improve their children's lives by giving them a stable home, they

may tolerate living with a partner who demonstrates abusive behaviours (Aparicio *et al.*, 2015).

Studies reflect that a significant number of the male CEP either deny they are the father or they were only sporadically involved in their children's lives (Dworsky and Courtney, 2010; Shelbe *et al.*, 2013). Male CEP in Tyrer *et al.*'s (2005) UK study, spoke of how becoming a father had made them more responsible. For some of the male CEP ongoing contact with their child was difficult and they struggled to co-parent without the influence of positive role models. Tyrer *et al.* (2005) suggested attachment issues in childhood explained why some young men did not trust their partner and led them to question the paternity of the child. A further retrospective UK phenomenological study by Dandy *et al.* (2020) used a purposive sampling strategy with 5 CEP male participants. The research focused on fathers with at least one biological child who they maintained regular contact with. All the participants had become CEP in their early twenties and all described seeking a sense of belonging prior to becoming parents. Yet their lack of trust of others appeared to have affected their adult relationships and their bond with their child (Dandy *et al.*, 2020). Due to the retrospective nature of the study participants, there was the potential of recall error as some of the CEP became parents over 40 years ago.

Female CEPs may be more likely to be impacted by IPV due to having little experience of healthy relationships in their own families (Couvrette and Lanctot, 2017; Bermea *et al.*, 2018), which may put their child's safety at risk. Likewise, Aparicio *et al.*'s (2015) USA phenomenological study identified the need for further research to study available support for female CEPs to enable them to learn how to foster healthy intimate relationships.

Research in the USA by Shpiegel and Cascardi (2015), used information from the National Youth in Transition Database (NYTD) (n=15,601) to consider issues associated with early parenthood for male and female CEP at age 17 years and how parenthood experiences differed between the genders. Results demonstrated that 4% of males and 10% of females from the NYTD data had children. The authors found that male CEP were often involved with both child and family social work services (due to childcare concerns) and with criminal justice services (Hook and Courtney, 2013; Shpiegel and Cascardi, 2015). Concerns about the over representation of care

experienced young people involved in the Criminal Justice System have been highlighted by Mendes *et al.* (2014b)

Due to the scarcity of studies on male CEPs, further qualitative research to provide a deeper understanding of fathers' perspectives would be beneficial. Although many of the CEP had relationship difficulties, Haight *et al.* (2009) stated that despite this the young parents also offered each other practical and emotional support. Haight *et al.* (2009) recommended that parenting supports to motivate young fathers' involvement can be beneficial for the CEP's families.

Attachment behaviour, lack of trust and poor mental health due to traumatic childhood events, poor role models and the inability to positively manage conflict can impact on the CEP's relationships with their partners. Concerns about unhealthy romantic relationships and the risk of IPV have been discussed. Herrman *et al.* (2016) recommended that due to the complex nature of IPV and CEP, further qualitative studies are required to provide a deeper understanding of CEP's experience of IPV. Parenting supports to young fathers may also benefit the CEP's families. The majority of the evidence stems from the USA, which may impact on the transferability of the findings. Further research to explore how CEPs manage their intimate relationships and how it positively or negatively impacts on their parenting could inform future practice.

2.5.3 Relationship with foster carer

This section considers the evidence in relation to the benefits and challenges of ongoing foster care for CEP as they adapt to motherhood. The range of findings discussed provides insight from both the CEP's perspective and the role of the foster carer.

Some female CEP who remained in foster care following the birth of their child have valued mother and baby foster care placements (Chase *et al.*, 2006; Radey, 2016; Scheble and Geiger, 2017; Burmea *et al.*, 2018). Scheble and Geiger (2017) found adolescent mothers in foster care residential placements helped them learn healthier parenting practices. In the UK, qualitative research by Knight *et al.* (2006a) comprising of 63 young care experienced participants and 78 professionals, focussed on CEP's experience of foster care, availability of sexual health and relationship education, what

influenced their pregnancy and the support received whilst they were pregnant and parenting. The value of mother and child foster placements were affirmed by the research, although the authors acknowledged that these limited mother and child foster care placements are normally only offered to female CEP under 16 years of age.

Radey *et al.* (2016) found in their USA study that combining residential foster care with a range of educational programmes designed to meet the female CEP's range of needs, were viewed as being supportive by the CEP. The findings were similar in Bermea *et al.*'s (2020) USA study where a participatory action research approach was used within a residential foster home for CEP. Bermea *et al.*'s (2020) research held focus groups with the 39 female CEP in residential foster care to explore their experiences. The participants spoke of feeling secure with the consistent network of support they received from the other CEP residents, as well as from the residential support staff. In contrast, Aparicio *et al.*'s, (2015) USA phenomenological study with 18 female CEP in foster care, found all the CEP desired their own permanent family home due to the previous insecure foster placements they experienced in their childhood, and the ongoing uncertainty of whether they would yet again be moved to another supported foster care placement. Other CEP in the study felt the foster carers were interfering in the care of their baby and felt that their parenting capacities were viewed more harshly by the foster carers than their non-care experienced peers may have been viewed (Aparicio *et al.*, 2015). Lieberman *et al.*'s (2020) qualitative study in the USA interviewed 36 female CEP and 11 support staff participating in a parenting programme that was run within 3 foster care settings. The study found CEP were anxious about being judged in the residential foster care setting due to their concerns that any negative perceptions could influence the decision of their baby being removed from their care.

Mantovani and Thomas's (2015) UK interpretative study explored the experiences of 15 female African CEP who resided in foster care. Some of the CEP described positive relationships with foster carers and felt they had been prepared for independent living, Other CEP voiced that their foster carers were emotionally unavailable to them and that the carers viewed the CEP pregnancy status simply as a means for them to claim more money from social services. Additionally, LaSala's (2020) USA study, conducted semi-structured interviews with 8 CEP living in group homes. The participants

described parenting decisions being taken from them, tough routines being implemented within the home and the frequent threat of having their babies removed if group home rules were not adhered to. From the foster carer's perspective in the UK, Knight *et al.* (2006) explained the difficulty of trying to balance supporting the CEP's needs and also managing the conflicting perceptions from the CEP and social workers, with accusations that the foster carer was being either over or under involved with the child.

An interpretive, exploratory study in the UK by November and Sandall (2020) involved 32 foster carers, 8 female CEP and 9 social workers in England. The researchers criticised the social workers' poor pre-birth planning arrangements and post birth decisions, which meant the CEP and their child in the post-natal period often had to adjust to residing with an unknown foster carer. Whilst November and Sandall (2020) recognised the potential for the specialist role of the foster carers to improve outcomes for the CEP, the authors were critical of the lack of training the foster carers received in regards to trauma-informed practice and the importance of building supportive trusting relationships. However, Aparicio's (2016) USA study, acknowledged that relationships between CEP and foster carers can be complex. Aparicio (2016) noted the increased risk for CEP, due to their abuse in childhood and having an insecure or disorganized attachment with carers, made it difficult for them to have formed and benefitted from supportive, trusting relationships. Biehal and Wade (1996) found continued support was not available from foster carers due to a breakdown of relationships and in some instances (Biehal and Wade, 1996; Mantovani and Thomas, 2015) the foster parents showed little interest once their paid, formal involvement ceased. Furthermore, CEP on leaving care felt conflicted loyalties between re-establishing a relationship with their birth parents and maintaining an ongoing relationship with the foster parents (Biehal and Wade, 1999; Wilson *et al.*, 2017).

In summary, Knight *et al.* (2006a) evidenced the reduced availability of foster care mother and baby placements once the CEP was over 16 years of age and a more contemporary study would be beneficial to discover if this remains the case.

Mixed views have been reported about CEP's experiences of residing in foster care following the birth of their child. Whilst some described feeling supported, for others the perception of being judged and the threat of their child being removed was present.

Training needs of foster carers supporting this vulnerable population have also been described. Furthermore, the availability of supported foster care provisions has also been evidenced. A deeper understanding of CEP's experience of supported foster care would provide further up-to-date information within a UK context.

2.6 Experience of Health Services

Research has described a range of complex issues that has made accessing health services difficult for CEP (Aparico *et al.*, 2015; Aparicio *et al.*, 2017; Eastman *et al.*, 2019). This section considers the evidence of CEP engagement with health services and any barriers associated with their engagement.

2.6.1 Maternity services

Studies suggested care experienced mothers are less likely to attend antenatal care and experience worse birth outcomes in terms of birth weight and prematurity (Courtney *et al.*, 2011; Dworsky and DeCoursey, 2009; Botchway *et al.*, 2014). Dworsky and DeCoursey, (2009) found CEP were reluctant to have engaged in prenatal care. Whilst most female foster youth in Dworsky and DeCoursey's (2009) research received at least some prenatal care, unlike their non-care experienced peers, many CEP were in their third trimester before ante-natal care began, with some CEP having not presented for any antenatal care.

Mantovani and Thomas's (2015) feminist study in the UK, interviewed 28 CEP with a mood disorder and discovered that health professionals were unaware of the complex social circumstances of the CEP and the health staff demonstrated negative views about teenage pregnancy. Mantovani and Thomas's (2015) study also found there was little evidence of joined up working between health and social care practitioners, which may have enabled a more sensitive approach to the CEP health and social care needs. Montgomery *et al.* (2015) considered that for a CEP with a history of childhood sexual abuse, attendance at maternity care, even for a planned pregnancy and with the provision of sensitive person centred care, was still traumatic. Montgomery *et al.* (2015) recommended the need for effective collaboration between social work services and maternity care, to ensure the provision of pre and postnatal health services were sensitive and responsive to the CEP's needs.

2.6.2 Mental health services

A literature review by Eastman *et al.* (2019a) on mothers in foster care and their children reviewed 18 research papers published between 2011 and 2017. The authors found that mental health concerns are common among care experienced young people, that appropriate mental health services may have enhanced a range of outcomes for CEP and their child, and that barriers to accessing mental health services was an issue.

Aparicio's (2017) phenomenological study investigated the experience of motherhood for 6 female CEP. This methodology is appropriate for investigating issues that require meaningful insight into often sensitive issues (Gray, 2018). Access issues to mental health services, the limitations in the range of alternative therapeutic approaches, and the stigma of engaging with mental health services were identified as barriers to the CEP receiving effective mental health support. Furthermore, without effective mental health treatment, substance abuse was being used by some participants as a negative coping strategy (Aparicio, 2017).

The fear of being judged when seeking help was discovered in Mantovani and Thomas's (2014) small-scale exploratory study in the UK. Eight of the 15 participants had previous experience of significant trauma and the CEP spoke of the stigma, disempowerment and self-blame they experienced during their encounters with health and social workers. The participants were all young Black single mothers in care, and were acutely aware of how they were stigmatised and judged (Mantovani and Thomas, 2014). Similarly, Bermea *et al.* (2018) found CEP accessing supports were threatened by societal stigma related to their age and motherhood status.

In Narendorf *et al.*'s (2013) study, CEP felt unheard by health professionals when they discussed their rationale for not taking their prescribed mental health medication. The CEP explained they were worried the side effects of the medicine could be detrimental to their unborn baby's health or that taking the medication would have interfered with their responsiveness to their child. Narendorf *et al.* (2013) also found that parenting demands meant some of the CEP were unable to access mental health services due to lack of childcare provision

Mental health services have the potential to improve outcomes for CEP and their children. Further insight into barriers for CEP to engage with mental health services needs further exploration.

2.7 Experience of Child Protection Services

This section discusses the increased prevalence of CEP involvement with child protection services and the increased likelihood of their child being removed from their care. Consideration is given to the cycle of abuse theory, the potential for surveillance bias, the pre-disposing factors that impact on their parenting and social worker's perceptions of challenges and opportunities to support CEP capacity to parent.

2.7.1 Prevalence of CEP's involvement with Child Protection Services

Studies have identified that CEP are fearful of child protection services being involved with their own children (Radey *et al.*, 2016; Aparicio, 2017; Schelbe and Geiger, 2017). The fear of the 'care cycle' being repeated, of their own children going into care was a common theme that emerged from the research (Knight *et al.*, 2006b; Rolfe, 2008; Pryce and Samuels, 2010; Aparicio *et al.*, 2018; Dandy *et al.*, 2020). In Dworsky and DeCoursey's (2009) study nearly a quarter of CEP children had been involved in child protection investigations, which suggests that CEP were considered an increased risk for continuing generational abuse. Experience of child abuse or violence within their family setting for male CEP, has also been linked to continued abusive or neglectful parenting styles of their own children (Newcomb and Locke, 2001).

Courtney *et al.*'s (2011) USA prospective study conducted interviews with 732 care experienced young people aged 17. Female CEP in the study were found to be 6 times more likely than their peers to be living without at least one of their children by the time the mothers reached 26 years of age. For young fathers their child was 1.8 times more likely to be living with other carers (Courtney *et al.*, 2011). This study had a good uptake with 96% of eligible participants involved in the baseline interview (Courtney *et al.*, 2011). A large Australian retrospective cohort study by Armfield *et al.* (2021) aimed to understand the risk of intergenerational transmission of child abuse. The researcher used administrative data of 38,556 mothers and their children. The researchers compared data on mothers who had not had child protection services (CPS) involvement during childhood (n=23,437), with mothers who had received CPS as

children (n=4,382) and CEP (n=469). The study found that in comparison to mothers with no childhood involvement with CPS, mothers who had CPS involvement in their childhood had an increased likelihood of CPS involvement for their own children. For the CEP, CPS involvement for their own children was an even greater in comparison to the mothers who experienced CPS support.

Canadian research by Wall-Wieler *et al.* (2018b), compared data on 576 female CEP and 5,366 adolescent mothers who were not care experienced. Wall-Wieler *et al.* (2018b) evidenced that CEP in foster care were more than seven times more likely than their comparative group, to have lost care of their babies by the time their children were 2 years old. Losing custody of their child in the neonatal period was 11 times likelier for the CEP than their non-care experienced mothers. Wall-Wieler *et al.* (2018b) also found 25% of CEP mothers had their children removed by social services one-week post birth. Often the CEP resorted to substance misuse following their child's removal, which further reduced the chance of the child being rehabilitated back to their care. Wall-Wieler *et al.* (2018b) questioned why the CEP were deemed as not having the capacity to care for their infant when there was a lack of sufficient resources provided (e.g. a foster setting for the mother and baby) to have enabled the CEP to have learnt to care and bond with her child.

A UK by Dixon *et al.* (2006) (n. = 20 female CEP) found that 10% of their children had been removed from their mother's care within 10 to 18 months of the CEP leaving care. Roberts *et al.* (2019) found that 26% of children born to CEP were removed from the CEP care, and child protection services had involvement with a further 34% of children. Roberts *et al.* (2019) stated urgent attention is needed regarding CEP within care proceedings, as the CEP are often deemed children themselves.

The USA longitudinal study conducted by Courtney *et al.* (2011) involved over 700 care leavers, 72% (n = 504) of whom were parents. In this study 16% of the children of the female CEP and 65 % percent of children of male CEP lived with another adult in comparison to 2% of the children of the non-care experienced birth mothers and 37% of the children of non-care experienced birth fathers who were in the comparison group (Courtney *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, a Danish study by Mertz and Andersen (2017) using administrative data of 1,569 care experienced women, revealed that CEP's children were between 7 and 10 times likelier to experience foster care during

their pre-school years compared to children whose parents were from a non-care experienced background.

The experience of CEP, and their involvement with child and families social work, needs further attention to understand the circumstances for child and family social worker's involvement and long term outcomes for the CEP and child.

2.7.2 Increased risk of being reported

Leve *et al.*'s (2013), study using logistic regression analyses, revealed that CEP who misused illicit substances had higher incidence of child protection involvement and their children were 2 to 3 times more likely to be reported to child protection services for child maltreatment, in comparison to children born to teenage mothers without an abuse history. However, the authors acknowledge there is the potential that some of these allegations may have been unsubstantiated or indeed malicious.

Widon and Wilson (2015) proposed that evidence for the increased risk of intergenerational transmission of child abuse, may instead be due to increased surveillance bias and thus a greater likelihood of child protection services involvement. This finding of surveillance bias is further strengthened by Purtell *et al.*'s (2020) narrative review of studies from 2015–2020, which focussed specifically on CEP transitioning from care. A further qualitative study by Purtell *et al.* (2021) carried out in Australia, involved 16 staff working with CEP. The staff provided their perspectives on what influenced the high prevalence of early parenting amongst care leavers. The staff identified that as the CEP were already known to social work they were more likely to be involved with child protection services. This reportedly caused the CEP to feel unsupported and pressured to prove themselves as capable of being a good parent, solely because of their childhood experiences (Purtell *et al.*, 2021).

2.7.3 Risks associated with neglect and/or abuse

Several studies state that CEP, who have experienced child abuse and neglect, may be at greater risk of abusing or neglecting their own children (Pears and Capaldi, 2001; Chase *et al.*, 2006; Dixon *et al.*, 2006; Courtney *et al.*, 2011; Geiger and Schelbe, 2014; Botchway *et al.*, 2014; Wall-Wieler *et al.*, 2018(a); Eastman *et al.*, 2019(b); Armfield *et al.*, 2021). Pears and Capaldi's (2001) longitudinal study aimed to

investigate if there was an association between a parent's history of abuse and the parent's own abusive actions toward his or her child. The participants (n=109) were parents who had experienced childhood abuse and their own children. The researchers discovered over a 10-year period, that parents who had been abused in childhood were significantly more likely to have been abusive towards their children. Pears and Capaldi (2001) further indicated depression and post-traumatic stress disorder were predictive of CEP abuse of their child. Likewise, Putman-Hornstein *et al.* (2015) demonstrated that by the age of five, CEP children were twice as likely to be abused in comparison to children whose mothers had not been similarly impacted. Similarly, in a Swedish study, Wall-Wieler *et al.* (2018a) reviewed administrative data. Information on female CEP (n=7,396) was compared to non-care experienced women (n= 270,931) born between 1973 and 1980, who bore children between 1990 and 2012. Within the data they noted that, in comparison to their non-care experienced peers, the CEP's children were at greater risk of being placed in care due to abuse or neglect.

In a USA study, Font *et al.* (2020) sampled data from Wisconsin administrative database of 36,475 individuals born in 1990–1991 and tracked CEP's involvement in child protection services. Font *et al.* (2020) discovered that a previous history of abuse in childhood for the CEP increased their likelihood of suffering from IPV as adults and the associated child protection risks to their child. Font *et al.* (2020) suggested that the cycle of intergenerational abuse could be reduced by educating CEP to understand healthy attachment in romantic relationships.

Whilst there is considerable evidence associating childhood experiences of abuse and increased risk of maltreating one's own child, intergenerational child abuse is not inevitable and is not present in most families (Newcomb and Locke, 2001; Jaffee *et al.*, 2013). Roberts *et al.*'s (2017) research analysed data on the 374 parents from the Wales Adoption Study which included information on 27% care experienced mothers (n=96) and 19% (n=45) care experienced fathers. The study found children born to CEP had no higher risk of being abused than other children of non-care experienced young parents. Despite this finding, statistical analysis showed that of the 96 female CEP, approximately 33% of the care experienced mothers (n = 19) had their first child adopted, with 58% of these children placed for adoption at birth. In comparison to the data from non-care leaver mothers (n=278), only 18% of their first born were placed

for adoption. This difference raises concerns about the extent of support provided to first time CEP. Roberts *et al.* (2017) recommended further research to understand why female CEP lose care of their child and also what resources and supports are available to help them successfully parent.

2.7.4 Predisposing factors to CEP's children being taken into care

In a USA study by Eastman *et al.* (2019b) female CEP's children who had been involved with child protection services were studied. Data was examined using latent class analysis, and factors for increased child protection involvement with CEP's children included a younger maternal age, unstable parental placement and leaving care early. Putnam-Hornstein and King (2014) used aggregated data in their descriptive study and identified a higher likelihood of children's social work involvement for children born to CEP in foster care in comparison with children born to CEP in kinship care.

As previously discussed, research indicates that CEP are more likely to have rapid repeat births (RRB) (Courtney *et al.*, 2007; Finigan Carr *et al.*, 2015; Aparicio *et al.*, 2018). Crowne *et al.* (2012) found vulnerable families who had an RRB were more likely to be investigated for neglectful parenting compared to families without an RRB. In a similar vein a UK mixed methods study by Broadhurst *et al.* (2015) demonstrated that of the 24% of women involved in recurrent legal proceedings for the removal of their children, young women aged 16 to 19 years were most at risk. Aparicio *et al.* (2018) noted that the inability to meet subsequent children's needs, due to social and economic barriers, detrimentally affected the CEP's parenting abilities and increased the risk of child maltreatment.

Aparicio *et al.* (2015) discovered that CEP's reluctance to participate in parenting programs often led to professionals' to resort to parenting assessments being based solely on historical evidence of the CEP birth family as a predictor of future risks. Similar concerns were identified by Siverns and Morgan (2019) who conducted an interpretive meta-synthesis on 11 papers on the parenting experiences of survivors of childhood abuse. The researchers stated professionals needed to recognise that, when assessing parenting abilities, their scrutiny can leave CEP feeling re-traumatised as their vulnerabilities are exposed. They also found that children's services often criticised the CEP's parenting behaviours while parenting strengths were neglected.

Siverns and Morgan (2019) cautioned what may have appeared as ambivalence about engagement with parenting supports had to be understood in the context of the CEP having experienced trauma. CEP's non-engagement should be normalised and understood with psychological strategies provided to help the CEP participate in supportive parenting interventions (Siverns and Morgan, 2019).

Marshall *et al.*'s (2011) USA study compared the parenting outcomes of two generations of families involved with child and family social work. The study evidenced that permanent removal of the child from the family was lower for the 2nd generation. However, there was an increased likelihood the child would be permanently removed from their care for the CEP with a mental health diagnosis. A weakness of this study by Marshall *et al.* (2011) is that participants were all involved in a substance misuse programme, which carries an increased risk of child abuse and therefore the findings may not be generalised to CEP who are not similarly affected.

Some caseworkers are pessimistic about improving CEP outcomes (Radey *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, Maxwell *et al.* (2011) concluded that CEP exposure to negative views of teenage pregnancy and the stigma of being in care, could have weakened their relationship with their child and undermined the CEP belief in their ability to parent. Parenting can reinforce feelings of inadequacy and act as a trigger to the abuse they experienced. (Leeners *et al.*, 2016; Siverns and Morgan, 2019). CEP in some instances felt fearful and powerless, viewing social workers as being deceptive (Radey *et al.*, 2016) and having the power to remove their children from their care without justification (Chase *et al.*, 2006; Knight *et al.*, 2006). Studies have also found that professional practice has frequently been considered as judgmental and unsupportive for CEP (Rutman *et al.*, 2002b; Dominelli *et al.*, 2005; Knight *et al.*, 2006; Haight *et al.*, 2009; Marshall *et al.*, 2011; Roberts, 2017; Lancoit *et al.*, 2018). In Canada, a qualitative retrospective study by Lanctot and Turcotte (2018) captured the experiences of 13 female CEPs. Two of the participants had lost custody of their children due to substance misuse. The other participants reported they adhered to a restricted lifestyle such as having no romantic relationships and being stay at home mothers with few social contacts. The restrictions the CEP felt they needed to impose on themselves, sometimes to the detriment of their own well-being, was in an attempt to ensure the enhanced scrutiny they felt within their community did not bring them to the attention of child and family services (Lanctot and Turcotte, 2018).

In Haight *et al.*'s (2009) ethnographic study, the researchers sought to understand human development within their cultural context. The 3 female African American CEP spoke of being discriminated against by social workers due to the CEP living in poverty. Similarly, in a small-scale grounded theory study, in Canada, involving 11 female CEP and 20 child welfare workers, Rutman *et al.* (2002) demonstrated that social workers' core middle-class values influenced their practice and workers failed to see adolescent pregnancy as a positive or normal occurrence. Instead, the teenage pregnancy was viewed as the CEP having repeated the cycle of their own poor parenting.

Many CEP have been resilient in coping with the many challenges they experienced (Rutman *et al.*, 2001; Shpiegel, 2016; Radey *et al.*, 2016; Aparicio, 2017; Bermea *et al.*, 2018; Shpiegel *et al.*, 2020). However, CEP's belief in their ability to successfully raise their family was not always shared by others (Rutman *et al.*, 2001; Rutman *et al.*, 2002; Dominelli *et al.*, 2005). Dominelli *et al.*'s (2005) Canadian study involved 11 female CEP and 20 child welfare workers. The authors highlighted the double-standard of expecting CEP to manage parenthood, whilst corporate parents at the same time failed to provide them with the resources needed to make it achievable. Bureaucratic procedures were found to have prevented social work practitioners from sensitively supporting the CEP and the authors suggested the recognition of the structural inequalities should be addressed, rather than focussing on the perceived CEP's failings. Dominelli *et al.*'s (2005) study supported the earlier findings by Chase *et al.* (2003) that CEP needed independent advocacy to ensure their legal rights were being upheld.

2.7.5 Challenges for practitioners

Whilst some studies consider that young people leaving care are increasingly more likely to be offered social support (Courtney *et al.*, 2005; Dworsky and Courtney, 2010) CEP have been wary of the very services that are there to support them (Chase *et al.*, 2003; Leve *et al.*, 2013; Lanctot and Turcotte, 2018; Siversns and Morgan, 2019). All 13 female CEP participants in a Canadian study by Leve *et al.* (2013) demonstrated pride in the fact that they did not depend on anyone. However, their self-reliant approach appeared to be built on mistrust and their desire to keep their problems to themselves rather than having risked being judged for seeking help. Due to their past

experiences, teenage parents who have left care settings are especially reluctant to seek support (Chase *et al.*, 2003) for fear that they will be judged as unfit parents.

Mantovani and Thomas (2015) study found good practice in supporting CEP. A quarter of the CEP participants in Mantovani and Thomas's (2015) research discussed social workers who had provided caregiving practice beyond the realms of their professional remit, which made the CEP feel valued and hopeful of a better future. Similarly, Baker *et al.*'s (2019) quantitative UK study of 474 young people leaving care in 6 local authority areas revealed that 96% of respondents found it easy to contact their social worker for support. However, the non-response bias of 70% reduces the reliability and validity of Baker *et al.*'s findings. Of those who participated, a large majority (86%) felt they had been involved in preparing plans for their future. In contrast, despite the high level of support that the CEP needed, data from a larger ethnographical study of 33 CEP (Schelbe *et al.*, 2017) found that only 6% engaged with aftercare support services. Aparicio *et al.*'s (2015) small phenomenological research also highlighted that CEP lacked trust in social work services, due to their own early childhood experience and this lack of trust appeared to also be transferred to other types of services. Siverns and Morgan (2019) concluded that young parents who have developed attachment difficulties, due to their own carers being a source of abuse, found it difficult to receive support.

CEP's experience of childhood abuse and various care placements means that CEP are at greater risk of struggling to cope with new circumstances, which Lee and Berrick (2014) considered may explain their difficulty managing the challenges in adulthood. However, Geiger and Schelbe (2013) and Dworsky and Gitlow (2017) considered that independent living skills programs need to be improved for young people and particularly targeted to CEP in care. CEP need access to coordinated wide-ranging support services, such as childcare, education and vocational support, stable housing and parenting skills (Max and Paluzzi, 2005; Vorhies *et al.*, 2009; Schelbe, 2013). Moreover, the need for basic cooking skills should also be addressed (Dominelli *et al.*, 2005).

Changes of social worker are often described as poorly managed (Dominelli *et al.*, 2005). Difficulties can be exacerbated if the CEP has a therapeutic relationship with a social worker who is subsequently replaced with another social worker with whom they

cannot relate to (Dominelli *et al.*, 2005; Purtell *et al.*, 2020). Over half of the 15 female CEP in Mantovani and Thomas's (2015) UK interpretive study discussed their frequent attempts to contact their social workers, only to have received a sporadic response in return. Bermea *et al.* (2018) reported that the high job turnover in the profession reduced the individual time that social workers can spend with each CEP and the challenge of heavy caseloads and paperwork impacted on this ability.

Social workers in Roberts *et al.*'s (2019) research, expressed that their dual role of providing support whilst investigating concerns about their child's well-being, impacted on their ability to gain the CEP's trust to engage with support. Similarly, a study by Rutman *et al.* (2002), discovered children's services workers felt like an inadequate 'parent' in supporting CEP. In the USA, care providers likewise considered changes in child welfare policy, along with a lack of resources, to be detrimental to their corporate parenting role (Radey *et al.*, 2016).

2.7.6 Social support

The influence of social support and the impact on the CEP parenting ability has been evidenced (Biehal *et al.*, 1995; Dominelli *et al.*, 2015; Aparicio, 2017; Purtell *et al.*, 2020). Research by Aparicio (2017) discovered that CEP's ability to care for their children was strongly related to the level of social support from trusted individuals, which reduced their feelings of isolation and stress.

However, it has been evidenced that CEP can have difficulty trusting and maintaining relationships (Knight *et al.*, 2006a; Maxwell *et al.*, 2011; Bermea *et al.*, 2019). Research indicated that CEP are often lone parents (Dominelli *et al.*, 2005), are isolated from friends (Biehal *et al.*, 1995; Dominelli *et al.*, 2005), can have had complex relationships with birth families (see section) and are more likely to have suffered IPV (Cashmore and Paxton, 2006).

Combs *et al.*'s (2018a) USA quantitative study explored early pregnancy rates and parenting among 215 male and female young adults with a history of foster care. Despite often negative perspectives of the young fathers, the majority of male CEP (86.2%) continued to provide financially for their children and supported their child's well-being needs. Dominelli *et al.* (2005) stated that social workers are known to have pressured female CEP to end their relationships with their male partners because of

the partner's poor parenting skills. This resulted in the opportunity to develop the fathers' parenting abilities and for the mother's to gain vital support being lost. Another USA study by Hook and Courtney (2013) used longitudinal data from the Midwest Evaluation of the Adult Functioning of Former Foster Youth. This study focused on male CEP that had left foster care and their contact with their children (n = 150). Hook and Courtney (2013) discovered that by age 26, male CEP provided ongoing involvement and support for their child. In contrast, Bermea *et al.* (2019) evidenced that challenges in relationships with their partner and issues of IPV were noted to have negatively affected the CEP coping abilities. Providing support to CEP to successfully co-parent with their child's father, when it is safe to do so, may help to negate the associated risks linked to lack of social support (Combs *et al.*, 2018)

To summarise, studies have identified an increased risk of CEP having their child removed from their care. Research has evidenced CEP's own, often traumatic childhood experiences, have made them distrustful of the services that can provide the support they require. Due to the CEP's non-engagement with services, social workers have used historical information on the CEP's own childhood to assess potential risk to the CEP's child. Social isolation appeared to be linked with the increased risk of the child being removed from the CEP's care, yet some research criticised the lack of support for their partners to minimise the risk. Further study to explore from a multiple perspective the challenges CEP encounter, may help to provide a more robust understanding of the strengths and challenges CEP face in positively parenting their child and may inform future practice and policy.

Whilst both the professionals and the CEP sought to break the 'cycle' of care, the research highlighted that there appeared to be different perceptions regarding how this could be achieved. In addition, the lack of appropriate resources led to different opinions regarding what constituted supportive practice. Extended stay in foster care is associated with continued male CEP and child contact. Further research triangulating the views of CEP and children's service workers may offer greater insight to the phenomena.

2.8 Transition from care

UK research found that CEP leaving foster or residential care forced many CEP into independent living at a much earlier age than young people in the general population

(Biehal *et al.*, 1995; Dominelli *et al.*, 2005; Schelbe and Geiger, 2017; Shpiegel and Cascardi, 2018). This section considers the research in relation to CEP housing, managing finances, employment opportunities and childcare provision.

2.8.1 Housing needs

Biehal *et al.* (1996) discovered that it was relationship breakdown with their foster carer which prompted the CEP to leave care. Instead of scaffolding their transition into adult life, Dominelli *et al.* (2005) concluded the care system 'infantilized' them, causing the people to seek increased control which consequently increased their vulnerability when they decided to leave care early. Furthermore, Shpiegel and Cascardi's (2018) USA research, highlighted that female CEP felt they had to leave foster care due to lack of placement options that accommodated them and their child, or because they were unable to meet the education and/or employment expectations of extended foster care.

Social workers in Robert *et al.*'s (2019) study further expanded on a lack of resources to help CEP with housing and practical help. Similar findings were made by Schelbe and Geiger (2017) who found that although most CEP in the USA had the option to remain in their care setting until aged 21, most opted to leave foster care at age 18. Shpiegel (2016) stressed the need for robust planning to ensure suitable accommodation prior to leaving the care setting, which would consequently reduce incidences of homelessness. However, other studies have demonstrated that CEP encountered an increased risk of becoming homeless in the period soon after leaving care (Biehal *et al.*, 1999; Dixon and Stein, 2005; Pecora *et al.*, 2006; Aparicio, 2017). Having symptoms of a mental health problem, as well as IPV, increased the risk of becoming homeless (Dworsky *et al.*, 2013). Risks were further exacerbated for this vulnerable group, as their homelessness resulted in reduced access to health care and social services (Wade and Dixon, 2006).

CEP participants had few housing options with most being offered group home living with other CEP (Dworsky and DeCoursey, 2009; Shpiegel *et al.*, 2020). Lieberman *et al.* (2015) noted that CEP were often moved from their foster care placement into other placements in pregnancy and again post birth. Putman-Hornstein *et al.*'s (2016) USA study analysed the child protection records of 17-year-old females who were in foster care during 2003 and 2007 (n= 20,222). A third of the population were CEP before the

age of 21. The researchers found that as policies had recently extended the right for care experience young people to remain in their care setting until aged 21, care settings may in the future have more resident CEP. The researchers considered that housing and childcare resources provisions need to meet the change in demographics. With a shortage of group homes evidenced by Dworsky and DeCoursey (2009) and Shpiegel *et al.* (2020) the researchers highlighted their concerns that CEP are more likely to become homeless with their children after leaving care. Moreover, the lack of suitable accommodation options was further compounded if the CEP wanted to reside as a family with the child's father (Shpiegel *et al.*, 2020).

It has been argued that early parenthood may mean CEP are eligible for additional housing benefits that are not available to their peers without children (Dworsky, 2015). Geiger *et al.* (2014) state that although CEP may be entitled to housing benefits, due to their limited resources, many CEP are forced to live in unsafe neighbourhoods with few employment opportunities. Leve *et al.*'s (2013) USA study found some CEP were anxious about living alone having been used to group living and they subsequently struggled with independent living (Mendes, 2010; Leve *et al.*, 2013). Consequently, Geiger and Schelbe (2014) revealed that CEP often preferred to stay with family and friends.

Evidence suggests that CEP face difficulty in securing suitable accommodation for themselves and their families. Many of the studies discussed were conducted in the USA. Consequently, further research of CEP's housing experiences within a Scottish context will provide greater understanding to ensure that their needs are being met.

2.8.2 Poverty and employment

Research has found that poverty increased the stress on families and made parenting more difficult (Barn and Mantovani, 2007; Courtney *et al.*, 2012; Aparicio *et al.*, 2015; Radey *et al.*, 2016).

Evidence showed that many CEP live in poverty. A survey by Baker *et al.* (2019) of 474 care leavers included CEP from six English local authorities. Baker *et al.* (2019) revealed that nearly a fifth of young people leaving care found it difficult to manage financially, compared to only 7% of young people in the general population. Due to having few available resources, and the demands of parenting, CEP prioritised

meeting their basic needs rather than preparing for the future (Love *et al.*, 2005; Barn and Mantovani, 2007; Radey *et al.*, 2016).

Care experience parents in Aparicio *et al.*'s (2015) research described not having sufficient money to care for their own children and for some CEP, particularly those with several children, this perpetuated the cycle of their child no longer being in their care.

Challenges of finding suitable employment to escape the poverty cycle are regularly illustrated (Mendes, 2009; Geiger and Schelbe, 2014; Levie, *et al.*, 2015; Baker *et al.*, 2019). Barn and Mantovani (2007) found that 1:4 female CEP in their study had no school qualifications, which further increased their risk of social exclusion. CEP are less likely to be in employment than their counterparts without children, due to their lower educational qualifications. (Combs *et al.*, 2018; Shpiegel and Cascardi, 2018; Wall-Wieler *et al.*, 2018a).

Accessing affordable childcare, without the provision of extended family support, impacts on CEP's employment and education opportunities (Geiger and Schelbe, 2014; Dworsky and Gitlow, 2017; Schelbe *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, Geiger and Schelbe (2014) found access to emergency childcare during illness or holiday periods made it difficult to secure employment. Geiger and Schelbe (2014) also discovered both male and female CEP faced challenges in securing employment. On the other hand, Combs *et al.*'s (2018) study explored early pregnancy and parenthood with foster care experienced young people (n= 215). In this research over a quarter of the male and female participants were CEP. The educational attainment, finances and homelessness experiences of the CEPs were contrasted to the participants who did not experience early parenthood. CEP were found to have reduced qualifications, lower employment and a history of homelessness. Male CEP were found to be less impacted by structural inequalities than female CEP and males were considerably more likely than female CEP to be in employment (87.0% vs. 31.3%). A quantitative, longitudinal USA study by Dworsky and Gitlow (2017) analysed administrative data for 1,943 CEP who were the parent of at least one child when they left care. This study found both male and female CEP were equally less likely to have secured employment or if they had they were on a lower than average salary.

Lieberman *et al.*'s (2015) USA study used a quasi-experimental design within two residential foster care sites. A total of 233 CEP participated between the two sites. There were pre and post birth interviews offered with follow up on 2 occasions over the year. One of the residential sites provided core services whilst the other site provided enhanced supports to the CEP which included childcare support, development of the CEP's career skills and management of household finances. Whilst Lieberman *et al.* (2015) found that the range of enhanced interventions delivered in the residential setting to the CEP were acceptable and resulted in increased internships and interview invites, unfortunately there was no further follow up to assess if any long term benefits following the enhanced interventions had been achieved.

There appears to be a lack of available research about CEP employment outcomes on leaving care and so further research exploring CEP employment and training opportunities would help to inform the issues.

2.9 Summary

The current literature highlights the increased prevalence of teenage pregnancy for care experienced young people and poor outcomes for the CEP. Further research is required to understand CEP's experiences of sexual health education and healthy relationships. In addition, more needs to be known about the barriers they face with regards to accessing support in order to identify the particular needs of CEPs and to potentially extend the periods between subsequent unplanned pregnancies during adolescence.

The literature review has illustrated a paucity of recent UK studies on supporting CEP. Many of the studies were conducted in the USA and extrapolation from American findings to the UK population can be challenging. Care experience parents in Scotland require research that considers their specific circumstances within the context of the Scottish child welfare system and legislation. Teenage CEP are known to be a vulnerable group at risk of a variety of poor outcomes including poverty, poor family support, social isolation, housing issues, poor engagement with services, IPV, rapid repeat pregnancies and an intergenerational cycle of involvement with child protection services. For these reasons, there is a need to explore teenage CEP's perspectives

are regarding their experiences of parenting, and what factors hinder or promote success.

Fallon and Broadhurst (2015) state that far more investment is needed to ensure evidence-informed practices deliver better outcomes for CEP and their children. Further understanding is needed regarding CEP, the roles of health workers and significant others in their lives, and children's services workers' perspectives of what would better support CEP to successfully parent their child.

Many CEP have experienced childhood trauma which has impacted on their emotional well-being and relationships. Nevertheless, there is a lack of evidence of how these teenage parents, impacted by poor mental health in the pre or post-partum period, are supported to manage their mental health needs and parent their child.

American studies have suggested that extending state care beyond the age of 18 for CEP moving out of foster care has been shown to improve pregnancy and parenting outcomes (Dworsky and Courtney, 2010). The legislation presented in Chapter 1 discusses the Children and Young People's (Scotland) Act (2014) and the corporate duties on providers to enable young people to remain in their current care placement. By extending care for young people up to 21 years of age in Scotland, there will be increased numbers of CEP entitled to support. Putman-Hornstein and King (2014) consider that current accommodation, childcare resources, and other transitional supports should be reviewed to meet the changing demographics of CEP in care. However, there is the potential that the most vulnerable CEP may not be willing or able to remain in the care setting and further exploration of their reasons for leaving care may be beneficial. Some of the CEP, from the studies reviewed in the literature, have voiced feeling judged by carers, health and social workers and further exploration of these perspectives, will be helpful to inform practice. The perspective of social work staff to understand the opportunities and challenges to support CEP may provide further insight.

Lack of positive parenting role models means that whilst some CEP can articulate how they do not want to parent they lack the knowledge on how to create positive parenting practices. Further understanding of what supports and what challenges CEP to strengthen their parenting skills are required.

Evidence from the literature review has informed the research aim, which is:

To explore how care experienced teenage parents (CEP) are supported to reduce the challenges associated with both leaving care and becoming a teenage parent.

Chapter 3. Methodology and methods

3.1 Introduction

The literature review identified gaps in the current body of knowledge and provided the focus for the aim, objectives and research design for the study. This chapter will explain the ontology, epistemology, methodology and philosophical perspective underpinning this research. An overview of the case study approach is presented as the preferred research design appropriate to address the area of research under investigation. The positivism and interpretivism paradigms are discussed. The study design and methods demonstrate how the key ethical principles are considered and protected.

3.1.1 *Ontology and epistemology*

Crotty (1998, p. 10) describes ontology as 'the study of being'. Whether reality exists beyond human consciousness and experience (realist ontology), or reality exists only through consciousness and experience (relativist ontology), is the main ontological debate (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Realist ontology considers there is only one single reality and that facts exist independently of the human mind (Robson and McCartan, 2016). In contrast, relativist ontology considers that there are multiple realities. Reality is perceived to be a subjective experience (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). An individual's ontological position establishes the process of how knowledge is gained, which relates to the theory of epistemology. Objectivist epistemology is associated with realist ontology. Crotty (1998) defines objectivism as the belief that things exist as meaningful entities regardless of human consciousness and experience.

Truth from the relativist view is how the individual perceives or interprets it (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). Relativist ontology is the belief that reality is a finite subjective experience and nothing exists outside of our thoughts (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). Levers (2013) states that along with numerous interpretations of experience there are multiple realities. Crotty (1998) further explains this ontological view, stating that whilst objects may still exist beyond human experience of them, the world of meaning about the phenomena can only exist if there are indeed individuals to make sense of it.

Constructivism is an interpretive framework that has two strands: Constructivism and social constructionism. These strands are comparable in that both perspectives endorse the view of knowledge being subjective (Crotty, 1998). Constructivists believe that knowledge is created as opposed to discovered and focuses on the individual's biological and cognitive processes. Social constructionism rejects the constructivist idea that an individual's mind represents a 'mirror of reality' (Galbin, 2014 p. 82) and instead believes that their knowledge and truth are developed through interactions with society members (Andrews, 2012). Social constructionists concentrate on the individual's role as their relationships with people supports them to create realities and make sense of their surroundings (Galbin, 2014).

Crotty (1998) states humans need interactions with others to make any sense of their surroundings. Meaning develops through the process of interpreting and reinterpreting (Burr, 2015). Culture is fundamental in social constructionism as defined by Geertz (1973), cited in Crotty (1998), who claims that culture is central to human behaviour and that without culture humans would otherwise be unable to function. Fish (1990) discusses that physical objects are only socially constructed when they are in contact or connected through human interactions. Crotty (1998) stresses that although something is socially constructed it does not make it less real, as our interpretations of reality are based on our current cultural and historical background (Crotty, 1998).

3.1.2 Methodology

Crotty (1998) advised it is the researcher's assumptions of ontology and epistemology that guides the methodology and research design. Methodology is described as the "strategy, plan of action, process or design" that informs one's choice of research methods (Crotty, 1998, p. 3). Each methodology is based on a particular system of theories, which specify the ontological, epistemological, theoretical perspective and assumptions as to what is meaningful data. Thus, each methodology has developed methods, procedures, techniques, or strategies to be used to conduct the study (Crotty, 1998; Robson and McCartan, 2016).

The researcher in this present study is seeking the 'multiple realities' of the CEP and the research is based on relativist ontology and constructivist epistemology to answer the research aim.

3.1.3 *Positivist and Interpretivist paradigms*

The debate about the merits of the different paradigms and their application in research has been discussed for decades (Corry *et al.*, 2019). Guba and Lincoln (1994, p. 105) define paradigm as a “worldview that guides the researcher in choices of method and in ontologically and epistemologically fundamental ways”.

Closely linked to realist ontology and objectivist epistemology stance is the theoretical perspective of positivism which was promoted most notably by the work of the philosopher Auguste Comte during the Enlightenment period of the early 19th century (Richards, 2003). Positivist researchers believe that truth is captured by statistical and mathematical concepts (Robson and McCartan, 2016). In positivist research the standards for judging research are reliability, validity, and generalisability. Quantitative data methods that positivist researchers employ are through true experiments or quasi-experiments, structured interviews, standardized tests and surveys using closed-ended questionnaires (Robson and McCartan, 2016). The numerical data collated is subjected to descriptive or inferential statistical analysis (Rehman and Alharthi, 2016). Quantitative research uses deductive logic with pre-existing hypotheses tested via experiments or observations to explain how a phenomena occurred (Bryman, 2016). Critics of quantitative research state the approach obscures the reality of the social phenomena of the study and that the non-measurable factors, which have provided the greatest insights to the phenomena, are either ignored or not sufficiently valued (Yarrow and Schwarts-Shea, 2014).

In contrast to the positivist paradigm, Yarrow and Schwarts-Shea (2014) discuss that the interpretivist paradigm seeks to understand and interpret meanings, motives and reasons in human behaviour, within a contextual and reflexive way. Unlike objectivist quantitative studies, interpretivist qualitative research does not focus on statistical analysis, but instead searches for an individual's perceptions (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Denzin and Lincoln (2018) described qualitative researchers as working in the ‘real’ world of lived experience. Qualitative researchers do not conduct experimental research in laboratory conditions. Instead, they often work in natural settings (Creswell and Cresswell, 2018) to gain rich, contextual and typically non-numerical data from the participants (Mason, 2002).

Crotty (1998) states interpretivist studies seek to explore people's views of their experiences, including their cultural and historical interpretations of the social world. Bevir and Rhodes (2002) state that the interpretivist theory is entrenched in history, drawing on hermeneutic and phenomenological philosophies to understand the beliefs and actions of the participants. The interpretivist paradigm has evolved from the philosophy of Wilhelm Dilthey's interpretive understanding. Dilthey, a 19th century hermeneutic philosopher, disputed the idea that only scientific explanations are valid (Makkreel, 2021) and rejected the speculative and metaphysical ways. Dilthey stated that it is humanistic knowledge which gives insight into thoughts, feelings and desires (Makkreel, 2021). Dilthey was focussed on the historical and social nature of the world and the individual's place within it as the prime source of understanding (Crotty, 1998).

The qualitative researcher seeks to make sense of social phenomena and the meanings people bring to them (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). Thus, the qualitative study uses inductive practices, with the participants described as being both interdependent and mutually interactive in the research process to illustrate 'multiple realities' (Stake, 1995). Qualitative research is positioned within a relativist, interpretivist and a constructivist epistemological perspective. Qualitative researchers reject the objectivist epistemology and positivism associated with quantitative research (Crotty, 1998). Constructivists do not begin with a theory. Instead, constructivists inductively create a theory or pattern of meanings (Creswell and Cresswell, 2018). Whilst the interpretivist researcher enters the field with some understanding of the research context, the researcher is aware this is insufficient to develop a fixed research design due to the complex and multiple nature of the participant's perception of reality (Creswell and Cresswell, 2018). Stake (1995) states the researcher is integral to the research process. A variety of methods e.g. interviews, focus groups, observations, is used to gather personal experiences and meanings in individuals' lives (Stake 1995; Yin, 2014).

The criteria used to appraise the findings created by interpretivist research differ from those applied within the positivist paradigm (Gray, 2018). While the value of the positivist paradigm is assessed by the extent results can be generalized to the wider population, the worth of the interpretivist study is evaluated by the extent it reflects the perspectives of participants (Gray, 2018). Qualitative researchers use a different terminology to better illustrate the different approaches from quantitative research

(Ponelis, 2015). Dependability (reliability), credibility (validity), confirmability (objectivity), and transferability (generalisability) are used to establish the robustness of qualitative research (Bloomberg and Volpe, 2008). Generalisation is the main issue over which qualitative studies have been particularly criticised, as the studies often focus on a small number of cases. Yin (2018) disputes this criticism, stating that generalisations are not statistical, they are analytical. Stake (1995) discusses 'naturalistic' generalisation, reflecting that the qualitative data methods facilitate a greater understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. Table 3.1. outlines the main differences between the two main research paradigms.

Areas	Positivist Paradigm	Interpretivist Paradigm
Nature of reality	Assumes there is a single reality.	Assumes the existence of dynamic and multiple realities.
Goal	Test and confirm hypotheses.	Explore and understand phenomena.
Data collection methods	Highly structured methods like questionnaires, inventories and scales.	Semi-structured like in-depth interviews, observations and focus group discussions.
Design	Predetermined and rigid design.	Flexible and emergent design.
Reasoning	Deductive process to test the hypothesis.	Primarily inductive to develop the theory or hypothesis.
Focus	Concerned with the outcome and predictions of the casual relationships.	Concerned primarily with process, rather than outcomes or products.
Sampling	Rely largely on random sampling methods.	Based on purposive sampling methods.
Sample size determination	Involves a-priori sample size calculation.	Collects data until data saturation is achieved.
Data analysis	Variable based and based on use of statistical or mathematical methods.	Case based and use of non-statistical descriptive or interpretive methods.

Table 3.1 Differences of quantitative and qualitative research (Renjith et al., 2021).

3.1.4 *Qualitative approach and types of qualitative research considered*

Whilst a quantitative approach would have provided a statistical exploration of reality (Robson and McCartan, 2016), this would not have addressed the overarching aim of the research and objectives of this study. Qualitative studies have advantages over quantitative research where the issues are complex or sensitive (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Therefore, a qualitative approach was the preferred option given that the emphasis would be on participants' perceptions and experiences. By committing to an interpretivist paradigm, this study reflects the CEP construction of reality by eliciting rich, contextually based information about their experiences of leaving care and parenting. The interpretivist paradigm aligns with the theoretical perspective held by the researcher that will support the research design, the methods of data collection as well as analysis and interpretation (Gray, 2018). Merriam (2015) identified 5 different types of qualitative research (see Table 3.2).

Types of qualitative research	
Basic interpretive qualitative study	
	An inductive approach is adopted to understand how participants make meaning from a phenomenon or a situation. The researcher inductively seeks to discover and understand the participant's views, the phenomenon and the processes involved.
Ethnography	
	Anthropologists develop ethnography to study human behaviour. The researcher explores social interactions, behaviours, and cultures that occur within groups, teams, institutes, and communities. Ethnographers immerse themselves in a setting to gather an in-depth understanding of social relations. Research can be problematic due to the lengthy periods of time needed to interview and to observe the actions of participants (Reeves <i>et al.</i> , 2008).
Phenomenology	
	A phenomenological study focuses on the commonality of individuals and shared experiences of a concept or phenomenon. Direct experience of the participants is valued and accepted without question (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Qualitative data is collected via interviews. Data analysis seeks to explain what and how individuals experience the phenomena. The challenges of this research include locating participants who have shared the same experience (Creswell, 2013).
Grounded theory	
	Researchers examine the data from participants to extract a theory, so that theories are 'grounded' in the information from the social world. This research is useful to use when little theory has been previously developed (Butina <i>et al.</i> , 2015). Data collection reaches saturation when no new insights are revealed (Robson and McCartan, 2016).
Case study	
	Focuses on a single case or a small number of cases. Case study research is the preferred method when "how and why" questions are asked. The researcher has little or no control over behavioural events and the focus of study is a contemporary phenomenon. The case is bounded by time and involves a purposive sample. The researcher conducts data collection methods by various methods i.e. conducting interviews, documenting field notes and reviewing documents and artefacts. Themes are sought from the rich data and categories (Hyett <i>et al.</i> , 2014).

Table 3.2 Types of qualitative research.

Ethical implications and time limitations of the current research made using an ethnographic approach impractical. Furthermore, Creswell (1998) recommended that a grounded theory analysis requires approx. 20-30 participants to develop a theory from the data and this was considered beyond the limitations imposed by this PhD study. Unlike a phenomenology study which relies heavily on interviewing participants with lived experiences of a phenomenon, Hyett *et al.* (2014) states case study research can provide more detailed information from a variety of sources other than

interviewing methods. Taking everything into account, case study was the preferred approach as the case study would answer the following research aim: To explore how care experienced teenage parents (CEP) are supported to reduce the challenges associated with both leaving care and becoming a teenage parent. The case study would also provide a wider view of influences, enabling this study to consider not only the CEP perspectives, but also (in alignment with Bronfenbrenner's bioecological model) the interrelation of family, extended social networks, neighbourhoods and recent Government policy and legislation.

3.1.5 Case study

The case study approach is often used in social research (Yazan, 2015), with case studies dating back to the middle of the 19th century. Yin (2018), Merriam (2009) and Stake (1995) are the 3 influential authors who provide procedures to conduct case study research. Case study is described by one of the three influential case study authors Yin (2018) as being applicable to a variety of different epistemological orientations. Yin (2018) acknowledges that philosophically case study can be undertaken from a realist orientation but also states that the case study can excel from a relativist perspective. Stake (1995) and Merriam (2009) share the same philosophical orientations. From their perspective a case study is positioned within an interpretivist, constructivist paradigm. Yin (2018), whilst not aligning himself to any particular approach, appears to view case study from a post-positivist perspective (Harrison *et al*, 2017; Fearon *et al.*, 2021).

Yin (2018) claims that case studies create new knowledge by using exploratory strategies but can also be used for explanatory and descriptive studies. Due to the inflexibility in experimental or quasi-experimental research, Yin (2018) considers case studies can sometimes be the only feasible alternative. Due to this study's research aim and the limitations of other strategies, an interpretivist perspective to case study design was chosen, which closely aligned to the case study approach taken by Stake (1995) and Merriam (2009).

The case study approach is determined by the research questions or aim; the control the researcher has over the variables under investigation; the desired end product; and the identification of a bounded system as the focus of investigation (Merriam, 1998, p. 8). Table 3.3 outlines the elements and descriptors of the case study.

The case study should have a “case” which is the object of the study. Yin (2018) states the case should be a contemporary issue that can be investigated in its natural context using a multitude of different methods. Stake (2003, p. 134) has a more inclusive definition stating: “case study is defined by interest in individual cases”. The case, for example, can be an individual, a programme and differences in organisations (Baxter and Jack, 2008). Stake (1995) proposed three types of cases and study design frameworks. These include the intrinsic case which seeks to understand the particulars of a single case; an instrumental case study provides greater insight into an issue or to refine theory; a collective case is when more than one case is studied, with each case study studied holistically in its own right (Stake, 1995).

Element	Description
The case	<p>The case study is the area of interest or unit of analysis.</p> <p>The case can be a programme, an individual, a group or social situation, an organization, phenomena, or process.</p>
A bounded system	<p>Bounded by time, space, and activity.</p> <p>Incorporates a system of connections.</p> <p>Bounding applies structures to manage contextual variables.</p> <p>Boundaries between the case and context can be blurred.</p>
Studied in context	<p>The case is studied in its natural environment.</p> <p>Context is important to enhance understanding the case.</p> <p>Variable contextual areas can be considered e.g. social, political, economic, cultural, historical and/or organisational factors.</p>
In-depth study	<p>Chosen for in-depth analysis of an issue.</p> <p>Fieldwork is central to the process of the inquiry.</p> <p>Key - Understand the researcher's position and issues of subjectivity of their philosophical orientation of the research.</p> <p>Reflexivity is considered vital to support research credibility.</p>
Selecting the case	<p>Case is selected based on the study's aims and objectives.</p> <p>Involves decisions about people, settings, events, phenomena, social processes.</p> <p>Single or multiple case sampling.</p> <p>Broad: capture ordinary, unique, varied and/or accessible aspects.</p> <p>Methods: specified criteria, methodical and purposive; replication logic: theoretical or literal replication (Yin, 2018)</p>
Multiple sources of evidence	<p>Multiple sources of evidence for in-depth inquiry.</p> <p>Data collection methods often include interviews/focus groups, observations, document reviews and surveys/questionnaires.</p> <p>Methods of analysis vary and depend on data collection methods and cases; need to be systematic and rigorous (Yin, 2018).</p> <p>Triangulation is often used to improve study rigour.</p>
Case study design	<p>Descriptive, exploratory, explanatory, illustrative, evaluative.</p> <p>Single or multiple cases. Embedded or holistic (Yin, 2018).</p> <p>Particularistic, heuristic, descriptive (Merriam, 1998, 2009).</p> <p>Intrinsic, instrumental, and collective (Stake, 1995).</p>

Table 3.3 Elements and descriptors of case study (Adapted from Harrison et al, 2017)

3.1.6 *Deciding the number of cases*

Yin (2018) recommends inexperienced researchers begin with a simple case study due to the complexity of managing and analysing the large volumes of data. Although there is no ideal number of cases, there are several recommendations. Stake (1995) describes a collective case study as being when multiple cases are used to generate an even wider appreciation of a specific issue. A multiple case study enables the researcher to analyse the data within and across different situations. Evidence from multiple case studies is often viewed as being more robust (Yin, 2018). However, as collective (or multiple) case studies seek evidence in different contexts they do not necessitate direct comparisons (Stake, 2003). Rather, patterns of convergence and divergence are sought and similarities and differences between the cases can generate reliable evidence. Whilst there is no ideal number of cases Eisenhardt (1989) and Crabtree and Miller (1992) (cited in Ponelis, 2015) considered between 4 and 10 cases is an appropriate sample size.

Each 'case' in this research was to be studied in a concentrated, single inquiry approach. For this study, a multiple (Yin, 2018) or collective (Stake, 1995) case study was to be adopted to gain a wider appreciation of the phenomenon. An in depth thematic analysis exploring what is common about every participant's support needs and their experiences, and what is particular about each case was central to the study and is presented in the thematic findings in Chapter 4.

3.2 The present study

3.2.1 *Research aim and objectives*

The research aim and objectives were developed after undertaking a literature review on CEP. The research aim was: To explore how care experienced teenage parents (CEP) are supported to reduce the challenges associated with both leaving care and becoming a teenage parent.

The objectives set to achieve the overall aim were to:

1. Critically explore the protective factors and challenges that teenage CEP experience that impact on their parenting of their child.

2. Critically explore teenage CEP perceptions of their support needs when making their parenting choices.
3. Consider, from the experiences of Children's Services, carers and other significant individuals, wider systemic factors that enable or constrain their practice to support teenage CEP care for their child.
4. Generate evidence-based recommendations which may inform future policy, practice, further research and education.

A common error for case study researchers is to have a research question or objectives that are too broad in scope. Yin (2018) and Stake (1995) suggest binding the case to ensure setting realistic aims and to manage the data collection and analysis procedure. This collective (or multiple) case study design was bounded by time (child no older than 2 years of age), location (within a health board area), and the population of care experienced teenage parents (age 16–21).

3.2.2 The research design

The research design was a qualitative collective (multiple) case study, to explore how the care experienced teenage parents are supported to reduce the challenges associated with both leaving care and becoming a teenage parent. A collective case study enables the researcher to explore the complexities of each single case. Thereafter, similarities and the differences within and between the cases can be analysed (Stake, 1995; Jack and Baxter, 2008).

3.2.3 Ethical considerations

Petkovic *et al.* (2018) state that all research has the potential to cause harm, for instance due to possible discrimination, confidentiality issues, discomfort or undesirable reaction. The researcher had to consider the ethical implications in the early planning of the study. The research ethics committees needed to be assured that any anticipated risks, burdens or intrusions were minimised for the people taking part in the research and were justified by the expected benefits for the participants or for science and society (Health Research Authority, 2021). Gaining ethical approval was a carefully considered process within the design of this study. The dignity, rights, safety and well-being of the research participants and the researcher, needed to meet

the key ethical principles of beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy and justice when planning the research (Beauchamp and Childress, 2013). This study was designed and conducted to protect the following key ethical principles as identified by Beauchamp and Childress (2013). Appendices in Chapter 8, relating to data collection, evidence how the researcher sought to mitigate ethical issues.

Beneficence - to always do good: Beauchamp and Childress (2013) advised the principle of beneficence considers if the benefit of the study's method outweighed the potential risks. The other principle of non-maleficence - to do no harm, ensures the participants are not exposed to any physical or psychological harm (Beauchamp and Childress, 2013). Both of these ethical principles held the researcher accountable for prioritising the well-being of all the participants during the design and conduct of the study. In this study some of the questions were of a sensitive nature, with the potential to cause discomfort or embarrassment. The participant information sheets advised participants they did not have to answer any questions they found too uncomfortable or distressing. Examples of the semi-structured interview and focus group questions are provided (Appendices 8.16; 8.17; 8.18; 8.19). Parahoo (2014) stated that it is important the participants know they can withdraw from the study at any point. All participants were made aware that they could leave the study at any point with no explanation required and that their information would not be used.

Justice refers to the principle of fairness and openness to be established during the conduct of the study (Beauchamp and Childress, 2013). This concept emphasises equality amongst the participants and ensuring that the participants were all treated fairly. The participation information sheets (Appendices 8.8; 8.10; 8.12; 8.14) offered assurance there would be no preferential treatment or disadvantage to any participant should they decide not to participate in the research.

Autonomy is the ability to make decisions for oneself (Beauchamp and Childress, 2013). Respecting autonomy is especially an issue for certain groups of participants whose lack of power may mean they feel unable to refuse consent (Robson and McCartan, 2016). To protect against any potential coercion or bias due to possible feelings of power imbalance (Gray, 2018), participants were assured their involvement in the study was entirely voluntary and there would be no detriment to their care should they choose not to be involved. The concept of informed consent arises from the

ethical principle of autonomy and basic human rights (Robson and Caplan, 2016). Autonomy was reflected in the participant information sheets (Appendices 8.8; 8.10; 8.12; 8.14) and consent forms (Appendices 8.9; 8.11; 8.13; 8.15) and was reflected throughout the study.

As the researcher was employed as a nurse registrant, the researcher abided by the ethical considerations within the Nursing and Midwifery Code (2018) by primarily considering the interests of the participants, ensuring safe and effective practice and promoting professional trust. No medical or social records of any of the CEP were accessed by the researcher. There were no CEP on the researcher's caseload and thus no CEP known to the researcher were invited to participate in the study.

As recommended by Polit and Beck (2014), each participant was made aware their anonymity would be protected by the use of a pseudonym and that any identifiable information would be removed to protect their identity. Confidentiality to protect the participant's identity and maintain their privacy throughout the study and during dissemination of the results was ensured, as advised by Polit and Beck (2014). Although anonymity could not be guaranteed within the focus groups, as recommended by Robson and McCartan (2016), agreement from the social work participants about not sharing disclosed information from the focus group was achieved.

Electronic data and audio recordings were held on an encrypted password protected NHS device to which only the researcher had access. No identifiable information was stored on laptops or other portable or unsecured devices. Signed consent forms and scribed interview information were stored in a locked filing cabinet within secure health premises that only the researcher had access to. Any volunteers for the study received written assurance of the safe storage of their information and that the data would be held securely for a five-year period and then destroyed. Data were managed in accordance with NHS Scotland guidelines for the handling, storage, retrieval and disposal of data (Scottish Government, 2020), the Data Protection Act (2018) and was compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The researcher was aware of the need to be vigilant for any potential adult and child protection issues arising during the data collection. All participants were informed prior to data collection commencing that should any welfare concerns be identified, the

researcher would need to disclose this information in compliance with the National Guidance for Child Protection (Scottish Government, 2014c) and Adult Support and Protection Act (Scottish Government, 2014d).

The researcher's employment within the health board meant the researcher had experience and knowledge of supporting vulnerable teenage parents and was aware of the range of care and support that was available to them within their community. As a registered nurse, the researcher had professional relationships with other healthcare providers within the area. Written consent from the CEP was obtained to allow their GP to be contacted should there be any concerns for the participant's physical or emotional health during data collection.

Ethical approval was sought and obtained from the Health Research Authority (see Appendix 8.2). The University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee (see Appendix 3, section 8.3) and Research and Development approval from NHS Lanarkshire Research and Development Department (see Appendix 8.4).

3.2.4 *Recruitment process*

3.2.4.1 *Gaining access*

Stake (1995) suggests a brief scribed statement should be made about the case study research to gain permission to conduct the research, with plans for distribution included. The researcher contacted the senior health and social work managers within the two identified health and social care partnerships to advise of the research aim, objectives and ethical approval. Permission to invite health and social work staff to participate in the research was agreed by the Nurse Director for NHS Lanarkshire Health Board (see Appendix 5, section 8.5) and also by the senior managers within the two Health and Social Care Partnership areas (see Appendices 8.6 and 8.7).

Family nurses are experienced, qualified nurses or midwives. All the CEP participants in the study were engaging with the Family Nurse Partnership (FNP) within the two Health and Social Care Partnership areas.

The researcher was employed as an FNP supervisor working within the health board area and attended the FNP team meetings to discuss the study's aim and objectives,

inclusion criteria and to seek support for the recruitment process. The researcher was not actively providing care to any prospective participants.

3.2.4.2 Selection of cases

The sampling techniques selected within a research study need to reflect the research design and research question. The sampling process within qualitative studies utilises a non-probability technique of either convenience or purposive sampling (Parahoo, 2014). Whilst convenience sampling enables the researcher to select participants who are easily accessible or available, purposive sampling aids the selection of participants whose experiences are required for the study's aims (Bradshaw *et al.*, 2017). Purposive sampling was undertaken to ensure the participants could answer the study's focus.

3.2.4.3 Identifying the participants

Stake (1995) states that the cases are identified by sampling those participants who will provide rich information and are best able to answer the research questions. To support the identification of potential participants, the researcher attended the midwifery team lead professional forum, 4 family nurse partnership team meetings, and a locality child and family social work team meeting. A presentation was delivered detailing the aim of the study, ethical considerations and the inclusion and exclusion criteria (see Table 3.4) along with the relevant Participant Information Sheets for both the CEP and the FN (see Appendices 8.8 and 8.10). A presentation was also delivered to the Health Visitor (HV) Team Leaders via their professional forum. The HV Team Leaders' perception was that due to the eligibility criteria, the Family Nurses within the area would have been working with all of the CEP.

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Previously or currently 'looked after' or 'looked after and accommodated' in Scotland in local authority care, with foster carers and/or children's homes or having been 'looked after' by kinship carers.	No experience of being 'looked after' or 'looked after and accommodated' in Scotland.
Aged 16 - 19 years of age when the child was conceived.	Aged below 16 years or older than 19 years when child conceived.
'Looked after' young male and 'looked after' female parents, whether parenting their child together or apart.	
Parents whose youngest child is no older than two years of age.	Parents whose youngest child is over 2 years of age.
Local Authority Children's Services employees (including foster carers), Kinship carers, Health Visitors, Family Nurses, and Midwives.	Parent of a child who is affected by significant ill health.
Kinship carers and adult 'significant others' (for example siblings, partners) identified by the CEP.	'Significant others' under 16 years of age.

Table 3.4 Inclusion and exclusion criteria.

The CEP screened for their eligibility to voluntarily participate and were invited to the study by their Family Nurse (FN). The participant information sheets (PIS), (see Appendix 8.8) were made available to the CEP by their FN to inform their decision as to whether to engage in the research or not. In keeping with the ethical principles discussed in section 3.2.3, the CEP was assured by their FN that there would be no disadvantage to them should they decide not to participate in the study. A description of the extent of their involvement in this research was explained by their FN and these details were also included in the PIS. The researcher's contact details were included if the CEP required further information about the study. The FNs obtained permission from each CEP who expressed an interest in participating in the study for their contact details to be shared and for the researcher to contact them by phone. Following a 'cooling off' period of two weeks, the researcher contacted the CEP by phone to agree on a suitable time and venue for the interviews to take place.

The FNs voluntarily agreed that if any CEP on their caseload consented to join the research that they too would also consent to participate in a semi-structured interview. Participant Information Sheets were provided to the FNs (see Appendix 8.10).

The age range of CEP participants who volunteered (n=6) was 18-21 years. Further information about the CEP who volunteered and participated (pseudonyms used) is summarised in Figure 3.2. FNs identified 9 CEP as wishing to participate. However, due to various challenges in contacting the CEP (see section 6.2.1 page 170) 3 CEP were unable to participate. Table 3.5 provides details of the CEP profiles who participated in the study.

<p>Linda: Age 16 first birth FN Rose SO did not participate in study.</p>	<p>In various residential care settings from aged 14-16 years due to physical abuse from family and exploited by older men. Not engaged in training or employment.</p>
<p>Rebecca: Age 16 first birth FN: Carolyn SO Housing Officer: Lorraine</p>	<p>Removed as a young child, due to neglect and sexual abuse within family. In kinship care initially then foster care aged 3-16 years. Not engaged in training or employment.</p>
<p>Ashleigh: Age 16 first birth FN Marion SO did not participate in study</p>	<p>Two foster care settings infancy - 16 years due to parental neglect (substance misuse). Experienced sexual abuse in later childhood. 2nd pregnancy aged 18 resulted in miscarriage. Not engaged in training or employment.</p>
<p>Bronwyn: Age 19 first birth FN Trudi SO did not participate in study</p>	<p>In kinship initially and foster care aged 7-17 years due to sexual abuse as a young child. Not engaged in training or employment.</p>
<p>Nadia: Age 19 first birth FN: Pam SO Mental Health Officer: Caryn</p>	<p>In residential care aged 12-17 years due to neglect associated with parent's poor mental health/substance abuse. Exploited by males. Not engaged in training or employment.</p>
<p>Emily: Age 17 first birth FN: Liza Mother and baby foster carer: Fran</p>	<p>In foster care aged 13 -17 years due to neglect and parental learning difficulties. Not engaged in training or employment.</p>

Table 3.5 CEP profiles and FN and SO (pseudonyms used to protect anonymity).

The case construct is illustrated in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1 Case study construct for each CEP.

Significant others (SO), people who the CEP found to be important supports in their life, were identified by the CEP. The contact details for the SO were provided by the CEP and the researcher contacted the SO either by phone or email. A Participation Information Sheet (see Appendix 8.12) about the study was sent to the SO via post or email. Four CEP identified their partners as their SO and one CEP identified her sister. However, their partners and the sister chose not participate in the study (see section 6.2.1 page 174) and three of the CEP were unable to identify any other SO in their life. Two of the SO who participated were employed by the local authority, one as a Mental Health Officer and one as a Housing Support Worker. Another SO was a supported Foster Carer who worked in another locality authority area. Agreement was reached to meet in their workplace or in the foster carer's home to conduct the interview.

To enable a sense checking of the data emerging from the case studies and to gain a wide and collective perspective of support for CEP on leaving care and becoming new parents, a presentation about the study's aim and objectives were delivered at a Child and Family Social Work meeting. Invites to participate in a focus group were offered and the Participant Information Sheets (see Appendix 8.14) were provided. Nine social

work staff, all experienced in working with care experienced parents, volunteered to participate in the study (see Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2 Social Work participants.

3.2.5 Data collection methods

Methods refer to the tools and procedures used to collate the research evidence. The methods used to collect the data must be compatible with the philosophical, epistemological, and ontological assumptions of the research (Yin, 2014) and the researcher's theoretical perspective (Rehman and Alharthi, 2016). In accordance with Stake's (1995) recommendations, various sources of evidence were collated to ensure the issue was explored through 'a variety of lenses' allowing multiple aspects of the phenomenon to be exposed and understood (Baxter and Jack, 2008). The use of various data collection methods allowed for a more conclusive case study and data to be triangulated for improved dependability and credibility (Stake, 1995; Houghton *et al.*, 2013).

3.2.5.1 Interviews

Interviews were conducted as a data collection method. Interviews are useful to gather insightful subjective data from participants on their views and lived experiences (Stake, 1995). The researcher discussed the consent form with each participant to ensure their understanding and signed consent was obtained prior to each interview (see

Appendix 8.9; 8.11; 8.13 and 8.14). This study adopted two different interview approaches to gather information from the case study and the SW participants.

- Face-to-face interviews with CEP, Significant Others and Family Nurses (Case study).
- Focus group interviews with SW (experienced in working with CEP).

Yin (2014) states the findings from the literature review including the evidence gaps identified can appropriately inform the focus of the areas for exploration in the interview process (Yin, 2014). The themes from the literature review helped the researcher to formulate the semi-structured interview questions.

Stake (1995) and Stake (1998) give particular emphasis to the role of the case study researcher. For this study, the researcher recognised the importance of illustrating both the stories and the complexities of the CEP lives, providing the reader with 'good raw material' and thick description for the reader to reach their own conclusions. Stake (1995) describes interviews as the main route to discover and portray the multiple realities of the cases.

Qualitative research usually necessitates a feeling of trust between the researcher and participant(s). The face-to-face interviews provide participants with the opportunity to engage on a one-to-one basis with the researcher within a safe relationship (Stake, 1995). The researcher attended each interview with a simple pre-prepared semi-structured interview schedule based on the literature review findings (see Appendix 16, section 8.16; Appendix 17, section 8.17; Appendix 18, section 8.18) to facilitate discussion and sharing of personal experiences. As suggested by Robson and McCartan, (2016) the interview began with introductions and demographic questions to establish a rapport, with more complex and sensitive questions asked at the end of the interview.

Individual semi-structured interviews, which lasted no longer than one hour included 6 CEP, 6 FN and 3 SO.

The researcher used a conversational tone with the participants during the semi-structured interviews, attentive listening (Stake, 1995, Yin, 2018), pacing (Vandermause and Fleming, 2011) and using communication skills of open questions, reflecting and summarising to ensure their perspective was being understood. Other

questions evolved during the semi-structured interview. The flexibility of the semi-structured interview is described by Robson and McCartan (2016) as enabling the use of probing questions and, where necessary, to miss out particular questions. The flow of the semi-structured interview was mainly driven by the participant who was encouraged to take the conversation in an unanticipated direction and elaborate about whatever the participant viewed as relevant, to describe their experiences and perceptions.

Incomplete questioning as suggested by Vandermause and Fleming (2011) was used for example '*Did you get talks about em puberty or....?*' to draw the participant into the discussion and to elicit their natural response. Due to the sensitive nature of some of the questions and to minimise the potential for harm (Parahoo, 2014), the participants emotional well-being was of the utmost importance. The researcher sought verbal and non-verbal cues from the participant to assess whether to continue with the line of inquiry if there were occasions the participant seemed reticent, uncomfortable or embarrassed about responding to the questions.

3.2.5.2 Field Notes

Field notes are generally endorsed in qualitative research as a means of documenting the required contextual information and are an essential feature of rigorous qualitative research (Phillippi and Lauderdale, 2018). The field notes for interviews and focus groups were recorded immediately after the interviews and focus group. The researcher documented how the participants related to others in their setting, details of the interview setting, the researcher's impact on the setting as well as issues of rapport as to how the participant related to the researcher and also how the researcher related to the participant.

3.2.5.3 Focus Group Interview

Robson and McCartan (2016) advised that focus groups have the advantage of yielding a high amount of qualitative data that can be inexpensively collated at the one time. Further benefits are the dynamics within the groups allow for the participants to stimulate each other's thoughts while allowing collective or opposing views can be assessed. Robson and McCartan (2016) cautioned that the focus group needs to be

well facilitated to ensure a particular individual's views do not dominate and to manage potential conflict that may occur between participants.

Themes emerging from the data gathered from the semi-structured interviews with the CEP, FN and SO were explored at the focus group with the child and family social workers who were experienced in working with care experienced teenage parents. The focus group enabled a vital 'sense checking' of the themes and an understanding of commonalities and variations from a different perspective (Wibeck and Linner, 2021). The focus group also allowed the opportunity to gather any new insights into challenges or opportunities for social workers and their wider systemic experiences about how their practice was enabled or constrained to support CEP (see figure 3.3). This approach gained an additional collective perspective and the criticality of the claims that were raised in the preceding interviews (Stake, 1995).

Figure 3.3 Diagram illustrating themes from case studies and sense checking with social work staff experienced in working with teenage CEP.

The potential difficulty in using the focus group method was the potential for the facilitator to influence the participant's responses and to misrepresent the information (Parahoo, 2014). To minimise this, questions were mainly open ended to explore and

expanded upon the observations of the professionals (see Appendix 8.19). Although the focus group provided the opportunity to gather a wide range of information, due to the nature of the process, the opportunity to probe for deeper responses (as was possible during the individual interview with the CEP enable) was limited. The dynamics that occurred within the focus group generated discussion and debate and gave deeper insights into individual beliefs, priorities, pressures and workplace cultural values.

3.2.5.4 Setting

The researcher and the participants mutually agreed a naturalistic setting where the participants felt comfortable about sharing their story. Each of the CEP requested the interview took place in their home. Home visits were conducted by the researcher in accordance to the NHS Lone Working Policy. Professionals were interviewed or participated in a focus group in their workplace setting. Interviews and the focus group were recorded on an encrypted device. No participant in the study refused consent to audio record, which minimised the potential for misquoting the participants and ensured reliable data analysis.

3.2.5.5 Timescale

The data were collated over a 14-month period.

3.3 Rigour

This section describes the planning of the present study to enhance the research rigour.

3.3.1 Triangulation

Yin (2018) states that triangulating various data sources improves the validity of a study by reducing the potential of bias that may occur from single measures. Using the constructivist worldview where truth is relative and constructed, triangulation refers to finding and documenting the different perspectives. Denzin (2012) argues that triangulation is not a strategy for validation, but instead the use of multiple methods, or triangulation, is an attempt to reach an in-depth understanding of the particular phenomenon and is used as a strategy to add rigour, Denzin (2009) (cited in Fusch *et al*, 2018) identified 4 types of triangulation:

1. Data triangulation is related to 3 data points of people, time and space. Different data from these data points are collected over a period of time and commonalities are discovered.
2. Investigator triangulation is when 2 researchers investigate the same issue and each researcher obtains the same data.
3. Theory triangulation relates to different theoretical lenses being applied to the data set or for the raw data to be reviewed to develop a new theory.
4. Methodological triangulation is triangulating the data from various sources e.g. observations, focus groups and interviews.

In this study, qualitative data from the case studies were triangulated with the data from the focus group with the social work staff to seek any similarities or differences in the information. For the purpose of this current study, methodological triangulation was used.

3.3.2 Data analysis

An in depth analysis exploring what is common about each CEP's support needs and their experiences, and what is particular about each 'case', was central to the study. Whilst in positivist research a unique finding would be seen as problematic, Stake (1995) states that for the qualitative case study, identifying the uniqueness of a case is an important aim. Stake (1995) acknowledges the value of data analysis procedures to minimise the potential of the researcher misrepresenting the findings. Stake (1995) also encourages researchers to conduct data collection and analyse processes simultaneously, to include the researcher's initial impressions and intuitions alongside the completed findings.

The use of a named framework for data analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Clarke and Braune, 2013) is essential to demonstrate the rigour of the study. The thematic analysis coding process of Braun and Clarke (2006) ensured the internal validity of the study as the researcher followed the systematic approach, in consultation with her academic supervisors. This was in order to minimise research bias.

The interviews and focus group generated a high volume of qualitative data. All participants consented to the interviews being audio-recorded. The researcher

transcribed each recorded session verbatim. A rigorous and detailed account of all verbal, as well as non-verbal content (e.g. pauses, looking embarrassed, tearful etc.) was documented, as suggested by Stake, (1995). In transcribing the interviews, the researcher frequently checked the transcripts against the audio recording to ensure accuracy. Once the accuracy of transcripts was confirmed, the next stage was to conduct inductive thematic analysis of the qualitative data generated from the participants in the case studies and from the focus group.

Thematic analysis is a process for identifying patterns or themes within qualitative data. The aim of thematic analysis is to identify recurring patterns in the data that are significant or interesting and subsequently use these themes to address a particular issue or research question. As discussed in section 3.10, Braun and Clarke (2006) provide a thematic analysis framework to ensure qualitative data is analysed systematically and consistently and to capture the essence of meaning running throughout the data. This capture of a recurrent pattern is defined as a theme. A subtheme tends to emerge when it is related and shared with the concept in the identified theme but focuses more on one specific element (Braun and Clarke, 2013).

Thematic analysis is more complex than merely summarising the data as it also interprets and makes sense of the data collated. Braun and Clarke (2006) identified two levels of themes: semantic and latent. Semantic themes are described as when the data meaning is clear and no further interpretation of what the participant has communicated is required. The latent level looks beyond what the participant has said to examine the basic ideas, values and beliefs that are captured within the data provided. To achieve interpretive rigour, the researcher must evidence how interpretations of the data have been reached and to show authenticity in the findings, with quotations given from the raw data (Rice and Ezzy, 1999; Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006). Using the participants' own words through the use of direct quotes to support the interpretation, strengthens the validity and credibility of the research (Patton, 2002, Eldh *et al.*, 2020).

Table 3.6 provides the six steps of the Thematic Analysis Framework the researcher used to analyse the 16 transcripts of qualitative data in a consistent and systematic way (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Phase	Example of procedure for each step
Familiarising oneself with the data	The researcher became familiar with the depth of information collated and immersed in each participant experience. The researcher firstly listened to all the recorded interviews prior to any transcribing, to actively listen to and identify the primary issues raised. The process of transcribing the audio recordings, resulted in frequently re-listening to the recording and reading and re-reading and noting down initial thoughts. Inductive thematic analysis involved the identification, analysis and reporting patterns of meaning emerging from the data.
Generating initial codes	The researcher reviewed each of the transcripts to identify significant statements and formulated meaning from the interesting features of the data coded in a systematic way. Coding is described as reducing volumes of data into small 'chunks of meaning' (McGuire and Delahunt, 2017). The review of the data considered both the similarities and diversities. Thematic analysis is described as "the researcher's reflective and thoughtful engagement with their data and their reflexive and thoughtful engagement with the analytic process" (Braun and Clarke, 2019, p. 594). Codes represent the researcher's interpretations of patterns of meaning held within the data. The coding process evolved throughout the analytical process (Braun et al., 2019). Familiarity with the data and the frequent reviewing and seeking similarities and discrepancies from the significant statements in turn resulted in renewed patterns of meaning.
Searching for the themes	Through the coding process, codes important to the research question and similar to each other were grouped together into potential themes and emerging sub-themes. Braun and Clarke (2006, 2013) clarified that there are no firm rules about what constitutes a theme and it is considered to be what the researcher views as significant from the qualitative data available.
Involved reviewing the themes	This involved checking that the initial themes work in relation to the coded extracts and the entire data set. This resulted in an emerging thematic map.
Defining and naming themes	This step involved ongoing analysis by the researcher to further refine the specifics of each theme and generation of clear names for each theme. This final review included how the themes and sub-themes interacted and related to each other (Braun and Clarke, 2006). At the end of this process 3 main themes and 10 associated sub themes were identified.
Producing the report	This final step provided the researcher with the opportunity to select appropriate extracts; discussion of the analysis: relate back to the research question and produce the final report on the findings.

Table 3.6 Use of Braun and Clarke's Thematic Analysis Framework (2006, 2013, 2019).

There are a range of generic tools and tactics that can support this process of analysis and theory generation. Specialist software such as NUD'IST and NVivo was

considered as these software packages supports coding and analysis of large amounts of data in a time saving and efficient way (Richards, 2005). However, despite the benefits of the software, the researcher followed the guidance of Stake (1995); Polit and Beck, (2003); Vaismoradi *et al.* (2013) who advised that the researcher should stay immersed in the data during the coding stage to ensure that a strong focus on interpretation remained.

Methodological rigour and trustworthiness of the data analysis process were enhanced by a thorough, inclusive and carefully judged coding process, together with regular discussion with the supervisory team about the process and the concepts identified in the data. Consensus was reached relating to the key issues raised by participants within the case studies. Data analysis was considered complete when the researcher and supervisors considered the main theme and subthemes to be coherent, distinctive, and all inconsistencies reviewed and agreed upon. The final review of the themes and subthemes considered how these interacted and related to each other (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

The research used several data methods to ensure the rigour of the research process and the validity of the data. Table 3.7 provides a summary of the researcher's approach to increase the research rigour.

Approach to improve rigour	Trustworthiness	Credibility	Transferability	Confirmability	Dependability	Auditability	Bias
Interviews and focus group recorded to ensure accuracy	✓	✓			✓		
Semi-structured interview aide-mémoire/ prompts	✓				✓		
Researchers open body language/tone of voice	✓						✓
Field notes taken	✓				✓	✓	
Braun and Clarke's Thematic analysis framework used	✓						
Researcher transcribed and was immersed in data to seek truth	✓	✓					
Reviewed significant statements with supervisors	✓	✓					
Themes emerged from participants direct quotes	✓	✓				✓	
Analysis discussed with supervisors	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓
Rich/thick description of findings	✓		✓			✓	
Triangulation of findings.	✓	✓	✓				
Reflective diary during data collection	✓			✓	✓		
Reflexivity	✓			✓		✓	✓

Table 3.7 Researcher's approach to improving rigour (Adapted from Polit and Beck, 2014 pp. 324-325)

Chapter 4. Findings

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the findings from the 6 case studies. The study aimed to explore how care experienced teenage parents (CEP) are supported to reduce the challenges associated with both leaving care and becoming a teenage parent. An overview of the case studies used for the data collection and details of the thematic analysis process and interpretation will be presented. Findings may be of interest to policymakers and key stakeholders including CEP, children and young people's health care professionals and social work staff. An example of further information obtained from the data analysis will be provided for the reader in the appendices (see Appendix 20, section 8.20).

4.2 Research data

Qualitative data obtained from the semi-structured interviews (n=15) were collated over the six case studies outlined in Figure 4.1. All six case studies included a CEP (n=6) and their corresponding Family Nurse (n=6) with three case studies also incorporating a third participant deemed by the CEP to be a significant other in their care (n=3). The semi-structured interview schedule was informed by the themes identified in the literature review. The nature of the questions posed offered some structure with a degree of freedom for participants to share their experiences and comments from their perspective as advised by Cohen *et al.* (2017). Prompt questions were used by the researcher to keep the interview focussed on the area of investigation and promote the participants to provide further clarification of issues raised.

Following the semi-structured interviews, a focus group was subsequently conducted with child and family social workers (n=9) who were either employed in through care and after care or child protection work with CEP in general. The initial themes emerging from the case studies were 'sense checked' by the social work participants. The key themes also generated discussion and debate between the social workers who shared their own experience of supporting CEP and their views as to what challenges and opportunities they encountered in their practice.

Three themes and ten subthemes were confirmed in the final step of the data analysis process. This close association and interaction evident between the themes and subthemes are intimately intertwined. This complicated and challenged how the findings are presented in a meaningful way for the reader. Therefore, the individual themes and related subthemes will mainly be addressed separately for ease of explanation to ensure each theme is attributed with the associated and embedded complexities impacting on the experiences of CEP. Where appropriate, other collated sub-themes will be summarised in tables. Once this has been completed then the intimate relationship, interaction and any specific issues will be summarised. Figure 4.1 summarises the range of interlinking themes identified and associated subthemes.

Figure 4.1 Interlinking themes and sub themes

To provide clarity and context the identification of the participant as a social worker reflects that this quote was sourced from the focus group. Square brackets are used in this section to provide clarify and context, to add emphasis as perceived by the researcher or to show a change in the original transcription e.g. ... [I had] tears and covered in sweat [testifying in court]. Parentheses are used following quotes from participants involved in the semi-structured interviews e.g. (Bronwyn). Parentheses were also for all social work quotes (e.g., Brian, Social Worker).

To indicate a pause ... is used and a break between 2 related sections of text is indicated by

4.2.1 *Trauma: Shadows of childhood*

Experience of multiple chronic and complex traumatic events clearly impacted on the young mothers' emotions, behaviours, poor coping strategies and limited capacity in their decision-making. These experiences of childhood trauma are long-lasting and continued to contribute to the everyday challenges the young women encountered as they left care and adjusted to parenthood. Therefore, this main theme relates specifically to trauma which has had an overcast effect on the young mothers' childhood memories with a profound and enduring negative impact on their adult life.

Trauma is the response arising after exposure to an event or series of events of an extremely threatening, distressing, disturbing or horrific nature, most commonly prolonged or repetitive events that overwhelm an individual's coping ability and from which escape is difficult or impossible (Margolin and Vickerman, 2007). Complex post-traumatic stress disorder (complex PTSD) can result after experiencing distressing event/s that may be difficult to escape from (e.g., torture, slavery, genocide, sustained intimate partner violence and childhood sexual or physical abuse) (WHO, 1997). Complex PTSD is demonstrated by enduring problems of emotional regulation, low self-belief and feelings of shame and guilt in connection to the traumatic event and challenges in forming and maintaining relationships (Brewin, 2020). These symptoms can significantly impact on the individuals functioning within their family, education and career (Brewin, 2020).

All young mothers reported being subjected to some form of chronic trauma through neglect and/or abuse in their childhood. Although the CEP were not asked to disclose

the specific types of child abuse they had endured, during the interviews each of them raised and reflected on their childhood experiences of abuse and/or neglect from their parent/s and extended family. The 3 subthemes that are discussed below are: Shame and self-blame; numbing and repressed memories and triggers.

4.2.1.1 Shame and self-blame

Evidence of shame and self-blame permeated through the transcripts of young women. Shame is defined as being a self-assessment of being 'bad' or 'wrong' (Brown, 2006). Feelings relating to shame and self-blame are driven by concerns and negative perceptions of how individuals are viewed by others (Lee *et al.*, 2001) and involve an assessment or judgement of the self as being 'bad' or 'wrong' (Brown, 2006). Self-blame is associated with poor long-term adjustment for survivors of CSA (Wyatt and Newcomb, 1990).

One example is evidenced by Bronwyn who revealed she suffered from low self-worth and anxiety when legal charges were brought against her abuser. Despite having a strong feeling of wanting justice, her own poor self-image impacted on her mental health.

... ... [I had] tears and covered in sweat [testifying in court] because obviously I was feeling disgusting, it just gives you that feeling, and it was a vicious circle from then on. (Bronwyn)

A further example related to Linda who shared information about being removed from her mother to her father's home, due to her mother's physical abuse and lifestyle behaviours. She described being angry and behaving aggressively when she was moved to live with her father. Linda was later also removed from her father's home at age 14 due to her risk of exploitation from older adult men, and concerns about her having unprotected sex from age 13-14 years with unknown males. During the interview Linda looked embarrassed, expressed genuine remorse, shame, and a sense of incredulity about how she threatened her Dad and assaulted the carers in the children's homes.

I was just getting worse, and worse, and worse [looks embarrassed]. I threatened to stab my dad with a pair of scissors. (Linda)

Over a two-year period, Linda was placed in several care placements and shared information about a few occasions when she was unable to regulate her emotions, as the various children's staff attempted to implement boundaries. Linda found it difficult to settle into the children's homes. She struggled to understand the rules in the home, and whilst Linda continued to show embarrassment about her behaviour, she felt the staff contacting the police was too draconian. Apologies, which were initially accepted and led Linda to believe the relationship was mended, were later rejected and trust diminished.

Ugh... my first care placement was the worse. One of the women pushed me out the office and, because I grabbed her fingers, she phoned the police and got me arrested, saying I'd assaulted her but, I had just grabbed her... She never phoned the police straight away she was like, "look we will all apologise; we made up and that" ... I woke up the next morning to the door banging and the police were there... And this just all gets worse, like genuinely, I never meant to hurt any of the staff. (Linda)

Linda was subsequently moved to another children's house where she felt more settled and enjoyed the range of activities the second home provided. However, she was again moved, and her relationship with the staff in the next placement was more difficult for her. On one occasion, Linda was held in a restraint hold by staff and she stated she kicked out at this, causing one of the worker's arms to be injured. Whilst Linda thought all had again been forgiven, during her pregnancy she was later summoned to court for this alleged assault.

I left [the home] when I was 16. And the couple of, like months after that, I got a phone call from my social worker saying, 'you've missed court'. And I was like that, "what do you mean? I haven't done anything?", and he was like "aye, well you assaulted her, you broke her arm an' that" ... it was just an accident but, naebody believes me. (Linda)

During the interview, Linda presented herself as a gentle, thoughtful, good-natured young woman. This persona was confirmed by Rose, her Family Nurse (FN) who initially was fearful of visiting Linda due to her alleged aggressive and negative reputation reported by social work. Rose considered her involvement with Linda during

pregnancy and until her child turned 2 years. She reported finding Linda to be a really nice young woman who was remorseful of her previous actions.

... at first, I thought am I seeing the true person here, because ah was very aware of the background details I had been given. And he [her partner] was a very quiet gentle guy, so I could nae imagine him going wi' someone who was aggressive. And I've never even saw her being even passive-aggressive, anything like that... I never heard her raise her voice. I think within the [children's houses] Someone had taken her phone aff her and she kicked out... She was very remorseful and very worried and angry about this pending court case... saying "will I lose my baby; will I go to prison?" (Rose, FN)

Some young mothers disclosed feeling fearful they would be viewed by services as unworthy of being a parent. These strong emotions and feelings demonstrated by young mothers clearly reflected their low self-worth. For example, Rebecca voiced shame due to being both homeless and care experienced.

... [meeting the Family Nurse was] quite scary an' all, cause at that point, I (had just moved to a homeless hostel and was) trying to get everything settled in and obviously got a phone call saying, I'd... a Family Nurse. So, I was pure worrying in case anybody said anything about it. And then she came out, and she was actually, all right. ... (I was worried) in case the Family Nurse was saying [hesitates] in case anything... like... because, obviously with me being a care kid it was always in my head, I might get the wean take aff me... So, that's why I was scared. In case a Family Nurse came out and said, "yer no able to keep it". So, that was my main worry throughout it all. Especially with being in care and... homeless unit. That's how I felt. (Rebecca)

Vulnerable women during and in the first year following birth are at a higher risk of maternal death and suicide (Orsolini *et al.*, 2016; Knight, 2019; Knight *et al.*, 2019). These vulnerabilities are further complicated when the women have numerous problems, including delayed access to maternity services, substance abuse, poverty, mental health diagnosis and intimate partner violence (Knight *et al.*, 2019; Bunch and Knight, 2020).

Ashleigh did not engage with maternity services until late in her pregnancy. Therefore, this created a considerable health risk to both herself and her unborn child. The fear of judgement and potentially having her child removed from her care were possible reasons why Ashleigh delayed engaging with maternity services. Ashleigh also suffered sexual abuse in her childhood which had a profound effect on her emotional well-being. Therefore, she was perhaps unable to attend due to her fear of being vulnerable and consenting to the intimacy of midwifery care required, despite her conflicting fear of pregnancy loss. Following a visit from her social worker, Ashleigh was taken to register with maternity services for the first time when she was over eight months gestation. She explained she delayed engaging with maternity services as she was concerned about being viewed as an unfit mother if social work were notified. She also blamed herself for being fearful of engaging earlier with maternity services and she seemed to have some awareness of the health risks to her unborn baby.

Oh, it was later on [I went to the midwife] ... it was a lot later on... I was just scared. Like with everything as well, 'cause I just kept thinking I was going to lose her, and I didn't want to go to the scan in case there was no baby in there. And I was freaking out. (Ashleigh)

The FN appropriately arranged Ashleigh's scan and supported her to attend her midwifery appointments to ensure no pregnancy complications. The FN recognised the health implications and risks for mother and baby and the practical challenges involved in travelling to access maternity services. She explained that Ashleigh was apprehensive about losing the pregnancy and feared having her baby taken into care after birth.

When [the concealed pregnancy] was explored with Ashley... There were several explanations... she had some bleeding earlier in pregnancy... and thought she was miscarrying... however, as the pregnancy advanced... she shared that she was worried her baby would be taken into care... it was just through fear she didn't want to alert services about her pregnancy. (Marion, FN)

4.2.1.2 Numbing

Emotional numbing relates to a state in which an individual is not expressing or feeling emotions (Kerig *et al.*, 2016). The numbing of feelings is the defining symptom in

emotional blunting and relates to the internal feelings of the individual characterised by reduced responsiveness and a feeling of detachment from the external environment (Horowitz, 1993). Previous research with young people has associated emotional numbing to the experience of trauma. This results in intense emotions such as overpowering fear, anxiety or dread with these effects enduring for a lifetime (Litz *et al.*, 2002). The numbing of positive emotions has been linked to other mental health disorders in particular depression (Kerig *et al.*, 2016).

It was disclosed during the interviews that a third of the CEP had been sexually abused. Each of these CEP appeared to have used alcohol and drugs in an attempt to numb and suppress their difficult emotions. These factors further complicated their vulnerability and risk factors for maternal health and pregnancy outcomes. It was evident the trauma they had experienced had a profound impact on their emotional and psychological well-being.

Emily's FN considered the challenges experienced when trying to engage Emily in the Family Nurse Programme during her pregnancy. The FN came to realise Emily's reluctance to engage with the programme was due to the extent of emotional stress she was feeling whilst living in an abusive relationship.

I assumed it was because of this learning disability, however shortly after her baby was born, when her baby was two weeks old, em, Emily actually moved from where she was staying and moved to another authority, and overnight it was a completely different relationship. Her level of understanding seemed different, em, she seemed to really get things more... She was very uncomfortable in her old environment, she was quite frightened... mm, not actually of her partner which was what we had first suspected, but of his mum. (Liza, FN)

This emotional numbing response was further supported by Emily's foster carer. She highlighted that Emily's stress reaction was clearly evident when her partner's mother became angry and confrontational at a multi-agency social work meeting.

She won't show her emotions straight away because she will be slow to display it ... I feel like she is actually thinking, should I be getting upset here? Should I be getting frightened here? Should I be getting annoyed here? And she won't get annoyed... it's like talk about a rabbit frozen in

the headlights... in that situation she just stood there and stared... to have lived for almost a year in that house... she would have been tiptoeing about just trying to make sure she didn't upset anyone. (Fran, Foster Carer)

Linda guardedly explained how older males introduced her to drugs and alcohol. The use of drugs had a profound negative impact on her behaviour. Linda was excluded from school due to misusing substances when she was aged 14 and this appeared to mark the end of her school education. Whilst recognising her behaviour in school was difficult to manage, Linda also felt scapegoated for supplying another pupil with drugs.

I didn't leave [school] I got kicked out because I took drugs and went into school on drugs, and another girl wanted to join me. So, I let her do it, and she said [on being challenged by the teaching staff that] I spiked her, so it was my own fault. I wasn't exactly perfect before that. That's just me. I just lost my head for a wee bit. (Linda)

Bronwyn discussed using substances shortly after she left foster care, something she had previously never experimented with. Bronwyn appeared to be socially isolated on leaving care. She felt the loss of emotional support from her foster carer, at a time when the trial against her perpetrator was ongoing. At only 16 years, Bronwyn gained access to her social work file, and gained details of the childhood sexual abuse she had suffered. In an attempt to numb the difficult emotions this evoked, Bronwyn turned to substance misuse. The detrimental extent of her drug abuse was evident during early pregnancy.

So, because I was living with it day in and day out. I shut it out. And there were other drug users there [in the homeless unit] ... doing drugs at that time as well. I was using cocaine. Like, I was really, really bad on cocaine. (Bronwyn)

Bronwyn's FN affirmed the complexity of behaviours that Bronwyn displayed. She explained Bronwyn had a history of a very chaotic lifestyle, drug misuse and gastric ulcers, because of her excess alcohol consumption and significant cocaine use.

During pregnancy, she was referred to [Family Nurse Partnership] as having a severe cocaine addiction... ... I think the drugs affected her mood and mental health as well. (Trudi, FN)

4.2.1.3 Repressed memories and triggers

Theorists of post-traumatic stress disorder have discussed the varied involuntary triggers of intrusive memories that cause intense emotions similar to the events of the original trauma they endured (Ehlers *et al.*, 2004). The survivors of trauma, such as childhood sexual abuse (CSA), behave or feel in the same way as they did during or immediately after the traumatic event they experienced because the brain does not differentiate what happened in the past from what they are currently experiencing. Ehlers *et al.* (2002) found the trigger can be cues that do not have significant connections to the trauma, but were stimuli that had immediately preceded the event (e.g., a tone of voice, a sound, a touch). Triggers are personal and can be debilitating, with individuals often left feeling confused about their responses, as they may not even have recognised that they had experienced one (Ehlers *et al.*, 2004).

As trauma sufferers, several of the young mothers experienced triggers, had intrusive thoughts and demonstrated emotion-related disorders. These included feelings of anxiety fear, depression and thought of self-harm. Rebecca's housing support worker advised that Rebecca struggled to cope with her emotions during her pregnancy, which coincided with a court hearing against her abuser. Her self-harming behaviour was clearly linked to the abuse she had received.

... she [Rebecca] was a self-harmer... but the main concern for me was the eating. She would get obsessive wi' it. She would use a measuring tape to measure the circumference of her wrists, and her ankles, and her thighs, and her arms, and things like that. And I just had alarm bells everywhere. (Lorraine, Housing support worker)

Rebecca told her FN of early negative childhood memories, and how these continue to adversely affect her. She had a clear memory of being physically removed from her own parents when she was only three years old. The vivid memories Rebecca had of the fear she felt on being driven from her home have had a significant impact on her affinity to trust others. This is seen in her reluctance to engage honestly, openly and transparently with agencies.

... she still has got that worry... if a car comes into the street... she has the fear, and worry comes back and she is terrified... she feels scrutinised and feels as if she does one thing wrong that the baby will be removed

from her. It is my opinion... that's why she maybe withholds, or maybe isn't quite as forward with certain amounts of information, 'cause she knows that does need to be shared [amongst agencies]. (Carolyn, FN)

Despite an improvement in Rebecca's mental health following the birth of her baby, her FN recognised how fragile her mental health remained. Rebecca remained vulnerable to triggers resulting in her adverse behaviours including self-harming and suicide attempts. One example relates to Rebecca happily watching a movie at home with her family when she was exposed to a trigger resulting in her attempt to commit suicide. Whilst Rebecca attempted to portray that she was coping well, her FN remained concerned about her vulnerability.

There was one [evening] incident that she actually texted me... she was having suicidal thoughts... I had to get the police involved to ensure the safety of her and the baby... Later on, what Rebecca described was that she was watching a film... and it was about someone being suicidal in the film, and I suppose it made me realise how vulnerable she was, and how something like that could trigger her. (Carolyn, FN)

Rebecca's mental health continued to be a concern as she could be triggered to engage in self-harming behaviours at any time. This was exacerbated by her lack of social and emotional support from those around her, which tended to intensify Rebecca's behaviours. Despite Rebecca engaging with her GP and taking antidepressant medication, her FN considered that stress could cause a deterioration in Rebecca's mental health condition.

*... .. em, I think any further stress could trigger her mental health problems again... it's not dealt with as such, it has not healed.
(Carolyn, FN)*

Persistent poor mental health from early adolescence was evident with Nadia who was exposed to years of neglect and abuse experienced at home, as her own mother struggled with her own mental state. Despite being removed from the abusive environment, Nadia's mental health continued to decline in the children's home. At aged 15, Nadia was moved to a long-term residential mental health facility for 2 years. The mental health issues Nadia persistently struggled with included self-harm, anxiety and depression.

I was hospitalised... through my mental health problems. I would struggle with my like, numerous things to do with me like, my anxiety, depression and self-harm and everything. (Nadia)

Nadia's mental health officer claimed the extent of Nadia's self-harming was extreme. She felt this self-harming was Nadia's way of expressing her pain.

The self-harm was a way of expressing that pain. Eh, and it was difficult to see, it was difficult to see her coming through that... I mean the self-harming were some of the worst that I have seen... Initially she was under eh, the Mental Health Act and that involved short term detentions. (Caryn, MHO)

The transition to motherhood is a significant event in any woman's life (Nelson, 2002). The majority of the young mothers shared the joy they felt after their child's birth. However, pregnancy and childbirth for one young woman who suffered childhood sexual abuse caused her significant distress. Bronwyn shared her negative experience of the birth of her child as being hard to endure. In early labour, her unborn child was in the occiput posterior position, (foetal back to maternal back position) in the uterus. Bronwyn highlighted her feelings of the distress she felt as staff attempted to manipulate and turn her child prior to birth. This lack of control she felt was further evidenced when she was unable to control her urge to push in labour, despite not being fully dilated for the birth. Bronwyn's difficult labour appeared to reignite suppressed memories of her CSA.

I had a terrible labour, I thought thank God it's over. But I can't describe it, can't describe it. She [the baby] was back to back so I was in agony. They were trying to turn her. Ended up she was 8lb 2 so you can imagine, mm, and I pushed through my cervix, I really damaged myself, stitches and tears so I was in agony. (Bronwyn)

The trauma of the labour further negatively impacted on her physical and mental health, and her ability to care for her daughter following the birth. Bronwyn referred to this situation as being 'a breakdown'. This poor mental health and inability to bond and attach with her baby was confirmed by the FN who visited shortly after the birth.

[When I visited] it was like she had just froze. She was just like staring... just avoiding eye contact with me... Not looking at her baby... I suppose I

was a wee bit unsure what was happening. It was so sudden. I felt she was experiencing some mental health breakdown, 'cause she was really unresponsive to any conversation we were having. Wasn't communicating back. (Trudi, FN)

Bronwyn's FN related the difficulty she had experienced getting mental health support for her at that time. Her GP surgery would not offer her an appointment, as she had just recently taken her off their practice list due to Bronwyn being verbally abusive to a GP at her last late pregnancy consultation. The Community Mental Health Team were also unable to see her as an emergency. The out-of-hours GP service agreed to see her and antidepressants were prescribed.

As her daughter became older, Bronwyn discussed the recurring thoughts and difficult emotions she continues to have due to her history of CSA. Her daughter was nearing the same age as when Bronwyn was first sexually abused. Bronwyn expressed her constant state of fear for her daughter and her strong desire to protect her.

... When I pressed charges (against her abuser), I was talking through everything, and I was starting to get flashbacks. I was too terrified to go to sleep...every time I shut my eyes it was just constant memories, flashbacks and it got worse and worse and worse... the things that trigger it off. Like, she's [my daughter is] coming up to 2 (years of age) and that happened to me not even, no it was 3 when it came out. She can do the slightest thing, and stuff like that can come back. (Bronwyn)

The FN sensed that Bronwyn would not wish to engage with mental health services to address her mental health issues. In particular, she anticipated that Bronwyn would not be willing to take their advice and guidance to promote her mental health.

.. she only goes out if partner or stepsister is there and she won't get on buses she will only go in taxis, so I think there is a bit of agoraphobia there, and that's impacting on her finances as well, I've referred to the CMHT [Community Mental Health Team] for a mental health assessment... I don't think she will take the advice of the mental health worker, 'cause they are going to say to get out and about, and go to groups to improve her mental health. I don't think she is going to take that on board. (Trudi, FN)

Bronwyn clearly voiced her fear of engaging with mental health or counselling services in case she again became too mentally unwell, as she had in the post-birth period. It was of concern that Bronwyn was adamant she would not engage with the services offered.

So, if I had to go to counselling and re visit it an aw that, who says I would nae be back to the start or maybe somewhere even worse, and that's just something I'm not willing to put myself or my wean in that position. I'm just not willing to do it, (repeated with greater emphasis) just not willing to do it, at aw. (Bronwyn)

The childhood trauma that the CEP experienced continued to impact on their emotions, behaviours, poor coping strategies and quality of life. For a few the fear of engaging in mental health services in case of a further relapse was raised. The accessibility of appropriate mental health services to meet the CEP needs was also highlighted by professionals.

I think there is a gap for mental health services when you move from child to adult [mental health service]they transfer to an adult system where [they] don't know people, who [they've] not got the relationships with... (Gemma, Child and Family Social Worker]

4.2.2 Relationships and networks

Relationships and networks were identified as the second main theme. Relationships are deemed to be healthy when they are underpinned by honesty, trust, mutual respect and a balance of power (Alexander and Charles, 2009). The building blocks to maintain long-lasting healthy and positive relationships include commitment, co-operation and open communication. With adolescents, positive relationships can impact achievement levels and behaviour adjustment, instilling confidence and motivation (Jose *et al.*, 2012). In contrast, when supportive relationships are absent, unhealthy and negative relationships can prevail. These types of relationships can lead to individuals feeling restricted and unsupported (Goffman, 2009).

Supportive relationships can buffer stress and anxiety (Green *et al.*, 2007; Hancock *et al.*, 2015). Nurturing relationships with others, leads to healing in safe supportive

relationships with others (Herman *et al.*, 1992). Both supportive relationships and effective networks are undeniably linked to health and well-being throughout a lifetime (Bronfenbrenner, 1979; Krug *et al.*, 2002; Meltzer *et al.*, 2016). Protective factors about the well-being of mothers and their babies include individuals believing that they are loved and cared for (McLeod *et al.*, 2006; Kim *et al.*, 2014; Niven and Dow, 2016).

In this study, the young mothers highlighted the important role that relationships and networks played in their everyday life. They repeatedly discussed the relationships they had with their birth family, their partners, and others. There was an essence of desperation and the need for all the young mothers to connect with others in order to feel they belonged and were included. The young mothers clearly expressed their views of their supportive or detrimental relationships and how these had influenced their well-being or that of the baby. They viewed relationships to be supportive when these were felt to help them cope with the tough times, maximise the good times and support them to achieve more than they ever could on their own. In contrast, detrimental relationships were viewed by young mothers as being unsupportive and disempowering to them in many negative ways. These included feelings of isolation, lack of connection to others and deficits in how they coped in everyday life. The lack of dependable others in young people's lives can result in shame and difficulty building future positive relationships and connections (Maxwell *et al.*, 2011; Bermea *et al.*, 2018). The 3 main subthemes of relationships with birth family, partner and relationship with others are presented below. They were discussed in relation to the relevant literature and backed up with participant quotes.

4.2.2.1 Relationship with birth family

Maintaining relationships and connections with birth families are important for children and young people removed from their family unit (Scottish Government, 2021c; NICE, 2021). This often relates to the wide and diverse family members, including parents, siblings, stepsiblings, cousins, and a range of other relationships, including former carers (Jones, 2017).

The majority of the young mothers expressed their hope that their baby would bring them closer to their biological families. This expression of hope was related to their strong feeling of expectation and the desire to be re-connected with their own families. They repeatedly highlighted their feelings of not fitting in or connecting with others.

This was due to the relationships they had encountered with different foster carers and the transient relationships with the many adults who frequently came into and left their lives. It was evident their feelings of vulnerability during the pre and post-birth period fuelled their (and often their partner's) longing to be re-connected and valued by their biological family.

Rebecca voiced the desire for her mother to be the first person with whom she wished to share her pregnancy news, and how she anxiously waited for a response for several weeks. Despite her mother finally responding angrily to the news of the pregnancy many weeks later, Rebecca remained hopeful that her daughter's birth had succeeded in uniting them as a family.

... me and my mum have got really close now, since I've had her. I see my mum every week or every 2 weeks, I see my mum. It is after everything I went through, hardly seeing her an aw that, to now be able to see her. It's amazing. I've never felt so close to my mum, ever. Since having Aileen it's changed everything. ... This [Rebecca's home] is where mum comes tae. Either that or we go into [neighbouring town]. (Rebecca)

This hope of connecting with her birth family did not extend to Rebecca's father. Rebecca continued to fear her father's threatening behaviour toward her and her mother. She was concerned that her father could still interfere in their newly re-established relationship.

... [my dad during pregnancy] was threatening me, [telling me] to kill myself, and if I didn't, he was going tae kill me. I never wanted to be with my dad. I just wanted a relationship back wi' my mum. It was social work that said why don't you call the police and that, so, I had support from social work through all that. He knows, [my Mum visits] but he doesn't stop her. He tried tae a few times, but my mum stood up to him and said, 'it's my life I'll do what I want'. (Rebecca)

Relationships with birth families were often described as being fragile and inconsistent by both young mothers and professionals. These relationships were tentative and often lacked emotional support with practical support unavailable to the young mother. Rebecca's FN spoke of her perception of the young mother as having a transient and volatile relationship with her mother. This was partly due to Rebecca's mother

remaining in a relationship with her father, and the continued risks her father posed to her and also to her young child. The FN described Rebecca as appearing to have a 'negative tie' with her father and still fantasised about her mum and dad being supportive grandparents.

...I just feel it is fragile and the relationship dynamics change all the time. So, I will go in and say, "so what about your mum?" "I've not spoken to my mum, I'm; I'm not speaking to her again." I think she would have loved to have had a mother/ daughter relationship... I just don't think that is possible due to all the allegations against the dad... So, I would imagine there's deep resentment there. She was talking about the baby seeing her [Rebecca's] dad... the social worker said under no circumstances (should she have contact with her father), She [Rebecca] said "yeah that's fine... I just thought we should... let bygones be bygones". (Carolyn, FN)

Both the FN and Rebeca felt her sister offered some support. On the day of the interview, Rebecca's sister was at home and was looking after the baby in another room. Following the interview and just as the researcher was leaving the house, the sister had an abusive outburst directed toward Rebecca. Her sister swore angrily at Rebecca and undermined her for taking part in the study. The sister threatened Rebecca that both the sister and their mother would disown her if she tried to involve them. Although Rebecca's partner was present during this outburst, he did not come to Rebecca's defence. Rebecca looked profoundly shocked at her sister's unprovoked response to her. It seemed Rebecca found it difficult to put up any safe boundaries in her relationships, for fear of abandonment.

Nadia explained her mum's involvement with her and her daughter, and although Nadia was wary of her mother having unsupervised care of her daughter, she showed empathy for her mum's needs. She appeared to feel a duty that her mother should be involved in her daughter's life but had established safe boundaries for doing so.

I still see my mum quite often... she offers [childcare] but me and my partner prefer, to go down [to her home] ... I will stay at my mum's also instead of just leaving the wean overnight. Me and my partner would go down, stay down for a couple of nights... then my mum's still getting that [contact with her grandchild]. (Nadia)

Nadia's FN talked about the concerns that agencies had had when Nadia and her partner, who had also experienced being in care, made contact with their mothers following the news of the pregnancy. She described Nadia and her partner as lacking any consistent, positive maternal role model when they were children. Whilst Nadia's mother had offered more support to her daughter than had been originally anticipated, her mother's partner, due to a history of criminal behaviour, was deemed a potential risk to the child. Her partner's wish to have a closer relationship with his mother was short-lived.

[The partner's mother] had substance misuse problems and she visited recently and I think the first couple of visits went well... they were hopeful. However, I think she was around for 6 weeks or something... [and then] she was looking for money off them. And but, mm they can see that... you know they've got the insight to see that this is nae going well, and to be protective to their daughter and not exposing her to that. (Pam, FN)

Caryn (Nadia's Mental Health Officer) considered the biggest challenges Nadia experienced were generally relating to her family. The family would have periods of being very active in Nadia's life, and then the relationships would fall away again. Nadia's mother also suffered from poor mental health. Caryn reflected if Nadia ever challenged mum, or said no to her, this would result in lengthy periods of silence and anger. This would result in the re-emergence of Nadia's sense of childhood rejection. Nonetheless, Caryn believed that Nadia's resilience had grown over the years. Caryn considered that Nadia's ability to maintain social connections with supportive adults in her life has supported her to learn to maintain safe boundaries and demonstrate self-compassion.

She's quite resilient and she's now able to say... It's her mum's own mental health that causes these fluctuations in contact, fluctuations in mood. In need. Because mum can be very needy towards her. She wants to move... to be closer to her mum.... But as long as she keeps her boundaries and priorities, it's as good a place [to move to] as any. It's that thing where if mum's good, she's good, but then you can never rely, you can't rely on it that's the thing you can't take it for granted. (Caryn, MHO)

During pregnancy Ashleigh, unlike the other young mothers, expressed no intentions of reconciling with her mum, despite encouragement from her siblings to do so. Her mother continued to struggle with addiction issues. Ashleigh's FN carefully considered her decision to not have contact with her birth mother and regarded this as a positive choice for her and her family.

She was very young [when she was] removed from her mum... her (older sibling) recently met up with her biological mum, and they were keen for her and her [younger sibling] to all meet up as well [to] all be re-united... Em, however, Ashleigh... did not feel that would be a good choice for her at this time, she felt too much had happened, and too much trauma in her childhood... Her [youngest sibling] is really struggling... tries to get money off her and has been quite manipulative and Ashleigh has had to limit that relationship too, which has been sad for her. But then... she feels that's what she's had to do, to protect her baby. (Marion, FN)

The FN spoke of how Linda had also hoped for an improved relationship with her mother when her child was born. Linda, despite having continued connections through her relationship with other family members, became more confident in her ability to parent. She recognised the deficits in her mother's parenting and ensured any contact she did have with her mother was very much on her terms.

... her mum came to her dad's [home] to see the baby. And ah said how did that go? She said 'I'm just wary of ma mum, ma mum doesn't commit to anything. She is quite manipulative'. She was quite tuned in tae her mum not being the best and she really kept her at a distance. (Rose, FN).

Linda was still keen to maintain her relationship with her father and her younger sibling. She viewed them as more of a support than her son's paternal grandparents who lived locally. Linda's FN recognised that Linda was also providing mutual support to her father and younger sibling. Her FN raised some concern about the potential risks and additional stressors that her father could have brought to Linda's home.

He actually stayed with her for about a month... there had been issues in his house wi' a guy, who her dad had got involved with... [her father and brother] felt unsafe. I was a wee bit concerned about the overcrowding... She was keen they were seeing him [baby]. Ah think she felt it was useful

at that point to support him [her Dad]. 'Cause she was cooking and she was never a cook... but I think she was proving to him that she was mature and managing things. (Rose, FN)

The FN spoke of Bronwyn's confidence being undermined as a parent in the neonatal period. Bronwyn also discussed the additional stress her mother caused her shortly after the birth of her child, and when her mental health was poor.

Family [step siblings] were taking over the care of the baby... the fact that people came in and took over. It was like she felt invisible. They really undermined her ability as a parent. (Trudi, FN)

... she [Bronwyn's mother] was phoning [social work] to get custody [of her new-born]. So, it was pure... [Laughs gently, shakes head] ... the only contact I had [with my mother] was through the court case, 'cause she was getting done with perverting the course of justice, and molesting me. So that was the only contact we had with her. She's too much a high risk. If she came anywhere near me, she [child] would get took off me... I don't want to have anything to do with her anyway. (Bronwyn)

On leaving care and contacting her biological parents, Emily said her parents encouraged her to have a baby. Emily had seemed keen to re-establish a relationship with her parents and spoke of them being happy when she confirmed her pregnancy. Despite being encouraged to make them grandparents, Emily no longer has contact with her parents and mentioned that she did not speak to them anymore.

Obviously, we met up after Jayden was born. But I don't really speak to my mum and dad anymore. (Emily)

The foster carer spoke of Emily once again being rejected by her family when her baby was only a few months old. She empathised that it was a sad situation for Emily as her parents do not provide her with any support and repeatedly let her down. This ongoing situation with her parents has made Emily more vulnerable.

... she's got parents, but they don't take ownership of her, they don't really participate in her life and offer support or anything... She's not heard from them for a long time... her parents both have a high level of learning needs... they were using her bank details in order to get things...

so it's a shame for Emily... anytime she trusts anyone that's part of her family, they always let her down. She trusts everyone... that makes her very vulnerable. (Fran, Foster Carer)

4.2.2.2 Relationship with partner

The extent that parents engage in positive interactions with each other and share parenting activities have been found to have a positive effect on the quality of their parenting skills and on their child's cognitive and social and emotional development (Carlson *et al.*, 2011; Berger and McLanahan, 2015)

All the young mothers were currently in a relationship, with 4 of them being with the father of their baby. They spoke of their partners as offering support and being committed to the relationships. This was perhaps to offer their children the stability of being raised by both their mother and father/father figure.

One example of a supportive partner was Baird, who Linda declared was her main support. Linda also spoke of him being a good dad to their son 'He's a really good dad, naturally just really good'. Baird appeared to provide Linda with emotional containment by providing companionship and intimacy, with no apparent conflict in their relationship. Linda's FN agreed with this situation. It seemed the partner's stable family environment and his commitment to Linda and their son had helped promote her adaptive functioning following her difficult childhood experiences. Whilst Linda struggled with implementing boundaries with her toddler's misbehaviour, his father found his behaviour easier to manage.

I think he [Linda's partner] has been very stabilising. He comes from a welcoming family. Em, even though he's a quiet guy, he is very consistent in supporting her and genuinely wanting to be with her. You could see he wanted to be with her and have their own wee family. Her and Baird seemed very tuned to each other. His family are quite a motivated wee family. And Baird started a wee job... em, he was putting money in to make sure they had everything. So financially, Baird was there. (Rose, FN)

... she would say look he's [Campbell's] just hyper... he would calm him right doon. His dad was very good with him... he could really contain him and get him to focus. He could tell him no firmly, but still gentle. (Rose, FN)

Nevertheless, the relationships with partners also tended to be complicated and challenged due to a range of issues. These included partners who had also experienced childhood trauma, mental health issues and violent tendencies.

In several relationships, the partners had experienced difficult challenges through trauma in their own childhood and the young couples appeared to be overly dependent on each other. Despite challenges, Nadia praised her partner's strengths, and how they divided childcare and chores within their well-maintained home.

Your daddy cooks [addressing baby], I can cook but he's better at cooking. He cooks, I clean he takes the rubbish out so everything it's a balance. Yeah, everything is split. I get my sleep at night, don't I? (Nadia)

The FN described how Nadia and her partner saw strengths in parenting together, despite acknowledging the adversities and poor role models. In addition, the FN also recognised the couple still faced some challenges, including tensions within the wider family. These tensions had impacted Nadia's partner's emotional well-being.

... the two absolutely dote on this wee girl and really, really stimulate her (learning). They read up on what the next stage of development is, they know what is coming next and what they should be doing next. And mm, aye, they are great parents they absolutely do work really well together... (Pam, FN)

I think there is times when he is struggling with his mental health. And when I try and go there with (Nadia)... she'll go 'oh no he's just had a bad night, the wee one was up'... when you try and explore (emotions) with him he just kind of shuts down. So obviously (his mother's behaviour) it's hurting him and he's not quite ready to go there yet. (Pam, FN)

Mental health complicated the relationships and for a few young men, this was a consequence of their traumatic childhood experiences. For some young women, the mental health of their partners increased their caring responsibilities. Some partners' families offered the young mothers and their children an increased sense of security and belonging. However, for others, it brought conflict and increased stress. There was evidence of some conflicting perspectives about the extent of the support that their partners provided.

The Mental Health Officer shared concerns about how the low mood of Nadia's partner may affect her well-being. His low mood was impacted by social conflict in relationships within his extended family.

... both of them have got that shared history, and they can understand how each other are feeling. I think children and families [social work department] ... are keeping an eye that his mood doesn't dip too far. Eh, his family are probably more fractured and damaged than hers are... and you know (he has) very few memories about his mother... I do think it's a fine line, and a difficult balance if his mood is low how that would affect her... But I think... she is more understanding of the supports that they need. (Caryn, Mental Health Officer)

Some partners displayed violent tendencies and abusive behaviour that impacted relationships. Emily provides an example of living with an abusive partner. She spoke about her fear of telling her partner she was moving out of his family home, due to agencies' concerns about his behaviour and interactions with his child. Both her FN and foster carer raised concerns about the partner who had an offending history of violence in the community and against his 2 previous partners.

But I was too scared to tell his dad, then obviously social work told his Dad... eh... obviously Steven's got previous stuff. He'd been in jail and all that. (Emily)

She [Emily] also told us how she was looking for help [with their baby] from her partner in the middle of the night, or at any time for help that he could also become quite aggressive... He would take himself outside and punch walls and things. He wasn't physically aggressive to her, but he would display this type of behaviour. (Liza, FN)

... I think she [Emily] thinks this is a loving relationship and even though we keep explaining to her how abusive it was, and can still be... it's not a physical aggression, it's an emotional aggression...and I think that is sometimes worse... Initially they (social work) were hoping to get Emily to a stage where she would say 'you know Steven isn't for me and I'm not safe with Steven... but she's saying she wants him in her life. (Fran, Foster Carer)

Rebecca also lived with a partner who was emotionally abusive to her. The housing worker discussed how this emotionally abusive relationship resulted in Rebecca having significant emotional distress and negative thoughts about herself. The FN felt Rebecca's partner offered her and her daughter little emotional or practical support, due to his poor mental health. Perhaps as a result of his insecure attachments, the partner appeared at times to withdraw from the family, often sleeping during the day and playing video games at night, leaving Rebecca to do the majority of childcare. The emotional support given to her partner for his poor mental health appeared to be at the cost of Rebecca's own emotional needs being met.

... it was quite hurtful words that he would use. Em, so she genuinely felt that. She would cut names into her arms... carving 'slut' into her arm and things like that. ...And I spoke to her about trying no tae, em, let the words hurt you. And say to him "the words that you are saying are no helpful" ... I think she does love him, but it's not the best that it could be, she could thrive elsewhere. (Lorraine, Housing worker)

So, one of the reasons they both say is because he suffers from anxiety and low mood, but particularly severe anxiety. Social workers tried to get him to join a dad's group, but he was only in two minutes, and he said, "I need to go, I need to get out of here". (Carolyn, FN)

So, there are days that he can be ok. (But) I think there is a lot they don't tell me about (for)... fear it will be a black mark against them. I know in the past she has wondered about the longevity of the relationship and is it going to last. (Carolyn, FN)

Bronwyn spoke about her 'on and off' relationship over 4 years with her current partner who had to deal with maternal rejection in his childhood. She had become pregnant with her baby during a period of separation from him and the father showed no interest or desire in supporting Bronwyn with parenting. Although Bronwyn and her current partner had other relationships during their separation, they reconciled following the birth of Bronwyn's daughter. This partner has had to deal with maternal rejection himself. The FN recognised the benefits of Bronwyn having another adult to support her care for her child, but she was also reflective of the tensions evident within their relationship. At times, these tensions appeared to be volatile.

... he wanted nothing to do with her. He didn't come to the birth, just that phone call [when she was born] and that was the end... me and him got back together. So, he just took Lucy on as his own. Like nothing's changed, he doesn't look at her as not his or anything, cause like through my pregnancy he was there as well. (Bronwyn)

... there have been periods where they work well together and he is supportive, but there have been times when they've been 'fiery' and that's not the best combination either... there has been one occasion where she was pushed out the road, but more that she was coming at him more than anything. Mm, since then she's not disclosed it... And I think that's when the tension with them started, when he wasn't working and it was becoming too much. He says, 'I need to be working. I need to be out here'. (Trudi, FN)

4.2.2.3 Relationship with others

The journey from adolescence to adulthood and increased independence in society involves young people often moving backwards and forwards between independence from and dependence on their families (Biggart and Walther, 2006). The notion of trust is essential to underpin all types of relationships in order for these to be effective (Rasiah *et al.*, 2020). For the CEP, the crucial aspect of trust and mistrust were even more emphasised when relating to others and to situations outside families and partners. In this context, trust and mistrust were repeatedly highlighted when referring to carers, health professionals and support workers. The presence of trust was fundamental for the CEP in determining whether they felt reassured and confident in their relationships with others. Even when the element of trust did support positive interpersonal relationships, there was a tendency for these to be fragile. Mixed key findings (i.e., positive and negative) emerged from the case studies and focus group.

Care experienced young people do find it difficult to trust others. This poignant comment highlights that the difficulty in trusting others is due to their history of betrayal.

So, until you get to know someone like, you can be not sure of somebody, then once you get to know then it's different... Like, that's why they [care experienced young people] are annoyed because it's going from one [carer, worker or health professional] to another, to another... And there is

situations of like, people's upbringing and things that happen with people and they choose the wrong path. But then there is no one there to help and intercept. (Nadia)

Nadia reflected on the need to learn to trust others and to be open to receiving help. Despite her reduced attendance at school due to her poor mental health Nadia spoke positively of the help and positive relationship she had formed with the school staff. She had initially disclosed abuse to a member of school staff who kept her safe by alerting social services to the abuse and neglect she was experiencing at home.

I loved going to school, the [secondary] school were brilliant with me, it was through them I got put in care, it was them that helped my process with stuff. It was like, the deputy head, mm, I was really close to mm... when I had the wee one, I messaged her on like, social media to say thanks, in like, that how that wee girl she had helped, I still remember it, so I did. She messaged me back and that so helped me. (Nadia)

The majority of the young mothers when they left their residential or foster care placement, felt the opportunity to return was no longer available. Due to their teenage risk-taking behaviours or poor relationships with carers, most of the CEP appeared to consider that 'bridges had been burnt' and there was no means for them to return. Sustainability of what were mainly described as supportive relationships was not evident with foster carers once the CEP reconnected with their family or had greater autonomy.

... the last foster carers she was with the longest, I think she had the best experience - she [Rebecca] even changed her surname at one point... They were a good support for her... but I think that they were getting too involved wi' things that I think she was wanting her space tae be an adult wi'. (Lorraine, Housing Support Worker)

... She was just always there for me, and then when she passed away and I went to the funeral, and I was still in care. It was really hard. But till this day she was someone who made such a big impact on my life... She... was more like straight to the point talk to you. But she was supportive if that makes sense, she was like, she wasn't one of they ones who would try like, to coddle you too much, but not be supportive. She would do everything she can to support you and there would be times...

was a bad self-harmer back then, there would be times she would be in her bed sleeping and she would decide to come to the hospital, and she would come and have a big chat, what was the actual going on? It was someone that I could talk to, mm for definite. So... it definitely wasn't the fact it was just a job - you could tell she had the caring aspect for the kids in the homes. (Nadia)

Only one young mother had the opportunity to reside at a supported mother and child foster carer and she spoke positively of the carer and other resident care experienced mothers residing there.

It was emotional at first [moving into supported foster care with her baby]. But then another girl helped me (peer) settle in here so that was good. (Emily)

... she [Emily] was crying and all that. And then she settled in... What really helped was she said there was other girls in the house at the time [and Stephanie's not long moved out], they kept giving her [Emily] cuddles. (Fran, Foster Carer)

Young mothers reported mixed responses to relationships with health professionals (i.e., MW, NHS 24 and G.P). It was difficult to reach a consensus as the key influencing factors were determined by expectations, previous history and how all relevant individuals felt engaged with the relationship. At times, the relationships became complex and complicated due to intertwining factors and distorted perceptions which disrupted and blurred the boundaries of effective interpersonal relationships.

The key elements impacting the relationships included being judged, criticised, made to feel inadequate and guilty, the levels of empathy and support, and the feeling of being included. Negative aspects present were detrimental to effective relationships with health professionals. In contrast, positive connections made through empathy, mutual understanding and support contributed to more therapeutic relationships.

A positive example relates to Rebecca, who had been experiencing various relationship difficulties with her family that were impacting on her emotional well-being.

[The Family Nurse] just sat and listened and listened and listened. And it was quite good. I'd rather have someone to listen at that time when I needed it most. (Rebecca)

Linda spoke of her reasons for deciding to engage with the Family Nurse Partnership

... ..basically, my way of thinking was, if I've got a Family Nurse then social work will probably leave me alone. 'Cause I can't stand my social worker, so I was like right let's dae it. They [Family Nurse] didn't try and wind ye up. And like social work just tell you, you can dae this, and ye can't dae this, and I was like naw. I will make my own mind up. We [Family Nurse and I] never disagreed on anything big... (Linda)

Linda also spoke about her worry about being perceived as a bad parent when she tried to get support for her child's accidental head injury.

That was always in the back of my mind. The fear of what somebody else might say. What might be reported? (Linda)

... he had a huge mark on his forehead... She (partner's mother) had [phoned Out-of-Hours Service] and tried to get there, but did nae have a car... She said '(out of hours) phoned up and thought I was neglecting him, not taking him to out-of-hours when he had an injury to his head'... And she felt really bad about that, she kept saying 'Should I have done something different. What else could I have done?' I said, 'you could nae hae done anything different'. (Rose, FN)

Half of the young parents were reluctant to be involved with 'throughcare and after care social work' support. Those young mothers who did engage tended to be positive about the relationship with social work. Ashleigh is one example who became more optimistic about her future following the daily contact with her social worker in order to help her manage her stressors. Others such as Linda spoke of having strong negative emotions and distrust of social work.

I had a social worker at the time and she was actually quite good. I messaged her every single day, 'cause we got on quite well. Like she was probably the best social worker I ever had... she went off on maternity leave... I actually really thought with that one, my life was getting better, that she would actually support me. (Ashleigh)

... they tried giving me a family support worker and well like, she never phoned me. I met her, once but it was nae planned. I was with my youth rehabilitation worker and she was like, 'oh here's Dawn' and I was like, hiya. Yeah, so that was it. I seen her a couple of weeks back whilst I was shopping and she was like, 'oh by the way I've signed you off' and I was like, 'aw right, good, see you later'. I told her right from the start, I don't want you and I don't need you, Dawn. My social worker also knows I don't want her. If I need her, I'll phone her, but I don't need her so, I won't keep in contact... (Linda)

Fundamental evidence emerged from social work professionals, including the need to promote positive relationships and provide positive role models to facilitate the young parent's capacity to parent. The professionals were conscious of the essential requirement to use parenting groups to support new parents as one way to minimize negative influences. Numerous related challenges were also highlighted, including difficulties in connecting with parents, the time required to build a trusting relationship, the ambivalence of young parents to connect with them and their busy workloads.

*... if you have that relationship with somebody, texting them saying 'I'm in the area ... do you want to catch up?' they are more than happy to.
(Brian, Child and Family Social Worker)*

... but the reality is if they have kids, it [the Pathway Plan] will be dropped like a hot tawtie [potato]... I don't know if that would work. That we can make them fully functioning adults that can live a life without supports. I don't think we would be focussing as much on that. They might have their [pathway] meetings, but the view for me as a social worker - I know you are working in throughcare [addressing colleague Gordon] but my eye would just be on the kids. You have your reviews, your pathway reviews which is a monitoring job, but as for their planning, planning for them to be independent people out with a children's unit, I probably think as a worker it would be very limited. It would just be parenting work, parenting work, parenting work. You would, with all the will in the world, you would try to work the 2 systems, but I definitely think if we have a previously looked after young person and their 16 or 17 and they are pregnant, you have to be involved if there is that risk of level of concern. (Christy, Child and Family Social Worker)

... they [social workers] are just not given the opportunity [to build relationships] because local workers who have child protection cases and all sorts of things - duty – just don't have the time and space to do it.

(Gordon, Throughcare and After Care Worker)

The behaviours of the young parents and their negative attitudes towards Child Protection issues are well recognised (Healy *et al.*, 2011). In the case studies, evidence of these behaviours is evident. The CEP withdrawal from the relationship with the child and family social worker is complex. This withdrawal may be due to testing the workers' commitment, the nature of the relationship or their sensitivity to perceived rejection or loss. The CEP also struggled to contain their strong emotions which may be more related to attachment issues.

There is a lot of kick back, you get this kind of kick back when they push away from you sometimes, and you get this kind of behaviour and this type of behaviour might escalate. I always think this is because they want you to wrap round and contain them a wee bit more. Unfortunately, we cannae always give them ultimately what they are seeking, 'cause they have left the unit (children's home) There is a kind of level of kids aged about 16, and their behaviours are quite bizarre, but I think it's attachment behaviour seeking they are displaying. (Christy, Child and Family Social Worker)

Instead of being regarded as supportive, the child and family social workers involved with the CEP's children, were viewed by many young mothers with suspicion and a source of fear, anxiety and mistrust. This became even more evident when multi-agency or child protection meetings were held. This was directly related to the real fear young mothers had of losing the care of their child. This situation of referrals by health services was more likely to occur with CEP parents than with their non-care experienced peers.

... for our looked after young people [who become pregnant] we will often get referrals in from other areas. And the basis of other agencies notification of concern, is just that the young person has been looked after [care experienced]. Many times, we will get referrals for that, so there is a push from other agencies, typically health, that is a concern, and the bigger picture isn't necessarily understood by different agencies. We are

doing ok at battling them away and explaining to people an' that but if there is a push.... (Christy, Child and Family Social Worker)

Well through my pregnancy they [social work] didn't find out till the end... I think I was 8 months pregnant at that time. And I felt I was going to lose her with how much pressure I was put under... I didn't tell her [social worker] anything 'cause I felt if I told her anything she was like against me at meetings or like anything to do with [baby] I felt she would use that to try and get her off o' us... (Ashleigh)

Ashleigh's situation provides an example of the changing dynamics which highlight different perspectives and viewpoints. As Ashleigh had moved with her partner from another area in Scotland several months before, her social worker had changed and her new social worker was in touch mainly by phone at Ashleigh's request. At every Social Work meeting attended, Ashleigh felt her past was raised relating to her mum's lack of capacity to care for her in childhood. This was viewed by Ashleigh as the only reason for her current child protection investigation. In Ashleigh's opinion, it was not due to her failure to engage with antenatal care, but rather the fact she was being judged on her own childhood parenting experience. In contrast, the FN provided a different perspective and advised that the child protection investigation was an excellent example of joint working to prioritise the needs of Ashleigh's baby.

... they [social work] were very gentle and kind, and they said how they wanted them to come on voluntarily with the plans they had. I felt it was a good visit. And they explained very well what it was they wanted to happen. (Marion, FN)

Basically, they brought up [at the child protection meeting] about my real mum. My birth mum. They always bring that up no matter what meeting it is. They always bring it up. And I just had a break down at the meeting. I had to walk out. I've not seen my mum since I was a baby. No, the only reason I was there was because of her. We actually had to fight social work to keep her. It was a horrible meeting. Cause it felt like the whole way through the meeting as soon as the baby's born... that's it she's off you... that's the way it came across. I've actually recently just dropped social work because I felt like it was just too much pressure. They were watching everything you do. Even after the CP (child protection)

registration was finished. I just wanted to cut them out... it was just too stressful. (Ashleigh).

... they (Ashleigh and her partner) weren't seen to be putting their baby's needs first. So that Social Worker discussed their remit as well... It was really difficult for (them). The baby was placed on the register, em, pre-birth very quickly after the 1st meeting... And it was felt... ... there were too many unknowns and potential risks to not do that. They (Ashleigh and her partner) were quite distressed about that; however, we said if the plan was adhered to it would hopefully be a short period of registration which is what it turned out to be... It was a great example of joint working, everyone did really well in it. (Marion, FN)

In many cases, the CEP spoke of the challenges of various caregivers and changes in social work staff, which negatively influenced their ability to trust adults. One example relates to Linda who was vocal about her distrust of her social worker and how he had failed to recognise the strengths she had. She perceived that he deliberately tried to provoke her to elicit an angry response and he retained his preconceived ideas about her even when motherhood had changed her. This mistrust and withdrawal from social work services was confirmed by her FN.

I just hate social work to be honest. I despise them. My old social worker when I eh, like, I was just pregnant... was [saying] "eh, we need to do this parenting test" and I was like, "whatever, just do what you want" ... Then I was like "do you need to do it?" And he said, "it's not about if you fall, it's about when you fall and we need to be there to catch the little baby". And I was like "ok, hmm". I don't have him as a social worker anymore anyway. [Laughs]. He was a weirdo... used to say stuff to me to try and wind me up and then as soon as everyone else was there, pretend to be really nice... I used to kick off a lot at my social workers when they didn't give me what I want, and I think he was trying to make me do it. And I was like I'm no the same person. (Linda)

... she changed over to a female [social worker] and even then, she said I don't need anybody or want anybody in my life... She felt judged as though they [social work] were waiting for her to fall apart in the first year and through pregnancy. The fear of the child being removed. (Rose, FN)

Social workers also spoke of trying to build or maintain a relationship with some young mothers who are distrustful. Whenever parents are hostile and unwilling to engage with their support, it is difficult to conduct accurate and robust parenting capacity assessments.

But you have other kids that go in [to care] and they just have this institutionalised behaviour. They are just trying to recreate that, with every person that they meet. So, when you are trying to do pre-birth and they have been (care experienced), straight away they might rebel against that level of monitoring and the authority that comes along with these assessments. So, you will have these really negative looking assessments but, a lot of time it's their [care experienced] behaviours you are describing, not their parenting behaviours you are getting to look at.

(Christy, Child and Family SW)

Several young mothers reflected on being involved in the child protection care system. Profound feelings they expressed concerned mistrust, feeling judged and guilty and fear of losing their baby into care. Attending social work meetings was a stressful situation for the young mothers. Moreover, feelings were exacerbated when this involved concerns such as intimate partner violence and young mothers' need to make lifestyle choices to keep their baby.

... There was so many. There were too many people sitting round a table. Just me [and new born baby] and everybody else... Like, I felt everyone was sitting watching me to make sure I'm doing everything right. Just a constant feeling of being judged. And everyone was quite positive. Knowing that I wouldn't have got her took away. It was the best feeling ever. Knowing I was going to keep her. (It was an) extremely big (fear) cause that's all I was worrying about during labour and aw that. That was one of my main issues that I was facing. Getting her took off me. Knowing what I've come through [in my own childhood] it made it worse for me. (Rebecca)

They (social work) gave me two options, either Jayden getting took off me or me coming through here. [This related to living with a violent partner who was rough in handling the baby] So obviously, I took coming through here. (Emily)

The CEP reflected little support from their birth family and in many of the cases their family continued to display abusive behaviours towards them. Each of the CEP spoke positively of their partner and the support they provided. Some of the CEP and the FNs praised their partner's parenting abilities. However, in several of the cases there was concerns about IPV and the partner's mental health. Whilst there were positive reports of supports from professionals, relationships and engagement with some services were impacted by their own childhood experiences, their concerns of being judged and the fear of being deemed an 'unfit mother'.

4.2.3 *Transitions: Life events*

Transitions can be positive or negative and involve a change or adjustment that impacts an individual's life in a significant way. These transitions are often challenging and occur at a time when a beginning, turning point and ending of a previous way of life are identified (Almeida and Wong, 2009). Transitions may lead to changes in individuals' internal states, resulting in some degree of stress (i.e., eustress or distress). Eustress relates to positive feelings produced that are usually manageable and lead to growth such as satisfaction, excitement, fulfilment and well-being (Branson *et al.*, 2019). In contrast, distress relates to negative feelings which are more difficult and can sometimes lead to feelings which are unmanageable (Branson *et al.*, 2019). From the perspective of stress, these transitions also require individuals to make adaptations that may deplete psychological and physical resources (Almeida and Wong, 2009). Life changes require a particular level of resilience and coping skills to help the individual manage the transition process (Newman and Blackburn, 2002; Almeida and Wong, 2009; Schofield *et al.*, 2017).

Undoubtedly, the CEP experienced several life transitions through events that profoundly impacted their young lives, resulting in subsequent change and adjustment. These events occurred over a short period and were focused on pregnancy and issues relating to becoming new mothers.

4.2.3.1 *Pregnancy*

Deave *et al.* (2008) described pregnancy as a significant developmental period with implications for parents, for the child-mother relationship and the infant's development.

Research has demonstrated that it can be a stressful and profound life event (Couson-Read, 2013)

All young mothers stated that they knew how to access contraception and that they had a good understanding of how to use contraceptive methods. It became evident during the interviews that most of the CEP had inadequate knowledge about contraception and indeed a few others actually thought they were not capable of conceiving babies. Across all the cases criticism of sexual health and relationship education (SRE) within the schools or within care settings were described. Some had poor access to SRE due to frequent placement moves, exclusion from school or limited involvement with education due to their poor mental health. Others found SRE to be embarrassing and declared they already knew the information anyway. A few reported SRE to be insensitive and distressing. They found it tended to reaffirm their feelings of isolation and of being different. Moreover, it reignited traumatic memories of sexual abuse.

... the homes don't tend to want tae go too much into everything with you (SRE) unless you were asking. Then they would tend to be like, "oh we will get someone out" like, a sexual health person. ...instead of them saying something they know nothing about, they are not trained, they would [arrange to] get someone special to visit that you can talk to about it. (Nadia)

Honestly, I didn't really listen. We just carried on in that class... Ah knew most of it anyway so, my pals and that just carried on. (Bronwyn)

It basically just told you like, a healthy relationship is basically, kinda the relationship you have with yer maw and da - cos of what I went through. I never exactly had it [looks tearful]. (Rebecca)

... Because something actually happened to me when I was 15, so going through that [SRE]... It was awful. I couldn't sit through the class, I had to walk out. Once the teacher saw I was upset and stuff like that, she said to 'clear your head and come back [to class] when you're ready'. (Ashleigh)

Pregnancy diagnosis for most of the CEP was not confirmed until the second trimester of pregnancy. The majority of the CEP described themselves to be in a state of shock or disbelief that a pregnancy could happen.

It was a shock because I was actually 3 months pregnant when I found out... I was nae really expecting to obviously fall pregnant. It was a shock. I did nae think I would have fell pregnant very early on, we were only 8 months into our relationship... But, hey-ho, it happens. (Emily)

It was scary. Cause it wasn't something I thought would have happened. Obviously because, I was battling my eating disorder. So that's what really scared me. Cause I wasn't having any periods or nothing because of how skinny I was, so I thought it was something that would never happen. I was like, I cannae be, cannae be, cannae be. (Rebecca)

I was getting tested to see if I could even fall pregnant. It was a week before getting tested and I found out that week... I was sexually abused at the age of 3. So, was my torso and that, was badly damaged... that's when I found out I was pregnant and that was about the time I just found out all this had happened [the sexual abuse]. It was a bad time. Mm, mixed emotions really. Like, I didn't want her, but I don't know. Just shocked, it was just shocked because of everything that had been going on, kinda thing. (Bronwyn)

I was over the moon. We had been trying for over a year. I just wanted to have my baby young. This may sound stupid right, but just because when you are younger you can do so much with them whereas, I thought if I was older, I wouldn't be able to do so much with them. So that's why I always wanted to have baby young. (Ashleigh)

A small number of young women struggled with deciding whether or not to continue with the pregnancy. This dilemma was endured until late in pregnancy. Often the key influencing factor in the decision-making process tended to be related to the baby's father not having a significant role in their life. Mixed feelings about being pregnant were associated with fluctuating mental health issues. Bronwyn willingly shared her feelings, relationship and lifestyle behaviours which were experienced and contemplated during this period. She contemplated these influencing factors to finally decide to continue with her pregnancy.

I didn't want it [the pregnancy]. I wanted an abortion. I've been with my partner-like, we've been on and off fur 4 1/2 years but, at this point we had fell out, I was just doing my own thing, so it was somebody I was

seeing for about 3 months or something. Like, I didn't want her [baby] but I don't know. Just shocked, it was just shocked because of everything that had been going on, kinda thing. I came off straight away [the cocaine]. It changed my mood as well, changed everything. Didn't it? [addressing her child]. And then I got to 20 odd weeks [gestation] and then I was like, "naw I'm pure getting an abortion". But I was at the cut off, I was at the cut-off date, so I needed to go in that morning or go out the country to get it done. So ... [Family Nurse] and that booked it in. An' I dunno, I just couldn't go through with it. Like everything was all booked but, I just couldn't. (Bronwyn)

I think it just depended on her mood and how stable she was at that point. Because if she had a ding-dong with her boyfriend she would be negative about it, em, but if she was doing well with things and she was motivated then she was excited for it. Em, I think potentially the closer she got to the baby being born I think it was mixed [emotions]... I think she was distressed as she could see it growing over time because she spoke to me and other staff that had babies. I think the more she heard from other people the more she accepted it. (Lorraine, Rebecca's Housing Officer)

Family members' negative and positive comments, advice and personal experiences about pregnancy and parenthood were also considered in the CEP decision making. Negative issues in favour of terminating the pregnancy included parents highlighting their initial disapproval and the potential challenges faced as a young mother. The positive issues in favour of continuing with the pregnancy included the delight expressed by birth parents at becoming grandparents and the expectation that the new baby would bring families together.

I was like, oh my God how am I gonnae tell ma dad [said with great feeling]. Ma dad told me to get rid of it. But he was just angry. He said I couldn't look after a hamster when I last lived with him, never mind a baby. (Linda)

Well, my mum and dad (previously) said to me... like my dad had a laugh with me and he said, "hurry up and make me a grandpa": I was like, thinking to myself, "is he being serious or is he having a laugh?" And I was like that ... obviously, I said to my mum, tell dad he's had his

dream. She said, 'what dream, don't say your pregnant are you?' And I was like "yes, whoopsie..." They were happy.... (Emily)

4.2.3.2 Parenthood

Parenthood involves a major developmental transition with many challenges (Harwood *et al.*, 2007; Samuel *et al.*, 2007; Almeida and Wong, 2009). Many first-time mothers are positive about the birth of their baby and have optimistic expectations that their life will change for the better (Harwood *et al.*, 2007; Hoffenaar *et al.*, 2010, Levesque and Fernet, 2020). However, this is not always the case as becoming a parent can lead to significant stress and can drain new parent's internal resources (Levesque *et al.*, 2020). Evidence is provided in a selection of direct quotes.

4.2.3.3 Becoming a mum

In this study, becoming a mother was associated with an increased sense of fulfilment and pleasure in the lives of most of the CEP. Their joy and love when speaking about their children were palpable. This was evident in interviews when they became animated when talking about them. The CEP willingly shared videos and spoke proudly of their children's accomplishments. When Rebecca had her baby, after (previously) struggling with mental health issues, she described the feeling of being rescued and of being given a new meaning to her life.

...everything I used tae dae, I don't dae any mair. Because she's [her baby] changed everything, but for the better. So, I'm so thankful for her because I was always in a dark place where I was self-harming and everything and since having her never wance. She saved everything. She made everything better. (Rebecca)

Ashleigh expressed her immediate bond with her child and expressed her relief that her child remained in her care.

I just wanted to be with her. I was just in love. [Laughs]. Straightaway. I just enjoy everything... I honestly feel so lucky that I still have her, especially the way social work were at first. (Ashleigh)

Conversely, Bronwyn mental health deteriorated following her daughter's birth. Bronwyn reflected on her relational issues with her daughter and how she did not feel

love for her when she was born. Bronwyn's FN corroborated this deterioration in mental health and voiced concerns over her attachment with her daughter. The FN linked this detachment disorder with young mothers such as Bronwyn, to the fact they tended to dwell on and revisit their own childhood traumas.

... that's what scares me as well. Because I didn't have that instant love and wanting to protect her. And maybe I did.... maybe so much was going on that I wasn't interested... she just didn't feel like my baby. Obviously, she brought out the worst, but she also made it better. And realised that it's not her fault. She's innocent... Even though nothing like that will ever happen to her, it's that anxiety. 'Cause, I was too scared to touch her, just because I got that fear. There was just that constant fear. And she just didn't feel like my baby, she just didn't feel like my baby... I never had that until... a few months ago where I felt naw, if anything happened to her, I would kill. That instant love never came to me until a few months ago. (Bronwyn)

Social work are still there. I think as she's [Bronwyn's daughter] grown older, I think maybe an attachment disorder we are seeing at the minute. I think mums always preoccupied with her own experience and her own past. The last 3 visits have been about [her talking about] compensation claims due to the assault she had from a man when she was young...It's about lawyers and getting information from the police, and it's very, just very stressful in the house, and she's very stressed. And I think, what we are seeing now in the child, is the stress that she is mirroring, that stress that's she's [Bronwyn] carrying around. She's (child) very bright, she's seeking out information, wanting to go up on my knee. And yet she [Bronwyn] says she doesn't like cuddles. But when I go in, she's definitely wanting cuddles, putting her hands up and cuddles right in... (Trudi, FN)

4.2.3.4 Being a 'good mum'

The CEP described the strong desire they had to parent differently from their own parents. At times this desire and motivation to be good mums were related to their own mother failing to provide appropriate parental care for families. The motivation to positively change behaviour to become reliable, protective and supportive parents to their baby was corroborated by the health professionals and carers.

I became really excited about (being a mother) knowing no matter what I've been through that I can be a better mum, so I got really excited about it. Just [aiming for] being a better mum than my mum was, and I've already achieved that. (Linda)

I think she copes extremely well with the historical relationships [with her mother]. I think she's maturing, and as she is now a mother herself, I think she has now developed an ability to stand up (for herself) because she doesn't want her daughter to grow up in the same environment that she grew up in ... (Nadia's Mental Health Officer)

With Ashleigh's child placed on the Child Protection Register, Ashleigh highlighted the pressure on her to prove to social work she was a good mum. The FN was positive about Ashleigh's willing engagement with the FN programme to help her become a good mum.

We had to prove we were good parents. And we proved them (social work) wrong. I got 6 weeks to prove myself. That's what they said. 'You've got 6 weeks to prove you're a good mum. Mm, and if not then, she is going to be moving in with Craig's mum'. And we proved them wrong. (Ashleigh)

You can see the attachment her baby has with her, and what a really calm loving environment her baby is being brought up in. And Ashleigh is very aware she wants her baby to have a very different childhood to what she's experienced. She was very clear from early on if there was anything that could negatively affect her, she would seek to rectify that. I think the [FNP] programme encouraged her to enhance and reflect back, and use her strengths, 'cause she has never had anyone before to tell her, what she's doing well. (Ashleigh's Family Nurse)

Emily's foster carer spoke of the extent of support she needed when SW brought Emily and her baby to the foster carer's home. Emily had strived to develop her own self-care as well as her parenting skills to ensure her baby remained in her care.

I've seen big changes, I've seen her [Emily] go from very, very low personal hygiene with me having to prompt her ... (and with the baby) ... She has a learning difficulty mmm, very loving but very low self-care for

him too. So, you would be prompting with nappies and bathing and all that. You had to prompt until it was repetition, repetition until she is now in a routine. (Emily's Foster Carer)

Rose, Emily's FN spoke of her client's desire to be a good mother.

(She was) ...keen to prove she could be a good mum. Engaging with (FNP) materials. Desperately wanting to prove she would be there for her child. 'I don't want him to feel let down like I've felt'. ...she was very good about reading his cues, we did a lot of work around that. And she was just there wanting tae be having a wee baby to love. She responded very appropriately to all his needs; she scaffolded his learning. (Rose, FN)

4.2.3.5 Stigma

Teenage motherhood has increasingly been seen as a problematic issue by society and policymakers (Macvarish, 2010). There is an acknowledged stigma around teenage mothers (SmithBattle, 2013; SmithBattle, 2020). Goffman, (2009) defines the term 'stigma' as being the 'situation of the individual who is disqualified from full social acceptance'. For the young mothers in the case studies, they reported feeling stigmatised for several reasons. These included feelings of being stigmatised for living in care, foster care, having mental health issues, having a baby at a young age and not being able to cope. This also extended to the young mothers feeling fearful of being judged by others in their communities and the impact this can have on them or their toddlers when engaging in related activities.

People round about me, made me feel worse.... I was the lowest of the low. I had a lot of people looking down on me as a person and as a new mum. Lots of people from the outside that did nae know what was going on, looking in. It's a small place. They just presumed I didn't want her an' that. It was hard, it wasn't like that at all. (Bronwyn)

I thought them going to the toddlers would help, [with helping her play and set boundaries with her toddler] but she said, no. He was just running amok and she felt judged by his behaviours as a teenage mum... [another time] ... it was snowing, and ah said 'come on let's get him wrapped up and take him out to play in the snow', which we did. And again, she was saying she would have been too worried tae have done that, as she would

have been anxious about what the neighbours would think about having him playing out in the cold. (Linda's Family Nurse)

Well, after having the miscarriage.... she spoke about feeling judged at the hospital by a member of staff and feeling judged for being a young mum in society, in general. She definitely felt the stigma, which not all of them describe. I mean she looks young, but she is 18. (Ashleigh's Family Nurse)

Nadia explained how important it was for CEP not to feel stigmatised. This would ensure the young mothers would not be prevented from engaging with the very services available to help them. Nadia explained that trust and the fear of being judged as an unfit parent were significant barriers which discouraged young people from engaging with services.

I think it's just like a lot of people who have been in care, they are like, they don't want to be open and honest. An' that's kind of what I'd say is the issue for a lot of people in care. 'Cause, if they don't trust somebody, they are worried [that] they are going to judge me, they are going to think I'm not going to be a good parent. (Nadia)

4.2.3.6 Parenting

Research has identified that a lack of positive parenting role models for CEP means the CEP often need scaffolding to learn how to successfully parent their child (Aparicio *et al.*, 2015).

Managing the behaviour of their children was raised as an issue by the young mothers. This was supported by the FNs who also found it challenging to work with the young mothers. This challenge was in respect of helping young mothers to understand the important elements involved in raising a child.

Bronwyn was one example who spoke of the difficulty in setting safe boundaries and setting limits to manage her toddler's behaviour. The FN expressed her concern that the behaviour of her daughter was due to Bronwyn's poor mental health. She also raised her growing concerns about Bronwyn's capacity to parent her daughter, her inability to focus on her child's emotional needs and the fact that she was too quick to label her daughter.

I've spoiled her. So, every time I'm saying no, now it's just, it's a screaming match. She's too used to getting everything she wants and that's my fault... my partner, we've been fighting over it and he's the strict one and I usually give in. So, we've been arguing too. She's got, like her temper on her, is really, really bad, like for her age. It's really bad. She's cut [FN] and everything... She gets angry. If she doesn't get what she wants she gets angry very, very quick. (Bronwyn)

And I think what we are seeing now in the child is the stress that she is mirroring that stress that's she's [Bronwyn is] carrying around. Her stepsister states her (child's) behaviour is really terrible, she thinks she has autism... (Trudi, FN)

Another FN whilst acknowledging some of the CEP strengths, felt that the young mother was overcompensating, due to the deficiencies she experienced in her own upbringing.

... she [Linda] was great reading books with him. She was great with that, but when it came to the toys... she tried to prove... they were buying everything at birthdays and Christmases. He [her son] got the best of everything. He was a wee boy who was quite overwhelmed with all the stuff he got... That was quite a challenge. I would try to encourage her to have just a few toys in the living room at the one time, and maybe a book... But I think she felt she had to prove that she could buy everything for her kid and he had mair stuff than other kids ever get. (Rose, FN)

All young mothers were engaged in the Family Nurse Partnership Programme to help promote their parenting capacity. There was a general consensus on the benefits of this evidence based programme to offer knowledge, skills and a range of services for young mothers and their children to scaffold and support their care. The issue relating to parent support was repeatedly raised across the case studies. Whilst each young mother was clear about not wanting to be a parent like their own parents, this left them seeking guidance as to what they should do to make them good parents. Nadia provides an example of her engagement with her FN.

...we would have conversations about each thing, like so, it's like so they have the sheets [Family Nurse Partnership facilitators] and we would go through different things like, in this situation what would this do? And it

was something, somebody that can be reassuring for you when you are a first time parent. (Nadia)

The benefits of attending parenting groups for young parents were highlighted and explained by many professionals and care workers. There was a range of benefits of attending parenting groups involving their peers. This approach enabled young parents to share their experiences of motherhood with peers in similar situations, which had a positive effect on the well-being of young parents. The groups provided opportunities for young parents to learn and improve their parenting skills together and to reduce social isolation. Rebecca is one example who appreciated the support from other young mothers attending the groups. She spoke of the importance of reaching out to others for support and how it made her feel less alone. Unfortunately, frustrations were also reported by others when there was difficulty in accessing parenting support.

... to try and actually have a relationship with someone, someone that will actually listen to ye. It's just the best thing. And to go to groups. [Laughs].

To go to anything that will support you. That's what I missed out in. 'Cause I didn't go to any groups or antenatal groups or that. Because I'm no someone that goes places by ma self. Yeah, ... when I went to a young mum's group, and like seeing all the other kids and knowing you are not the only young person, the only one with a child, it's relaxing knowing, because obviously, you can put the weans down to sleep and aw that, and you can speak to the other mums about their experiences and know it's worth it. (Rebecca)

Well, they [parenting groups] have all been cancelled lately because of staff shortages again. So locally, we are really struggling for groups. But overall, when they were running but if it's pre-birth, obviously it's child protection so, the young mums and dads kinda feel they have to engage as part of the plan. Most people who engage do well, they do enjoy it but it's getting that continuity of the parenting groups being delivered. (Amy, Child and Family Social Worker)

Moreover, the role of the young fathers was raised on numerous occasions across the case studies and the focus group. There was consensus around the positive role the young fathers had to play and how they should be supported in their transition into

fatherhood. Wider discussions took place highlighting the specific needs of young fathers attending parenting groups and the limited availability of resources for parents. It was agreed that more parenting support and resources were required to meet the specific needs of young partners in promoting their parenting skills.

I think it's daunting as a young care experienced person to go along [to Dad's group]. I used to run the fathers' group in the (social work) centre and you would have a 19-year-old, 20-year-old young fathers who were sitting with fathers in their late 20s, 30s and 40 year olds who had a lot of life experience. It's pretty hard to feel as if you fit in. I think they are very nervous about coming along. And sometimes their group experience is another type of group experience altogether, because they have been sitting with 14-year-old teenagers in a group. And now they are being asked to come along, the young males are being asked to come along with very little knowledge of what to expect about being a new parent.

(Gordon, Social Worker Throughcare and After Care)

One of the Social Workers described the difficulties of supporting care experienced young fathers to attend antenatal appointments.

When we have young guys, you can't prioritise the same things for the guys. The girl it would be prioritised, and you would have that health legislation to push that to be supported, but I think if he is a young guy and they were wanting to be fully involved in the pregnancy or going to sit with the young woman if she was pregnant at clinics, I don't think that would be prioritised. (Christy, Child and Family Social Worker)

Emily was keen her partner was supported in his parenting skills to increase his involvement with their young child.

... I was used to changing nappies and that, 'cause I brought my two wee brothers up so... But [partner] doesn't have any experience, so it was quite hard for him. (Emily)

Furthermore, there was some discussion around the benefits of early-year education provision to promote the child's social and emotional development. There was agreement that this provision should be available to all toddlers. The FN and social workers recognised that Bronwyn's daughter would benefit from early nursery

placement as it would be ideal for her development. This placement would offer Bronwyn some respite and, moreover, it would provide the opportunity for 'another pair of eyes on her child' to see how the daughter functioned when Bronwyn was not present.

The benefits of the Family Nurse Partnership (FNP) programme were highlighted by the CEP and also within the focus group. The collaborative working relationships were also revealed. One FN provided an example of how well her client, Nadia, was managing and progressing by being on the FNP programme. The FN reported that Nadia showed a great deal of strength and her mental health state was now stable, which enabled the mental health officer to discharge her recently. Indeed, Nadia was also considered to no longer require any further support from Child and Family Social Work. As she was soon to be the only worker left working with the family, the FN was concerned about Nadia's future when she graduated away from the FNP programme. Nadia confirmed the benefits and support she and her partner had received from their FN. Social Work staff in the focus group also acknowledged the positive relationships established between the FNP programme and the young parents.

I think if you could keep the [care experience] families on a more longer-term basis... And I can see that they would benefit from a continuation of the [FNP] programme. I think that [extended support] would be good for her and her family. They would have that consistent person that I've been talking about, [that she and her partner] could be doing with... In a year's time [she] will be handed over [to the Health Visitor]. It's a very different service... they have much higher numbers than we have. And the person she can text, who will always text her back that day, or she can phone, and I will make an arrangement to see her later that week. Whatever, she will no have the same flexibility. Mm an' things are great this now, they absolutely are, however, if things break down with her mum. If maybe the relationship breaks down... I don't know how she would be without someone to support her as time goes on. (Nadia's FN)

However, one gap that was highlighted referred to other CEP over 20 years of age, in similar circumstances, but due to their age were not eligible for the FNP programme.

You have got the Family Nurse Partnership as well, who are really good with the young people. But then, their cut off [in this health board area] is 20 years old, which I find, a lot of the [older care experienced parents] ... that we work with are dead immature as well, so they could be doing with that kind of support. So that, that's another barrier. (Amy, Child and Family Social Worker)

4.2.3.7 Rapid repeat pregnancy

The reproductive history of young mothers was varied. Pregnancy loss and related distress and planning for pregnancy or repeat pregnancies were issues highlighted across the case studies. There seemed to be some reluctance and ambivalence at times for young mothers to express their viewpoints relating to contraception, pregnancy loss and planning. Therefore, it was the health professionals (mental health officers and FNs) who explained the background and situations of the CEP in their care.

... before she [Nadia] was pregnant with this baby, she had a miscarriage very early. I went to the GP with her and he prescribed just a short course of something just to calm the anxieties you know, just to get her over. (Caryn, Mental Health Officer)

I [FN] said to her "are you wanting contraception at the moment?", and she said no. I tried to explore with her if she wanted another baby and she didn't say that, so I asked what would happen if she didn't use contraception and she had another baby, how she would feel about it. And she said she would feel ok about it. Em, but at the same time was saying she wanted to wait a while before she had another baby so there was a bit of contradiction there... she said that Peter would like to go ahead and try for another baby now, but she felt it was too painful. She said she needed a period of time... maybe even a couple of years. [But] she has... not wanted to explore contraception again... So, I wasn't surprised when she told me a few months later that she was pregnant. (Marion, FN)

... he [controlling partner] was trying to talk her into having another baby. And we spoke a lot about, obviously that was her decision, but looking at the bigger picture, what the implications of that might be. Eventually she

actually contacted me one day and said would you take me to a sexual health clinic. She had made the appointment herself for an implant, but she hadn't told him. (Liza, FN)

Linda was an example of a young mother refusing to discuss contraception with her FN saying, 'you know I don't go there'. The FN (Rose), whilst affirming her skills as a mother, encouraged Linda to think of what other skills she could develop. Rose would discreetly leave condoms with Linda every few months following her home visits. It was also difficult for the FN to get Linda to consider long-term plans and any future aspirations, but she did indicate she may have another child.

... and I think she knew she was a good mum. And was so proud of her wee boy. She was thinking maybe that's might next step. 'Cause she was saying to me 'I might have another baby I don't want to wait a long time', So I would say 'right that's fine, you feel more stable obviously, and now you've got choices about what you want to do'. (Rose, FN)

4.2.3.8 Leaving care and setting up home.

All eligible care experienced children should have a Pathway Plan which sets out the support that will be given to the care leaver once they have left care (Scottish Government, 2016b). This plan is based on their Needs Assessment. The Plan should be prepared before the young person leaves care. Moreover, the Pathway Plan should include: the level of contact and support that will be provided by social work as well as how the young person's health needs will be met; it should also consider plans to support the young person in further education or employment. Furthermore, plans to support the young person in maintaining or developing family relationships should be considered. The young person's financial needs and capacity to manage a tenancy should also be assessed to ensure the young person is living in suitable accommodation; and any 'staying put' arrangements enabling them to remain in their current care setting agreed (Scottish Government, 2016b).

In the case studies, health and social work practitioners highlighted the difficulties involved in trying to implement policy into practice for these young mothers. For local authorities, there are challenges concerning legislation (i.e., the Children and Young People's Act, 2014) which supports young people to remain in their care placement until 21 years of age. These difficulties extend to the implications this may have for

children's services to mediate and ensure the risks of homelessness are minimised for individuals leaving care. This challenge of the 'right to continuous placement' becomes even more complicated if the young person leaving care becomes a parent. The corporate responsibility to support teenage parents leaving care to find suitable accommodation caused some frustrations for all concerned.

... [the local authority] have over 20 young people in our children's houses, and the young people [are] able to stay in foster care longer because of the recent 2014 legislation about their right to stay in care and continuing placement. But they haven't built or opened any more places. So, the higher end of older young people, 18 plus, we are still going to have to accommodate (them and there are) other children and young people without the proper establishments. (Gordon, Social Worker Throughcare and After Care)

The challenges of securing supported mother and child foster placements within the local authority areas were also considered.

I've spoken to that foster carer who has always said to me she would like to take in young mums and show them how to love and nurture their babies. It would be amazing if that [mother and child supported carer] service existed. (Gemma, Social Worker)

... ..but a lot of that is up to whether a foster carer is up to having a teenager with a young child in their house as well. I've heard it [happened] once. (Gordon, Social Worker)

... you are talking about young people who are removed from their parent's, right? Moved into looked after and children's home and things. Isn't the onus then on the local authority and staff to parent and prepare these young people? ...and that's just not being done. (Neil, Child and Family Social Worker)

We've got practice flats... [attached to the children's house] and something like that, but it's a risk to the baby if there are any violent aggressive behaviours (in the children's house) you couldn't do that. So, I'm not sure, I think they would be more likely to support them out of the

unit rather than attached to the [children's] house. (Christy, Child and Family Social Worker)

None of the young mothers spoke of experiencing a smooth transition from leaving care. For the individuals, their transition was at times fraught and complicated by a wide range of unforeseen events and situations. These included poor mental health, risk-taking behaviour, unsuitable accommodation, impulsive behaviour, lack of trust and engagement, rigid rules, and frequent changes of placements. There was no doubt that the young mothers were supported by a range of professionals. They did, however, feel that social workers often impacted adversely on their outcomes.

... because I was like, under social work, I had to go by their rules. It had to be like certain people, like I had to go to social work and ask them. And then they had to go round parents and ask them. It was embarrassing. And I felt like, different from any other kid. It wasn't really her [the foster carer's fault] it was like, social work, cause she [the foster carer] didn't have a problem with it 'cause every teenager does it. But it was just the fact that social work were strict on her as well, she couldn't really do anything about it. (Ashleigh)

Despite having positive relationships with foster carers, more than half of the young mothers reported these relationships deteriorated once they sought further independence as a teenager. When they naturally began to establish teenage relationships with their partners and began to self-actualise, this became an issue for foster carers. This seemed to be related to foster carers wanting to maintain appropriate rules and safe boundaries. Young mothers expressed their interest in spending time with their peers, exploring risk-taking behaviour and discovering life while still having a safe base to return to. These inflexible boundaries and restrictions placed on the young mothers' lifestyles and behaviours resulted in deteriorating relationships. Emily was one example of a girl whose pregnancy was the catalyst for leaving foster care due to the deteriorating relationships. The FN reflected on Emily's situation with the foster carers and corroborated that Emily's desire to be with her partner when pregnant was the reason.

... when I fell pregnant, I was in care for 4 years. Aye, it would have been 5 years this year... and then me and her [foster carer] had a fallout and I moved in with my boyfriend. (Emily)

It seemed to be a really good strong [foster carer] placement, she [Emily] had been in it for about 3 years... Mm, but when she met her current partner, she started to kind of stay out more, she started to challenge I suppose the boundaries that were in place in her placement. And mm, there was a lot of confrontation. And she really, the more she became involved with her partner, the less she went back home. (Liza, FN)

Deteriorating relationships with care home staff were also highlighted. One example is Linda who spoke of her sudden decision to leave the children's home when she had just turned 16 years of age. She reported perceiving the care home staff were actually encouraging her to leave, whilst her social worker was persuading Linda to remain in the care home.

... the way it happened with the care home. I just got fed up with them one day, 'cause there was another lassie staying there. She took the remote away and hid it from me and I kicked off, and I remember saying 'you're just a dickhead', and she started crying and saying that I'm bullying her. So, they were like 'right you are grounded, you are not seeing [boyfriend], you're not doing contact this week', and I was just like, watch me sign myself out, there and then. I packed my stuff and left. They were goading me to dae it. Saying, 'Aye, you won't dae it anyway. We've had this threat too many times'. And I was just like right, watch me. Aye that's me, am no feart. The second I sign myself out that was it... they never contacted me again, apart from when I phoned them to say I've left a couple of things behind, can you get somebody to drop it off. Eh, they knew [boyfriend] was a nice boy and that, so I think they knew I would be alright. My social worker was at a meeting when I done it. My social worker tried to take me out tae the shops to calm me down and I was like naw, naw I'm going. She was, 'oh I can give you a lift down... to be with your dad but I'll get in trouble'. And I said no, I'm not going back... I'm staying [with boyfriend's parents] (Linda)

All participants spoke of their experience of homelessness soon after leaving care and acknowledged the support they received. Of the participants, 5 of the 6 young mothers

had experienced multiple care placements in their childhood and had a strong desire to secure a safe permanent tenancy and to set up a home of their own. Four young mothers were already pregnant when they were homeless. Although supported with seeking accommodation, some young women highlighted being fearful of where they would be placed.

On leaving care, some young mothers experienced an unsettling period. This involved adopting adverse behaviours or living in temporary accommodation with relatives or in a homeless unit. Bronwyn had a positive relationship with her foster carers when she left home. However, she is an example of life deteriorating when she became involved in using drugs with poor self-care within one month of living in the homeless unit.

... obviously, I didn't know what happened [when she was sexually abused]. I've blocked it all out, so that just came to the surface when I was reading my file age 16 -17. So, I went off the rails for a good bit. I was just pushing the boundaries, drinking and that. It was just a breakdown in the relationship... .. when I had just left ma foster placement, I went into the homeless unit, I went into the (name of homeless unit), and from there, obviously with everything that was going on, that's when my life just went right downhill. Like, I was abusing drugs... So, I had top designer clothes. Phones, like, I was well-dressed, and I looked after mae self. And I would say, it got to a month of living [there] and I looked dreadful. I looked dreadful. All ma clothes were ruined, I was nae looking after mae self, I was using drugs which I never touched before. (Bronwyn)

Another example was reported by Nadia's mental health officer, as it was too difficult for Nadia (age 17 years) to personally share this during the interview. The mental health officer spoke of how moving to a supported homeless unit had a detrimental effect on Nadia's mental health and her vulnerabilities were exploited by older males.

... What children and families [social workers] did was, before she got this tenancy, they placed her in an adult care home environment, but it had a training flat. And they placed her in a, it was a training flat just on the outskirts of [neighbouring city] and that fell flat very, very quickly... She was readmitted to hospital so, and I think she was too young for the environment they put her into. Because, although it was an adult care

setting, they were a lot older than what she was and they weren't there for the same reasons as she was there. Yeah, she self-harmed quite significantly in that flat. Yeah, at most, it would have been a couple of months... Eh, she was participating in quite risky behaviours, people were coming and picking her up and things like that, so it became quite apparent quite quickly it wasn't the best route to go down with her, eh.

(Caryn, Mental Health Officer)

Challenges relating to inappropriate, overcrowded or short-term housing were highlighted by all young mothers and professionals. Two CEP lived with their partner and child in a small one bedroomed property, but despite the overcrowding they did not wish to move to two bedroomed home in a more deprived area. One major challenge expressed was their fear of being placed in accommodation which added to their difficulties in adjusting to leaving care and raising their families. Many young mothers experienced living in housing where they were subjected to anti-social behaviour or being isolated from supportive adults. The frequency of accommodation changes disrupted the opportunities for young mothers to develop a sense of belonging to a community and a sense of providing stable housing for their families. The CEP shared their desire to have not only a comfortable, physical environment to live in with their child but also to feel safe, to feel they belonged and to have a stable home. The sense of desiring a secure base to meet their family's needs, and the hopes of building a better future for themselves, their partner and their child was tangible.

Despite being offered a tenancy, some CEP continued to have challenges with overcrowding, high deprivation and anti-social neighbours. This has created fears which have impacted the CEP's decisions. One example relates to Ashleigh. Her FN spoke about Ashleigh and her partner's impulsive decision to move from an area where they felt fearful, to a remote rural area that had increased their isolation and reduced her partner's career opportunities.

I think there is still a bit of teenage brain, where they make decisions and it's a bit impulsive... then regret it... the flat they were in wasn't in [a] great area and there was concerns around the neighbours... ... [her current tenancy is] in an isolated rural community and I did have concerns about them being able to access public transport and being able to connect with the community... they are now recognising the isolation. And they want to

now live closer to Peter's family, which was one of the options in the beginning... it's a lovely house [her current tenancy], and no concerns around that... Peter thought he would have a job and be able to get driving lessons and have a car to get around and that hasn't happened yet. And I think, you know when you are that age, you think things will happen sooner than they do, and the reality of it is that it's really hard to get to a job because it is so rural and there is not much public transport.

(Marion, FN)

All young mothers reported struggling with finances on leaving care and setting up home. Some reported the difficulties experienced with managing the limited financial resources provided by social work and housing. The researcher's field notes documented sparse living conditions for three of the CEP. Whilst white goods were routinely provided, other essential items were purchased on a tight budget. Some of the CEP explained the necessity for them to accrue debt or turn to community charities for financial support and food banks, leading to further distress. The difficulties raised by the CEP and the support available were evidenced by professionals and other workers who also highlighted further issues and the potential for the CEP to accrue rent arrears.

... she ended up getting a really nice house... There is one thing which I think is a bit of an issue. So as soon as you get your keys, you're liable for rent on that property. So, if you don't move out on that day you would get arrears on the new property 'cause your housing benefit is still for the [homeless hostel]. So, we would try and get like a dual payment so the housing benefit would pay both. But they only ever done that sometimes.

(Lorraine, Housing worker).

However, on a positive note, a FN also praised the way the teenage parents dealt with the situation.

So financially... he [her partner who worked part-time] was putting money in to make sure they had everything, and his family were there if they were struggling. But to be fair, she has been very good at managing her money. She had all her benefits and things...she had sorted that out herself, she was very proactive. (Rose, FN)

One area of concern raised across the case studies related to the challenges experienced by CEP when claiming benefits. Others were related to the sanctions imposed for a range of situations such as poor mental health, medical-related issues and missed appointments. These 'bureaucratic' matters created anxieties, frustrations as a result of some bad behaviour and association of blame with others.

We have a number of young people leaving who are on the aftercare list who can barely write their names. I think that's a concern, that's not just about their home, they have been in our care for a number of years... And they are struggling with basic forms, but they are expected to complete forms for DWP [Department of Work and Pensions] and evidence that they are looking for work 5 miles away. (Gordon, Social Work Throughcare and After Care Worker)

He [Ashleigh's partner] was messed about a wee bit by the job centre at times which was unfortunate. He was sanctioned the week the baby was born, because it wasn't [considered] a good enough excuse for him not to go to the job centre... And it's so difficult trying to reverse that... So, they were getting less money... But his family helped out. I did refer them to financial support... however... they [Ashleigh and partner] didn't seem to engage with it and I had to help them with claiming all their benefits and that. (Marion, FN)

[Bronwyn] was applying for benefits and she first filled out the form and sent it away, but she hadn't filled it in properly. And at the next visit she deferred all the blame onto myself and she started shouting, standing up and swearing and telling me to get out the house. Mm, I tried to de-escalate that situation. I didn't leave. Luckily, I had another application in my bag, and she calmed down. We filled out the application together and then she was happy for me to post it off, she didn't have a stamp or anything. Then her application was successful and I think she started trusting me again. I think the fact that I did nae leave, 'cause I think, historically this is what she's done with lots of people. I think over time, I can see why she behaves as she does, due to the repeated trauma she has had in her life. (Rose, FN)

4.2.3.9 Plans for the future

Becoming a mother has been evidenced as a motivating factor for female CEP to plan for the future (Haight *et al.*, 2009).

Most young mothers in the case studies were positive in expressing their hopes and ambitions for the future. This was heartening for the health professionals who expressed their optimism for them when the CEP shared their goals and longer-term plans. They viewed these plans to be an achievement, especially when the CEP stated that they wanted to make a better life for themselves and family. This supported the Family Nurse Partnership aims to work with young mothers to optimise their life course potential. This work promoted the CEP to seek advice and guidance for their future aspirations and to build on their strengths through setting realistic goals (short to longer-term). Only 1 CEP expressed she did not have any future career plans, her reluctance being due to her preoccupation about her child being sexually abused if she was not there to protect her. Several planned to go to college and were also hopeful of their partners gaining secure employment to provide a stable family life. Others wanted to focus on being with their children in the first instance, although expressed longer-term plans to continue with their studies.

I plan to [study] health and social care, and then I want to be a paramedic. When I've been thinking about what I want to do, I don't think an office job would be good for me, I would just get bored. It would be something different and I want to help people and stuff. (Linda)

... I was saying what you would like to be if you had stayed on at school and she was saying 'paramedic'. I said that's great, you're very gentle... To make it sound achievable I said "hold onto that goal. Who could we use to help get you there? So that's what we did we contacted... [Skills Development Scotland]. And the woman, as I say, I'm very wary about how young people are spoken to, by other professionals, and I felt this is all hinging, things could really turn here. And she [the Skills Development worker] was excellent, and she reflected every strength and skill [that she saw in Linda as a parent]. And she was great, she went on the computer to look at the different points so she could become a paramedic. So, um, em, that's when I saw the change on the future is, 'I could not just be a mum, I could be something else'. And I think it was that woman's chat,

'cause, I was worried that how we would feel, 'cause she was very wary of adults. "Big people she called them". [Laughs]. She saw her potential; she knew her goal. So, she is now at college and the wee boy is at nursery and Ah saw that glimmer of hope that she could achieve something.

(Rose, FN)

Nadia found resilience in her love of writing and despite her disrupted education due to her poor mental health, she formed positive relationships with one of the senior school staff. This made her want to continue to further develop her education. Her FN confirmed.

She's [Nadia] wanting to go to college and she's wanting to make a career for herself... just being able to say to her, 'you absolutely can do this. You've got the capacity to do this, and how can we move forward with this'... she absolutely loves speaking about where she wants to be in the future... what she wants to bring back to the family. (Pam, FN)

Emily wanted to work in childcare on leaving school but described being encouraged to accept an apprenticeship in a care of the elderly placement which she found distressing.

I was at an apprenticeship before I fell pregnant... I used to work with people with dementia...but there was quite a lot of deaths so...I think I'll go to college and do stuff and then I want to do childcare [sounds enthusiastic]. I've always wanted to do childcare. (Emily).

Rebecca was keen to train as a social worker as she wished to support other children and young people who had been in care.

I'm thinking of going back in January. Back to college... [to study] social care, I'll be starting off with an NQ [National Qualification] (Rebecca).

She [Rebecca] does, she wants to go to college, she actually applied to college, em. So, she applied to do, em, social care and her ambition is to be a social worker, 'cause she thinks having been through the system herself, she thinks she will be able to understand better than anybody. She got an interview for another college in Glasgow, but on that particular day she didn't have any childcare so, she didn't go. Em, so she has not

did anything about it, but she still speaks about it positively. She still speaks about it; it is still something she wants to do. (Rebecca's FN)

The CEP described a range of challenges. Poor sexual health and relationship education was cited. The CEP who had suffered sexual abuse were all resistant to discuss or accept supports regarding their contraceptive needs.

Homelessness was an area of concern and for the CEP who had been supported in supported homeless accommodation the risks of exploitation and substance misuse were shared. Supported foster accommodation appeared to be a very limited resource within both the local authority areas. Ongoing housing needs were evident for a few of the CEP who resided in overcrowded accommodation or were isolated from supports due to their concerns about being housed in an area of high deprivation.

Poverty was an issue for the majority of the CEP. Sanctions and claiming of benefits were challenges for the CEP and professionals who sought to support them to maximise their income. Nearly all the CEP were motivated to study or seek employment to improve their family finances for their family and their need for dependable childcare was recognised.

4.3 Summary of Findings.

Three key themes of trauma, relationships and transitions, with associated sub-themes, clearly emerged from the high volume of qualitative data generated from the case studies and wider focus group (see Figure 4.2). The key issues underpinning the themes and sub-themes had a profound impact on the young mothers in the case studies. This is evidenced through the rich description of their experiences, as supported by the direct quotes. The shared verbatim quotes have expressed meaningful, relevant and valuable data about this vulnerable group of young mothers. This may influence future practice. These personal accounts provided the reader with a privileged insight into life as it is experienced by this vulnerable group of care experienced young mothers and by those involved in their lives.

Figure 4.2 Summary of interlinking themes and sub-themes.

Chapter 5. Discussion and conclusion

5.1 Introduction

This study aim was: To explore how care experienced teenage parents (CEP) are supported to reduce the challenges associated with both leaving care and becoming a teenage parent.

The objectives set to achieve the overall aim were to:

1. Critically explore the protective factors and challenges that CEP experience that impact on their parenting of their child.
2. Critically explore CEP perceptions of their support needs when making their parenting choices.
3. Consider from the experiences of Children's Services, carers and other significant individuals, wider systemic factors that enable or constrain their practice to support CEP care for their child.
4. Generate evidence-based recommendations which may inform future policy, practice, further research and education.

Using a case study approach, data were collated from CEP, their family nurses, and in 3 cases, their significant others (a foster carer, housing support worker and a mental health officer). In addition, qualitative information was obtained from the wider social work team around their experience of supporting CEP. Through the process of thematic analysis of the rich volume of qualitative data, three themes emerged: Trauma: Shadows of Childhood; Relationships: Networks; and Transitions: Life Events. Each theme incorporated subthemes which are summarised in Table 5.1 along with the significant issues raised. In this chapter key findings are discussed in relation to current literature relevant to CEP, and the conclusions of the study are summarised.

Trauma: Shadows of Childhood	Relationships: Networks	Transitions: Life Events
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shame and self-blame • Numbing • Repressed memories and triggers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With birth family • With partner • With others 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pregnancy • Parenthood • Leaving care and setting up home • Plans for the future
Related significant issues		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mental health issues • Sexual abuse • Childhood neglect • Substance misuse/ other risk-taking behaviours • Fear (care homes) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reconnect/disconnect with birth family • Disparity - meeting emotional needs • Mental health, sexual abuse, childhood neglect issues • Fears/anxieties - child protection issues • Stigma/anxiety - unfit parent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sexual/reproductive health issues • Implications/dilemmas – pregnancy/becoming a mother • Setting up home/safe place/ homelessness • Financial and lifestyle issues/changes Aspirations/future plans • Living with poverty • Stigma

Table 5.1 Themes, sub-themes and related significant issues.

The significant issues identified within the main findings have profoundly impacted the emotional, psychological, and quality of life of the CEP. When issues are considered in the context of the bioecological Systems Model there is potential for these issues to impact positively or negatively on the quality of life of individuals (see Figure 5.1).

Figure 5.1 Significant issues relating to the five systems in Bronfenbrenner and Ceci's bioecological model

The emerged themes and subthemes demonstrated the interweave and relationships between the different systems in the bioecological model. Interconnected factors contributing to the opportunities and challenges the CEP experienced, were illustrated in the findings e.g., poor family support and lack of childcare; stigma and access to service; housing and antisocial behaviour within the wider community; claiming benefits and securing a tenancy; the legislation of the Children and Young People's (Scotland) Act (2014) and professionals' responses; seeking training opportunities and accessing childcare. Implementing appropriate collaborative actions to make changes and adaptations to address these multi-factorial issues has the potential to improve a wide range of health, well-being and lifestyle outcomes for CEP and their children.

This chapter discusses the findings of this study in the context of the previous literature on care experienced young parents discussed in the literature review in Chapter 2.

5.2 Trauma: Shadows of childhood (Microsystem/Chronosystem)

The experiences of childhood trauma for the CEP contributed to the challenges they encountered as they left their care setting and adjusted to becoming a parent. Half of the CEP in this study had significant ongoing mental health issues including self-harming, suicidal intent, anorexia and mood disorder. These findings are consistent with the large scale study by Dworsky and DeCoursey (2009) of 4,590 foster care pregnant and parenting young people who found that one-third of the female and two-fifths of the males required mental health services. It also corresponds to the earlier studies that CEP are more likely to have suffered from neglect and trauma and have a higher incidence of mental health problems (Barn and Mantovani, 2007; Coleman-Cowger *et al.*, 2011; Narendorf *et al.*, 2013; Botchway *et al.*, 2014; Roberts, 2017; Wilson, 2017).

In this present study one case illustrated the CEP's longstanding history of poor mental health. This CEP engaged well with her Significant Other who was a mental health officer and her FN. The CEP spoke positively and trusted the wider agency help. Unfortunately, one of the other CEP, who suffered trauma and poor mental health prior to and during pregnancy, experienced barriers in accessing acceptable mental health provision in the critical perinatal period. This is consistent with the concerns raised in a large scale by Coleman-Cowger *et al.* (2011) and Aparicio (2017), who evidenced that despite CEP's increased vulnerability to poor mental health, there appeared to be little literature considering pre and post-natal mental health needs of CEP.

5.2.1 Numbing

Two of the CEP in this study, had experienced significant trauma and had little social support. The CEP had turned substance misuse in what appeared to be their way of avoiding the painful memories and the ongoing significant stresses they continued to experience. Evidence highlighted the increased incidence of care experienced young people misusing substances (Williams and Parker, 2001; Alderson *et al.*, 2017). Substance misuse in this present study appeared to be linked to the poor mental health of the CEP and lack of available social support after leaving their family home or foster

care setting. The misuse of substances also links to the study by Aparicio's phenomenological study (2017) who found that substance abuse was being used by some participants with mental health problems as a negative coping strategy.

5.2.2 *Shame and self-blame*

In this study, half of the cases highlighted that CEP had been a victim of childhood sexual abuse and for one CEP feelings of self-blame and disgust were expressed. This corresponds to the findings of Bermea *et al.*'s (2019) qualitative study, who found that participants in their study struggled to reconcile the abuse they were subjected to when they themselves became parents.

Another CEP spoke of her shame of a care worker being injured whilst the CEP was physically restrained over what she reported was an escalation of a minor behavioural issue during a very difficult time in the young woman's life. Subsequent court hearings were held during the CEP pregnancy and child and family social work intervention was instigated as a result of this event. Mendes *et al.* (2014b) discussed that restraint of a CEP has the potential to trigger or re-traumatise the young person. The Promise (2020) recognises it is the care settings and the staff's responses to the young person's behaviour that is leading to the criminalisation of CEP.

5.2.3 *Triggers and repressed memories*

One CEP appeared traumatised following the birth of her child and the FN was concerned for the CEP mental health in the post-birth period. The FN described the barriers she experienced in seeking mental health support for the CEP at that time due to the CEP no longer being registered with a GP. Although the CEP mental health improved over the following months, the CEP was fearful that if she engaged with mental health services in the future, speaking about the abuse she endured would again make her ill and she would have no one to care for her daughter. Barriers to mental health services for CEP have been highlighted in the literature review by Eastman *et al.* (2019). Aparicio (2017) found that the limited choice of mental health treatments and the stigma of engaging with mental health, meant the mental health services were unable to meet the participant's mental health needs. This CEP in the present study, as her child grew, became preoccupied with the fear her child could also be exposed to sexual abuse. This further builds on the evidence of Leeners *et*

al.'s, (2006) systematic review, which evidenced that sexual abuse survivors repressed emotions can re-surface when they became parents.

Another case identified that a CEP remained vulnerable to triggers resulting in her self-harming and suicide attempts. However, the CEP was reluctant to engage in mental health services or medication from her GP and her FN continued to have concerns for the CEP mental health.

5.3 Relationships (Microsystem/Meso/Exosystem)

5.3.1 Relationship with birth family

Similar to the previous studies by Love *et al.* (2005) and Chase *et al.* (2006), most of the CEP in the case studies had been hopeful the birth of their baby would re-connect them to their birth family. However, two-thirds of the CEP at the time of data collection were resigned to not having a relationship with their maternal figure due to their expectations not being met or ongoing abusive behaviours. During pregnancy a third of the CEP in this study were involved in court proceedings against their family. This finding provides further credence to other studies (Biehal *et al.*, 1996; Radey *et al.*, 2016; Aparicio, 2018), who identified participants rarely received support from their biological families and instead families were a source of further distress. Furthermore, a third of the CEP in the current study provided, rather than received, support to their mother or father, which corresponds to the findings of Cashmore and Paxman (2007). Some CEP in this study, due to ongoing risks to their child, were advised by SW not to have contact with the child's grandparent. This is similar to the interventions of social workers in stopping grandparents' involvement due to child safety concerns described in the study by Aparicio *et al.* (2015). For the few CEP who decided to have an ongoing relationship with their mother, the CEP spoke of their relationship with optimism. However, from the FN and SO perspective, it appeared strict boundaries in their family relationships were required to ensure the CEP's well-being was maintained. In two of the case studies, the CEP had some support from their partner's mother or from a stepsibling, which relates to the prior studies (Wade and Dixon, 2006; Haight *et al.*, 2009) who found extended female family members provided social support.

5.3.2 Relationship with partner

In all the cases the CEP was living with her partner. These findings are contrary to the findings of Botchway *et al.* (2014), large cross sectional survey who found their female participants were usually single parents. Inexperience of healthy, reciprocal relationships means care experienced teenage parents are more likely to be affected by intimate partner violence (IPV) (Roberts, 2017; Font *et al.*, 2020; Bermea *et al.*, 2020). In this current study controlling, physical and emotionally abusive behaviours had been a feature for half of the CEP, which contributed to the involvement of child and family social work.

In one of the cases the CEP was briefly separated from her long term partner and struggled with being a lone parent, causing her mental health to deteriorate. This further relates to other qualitative studies by Biehal *et al.* (1995); Maxwell *et al.* (2011); Radey *et al.* (2016), who found that insufficient support to young mothers resulted in participants being overwhelmed by the demands of parenthood.

All of the CEP spoke positively of their partners. Some CEP and the FNs recognised the child's father or stepfather were more confident in promoting positive behaviour in their child. This collaborates with previous research (Capaldi *et al.*, 2002; Lamb and Lewis, 2010) who reported the quantity and quality of father-child interactions during the early childhood years promote children's emotional regulation. It also corresponds with the findings of Haight *et al.* (2009) who found, despite difficulties in their intimate partner relationships, that the young parents gave each other practical and emotional support.

In some of the case studies, the CEP's partners were also care experienced and they too had also been impacted by unresolved trauma, poor mental health and difficult relationships with their birth mothers. These CEP offered some emotional support to their partners. However, the FNs and the Mental Health officer recognised they also had the potential to drain the CEP's own coping strategies too. This links Tyrer *et al.*'s (2005) research, who found that providing support to male CEP may benefited the mother's social support.

Young men's parenting skills in this current study were supported by the FNP as part of the delivery of the FNP programme. A third of the CEP voiced that access to

additional parenting support groups for their partners were either not available or did not meet their partner's complex emotional needs. The finding echoes those raised by Combs *et al.* (2018) who concluded that extended supports for male CEP improved the mother's coping abilities.

5.3.3 *Relationship with others*

5.3.3.1 *Child and Family Social Work.*

Attending social work meetings was a stressful situation for the CEP. All of the CEP in this study had been reported to Child and Family Social Work during pregnancy. In 3 of the cases the CEP's children had been on the child protection register. However, there were some positive outcomes from the child protection meetings. These cases suggest that the co-ordinated multi-agency support and additional resources, helped the CEP and supported their child's well-being. Access to maternity and other health services, accommodation needs were supported and parenting and life skills promoted. This finding corresponds with studies which evidence that CEP are more likely to benefit from additional supports to help them cope with parenting challenges (Courtney *et al.*, 2005; Dworsky and Courtney, 2010; Font *et al.*, 2019).

During the focus group, the SW team stated that their involvement with some of the CEP may have been due to the fact that the majority of notifications of concern originated from health professionals. This adds to the debate around increased surveillance bias versus the higher incidence of child protection concerns when working with CEP (Widon and Wilson, 2015; Walls-Weiller *et al.*, 2018; Armfield *et al.*, 2021).

A few of the CEP described past positive support from SW but explained their feelings of loss when a valued SW moved, which links with qualitative study by Dominelli *et al.* (2005) who recognised the benefits a positive relationship with a SW could bring. The CEP in this current research, despite their many obstacles, spoke of pride in their self-reliance. SW in this study discussed the importance of forming relationships with the CEP and recognised that CEP attachment styles could mean forming a trusting relationship would take time and commitment. Unfortunately, the SW admitted that bureaucratic procedures and tight time frames meant that their availability to form trusting relationships was compromised. One CEP, who had not formed a trusting

relationship with her new SW, concealed her pregnancy. This further adds to the evidence by Dominelli *et al.*'s (2005) research, which found that when participants could not relate to new workers, their challenges eventually manifested.

Following the birth of their child, half of the CEP viewed the child and family SW intervention in their lives as a threat. Many CEP voiced their fear of having their child removed from their care. Stigma and the anxiety of being deemed an unfit parent corresponds with existing evidence of the majority of CEP being distrustful of child protection interventions (Rutman *et al.*, 2002; Chase *et al.*, 2006; Chase, 2009; Mantovani and Thomas, 2007). Children and family SWs in this study described having a combined role when undertaking child protection investigations, as the focus shifted from CEPs' needs to ensuring the CEP's child's safety. This finding builds on previous evidence (Rutman, 2002; Roberts *et al.*, 2019), that identified SW's dual role as problematic.

In one of the cases the CEP was frustrated that SW frequently referred to her own mother's failings during the child protection meeting, despite the fact she had been away from her mother's care since a toddler. The SW's perspective from the focus group was that CEP wariness of their support services can make assessing the CEP's capacity to parent and develop their parenting skills more difficult. This finding links to the findings from Aparicio *et al.* (2015) who highlighted reluctance to engage with services often led to professional's risk assessments being based solely on historical evidence of the CEP birth family.

5.3.3.2 Relationship with health professionals.

The CEP described the benefits of having their family nurse visit as being a reassuring source of information to a first time mother, through provision of parenting advice and educational materials. Other benefits raised were the facilitation of access to other health services and community resources, that they were non-directive and that they spent time with them to listen. Social Work staff also spoke of the acceptability of the Family Nurse Partnership. This finding is fitting with a previous study by Datta *et al.* (2017) where the young parents and participants likewise valued the benefits of the FNP programme in supporting the young parents' needs through individualised, relationship focussed work.

Many spoke positively of their midwife, however a few of the CEP mentioned being anxious about attending midwifery care for fear of the treatment they would receive. The fear of engaging with health services may correlate with Mantovani and Thomas's (2013) study which found that health professionals were unaware of the participant's complex social circumstances, which then impacted on the sensitivity of care they received. Some of the CEP who suffered CSA had concerns about engaging with maternity services, which may be linked to the findings of Montgomery *et al.*'s (2015) study which found that attending maternity care was still a traumatic experience for mothers who had been victims of CSA, even with sensitive midwifery care.

The issue of stigma from engagement with wider health services and the concern the CEP in this study would be perceived as a "bad mum" was raised in most of the cases. It is recognised that stigma could undermine the CEP's confidence in their parenting ability and stop the CEP accessing the very services that are available to support them (Chase *et al.*, 2006; Maxwell *et al.*, 2011).

5.3.3.3 Relationship with carers

Five of the CEP, in accordance to their age and stage of development, (Piaget, 1950 cited in McLeod, 2018) sought to have increased autonomy in their lives, which seemed to negatively impact on the relationship with their carer and the CEPs leaving their care setting. This finding relates to earlier qualitative research by Biehal *et al.* (1996) and Dominelli *et al.* (2005) concluded the care system restrictions failed to support their transition into adult life, 'and thereby increased their vulnerability when they left care.

Although one CEP initially found the move to supported foster care distressing, she did acknowledge the benefits of moving from her partner's home to a supported foster care placement in the post-natal period. She also spoke positively of another CEP resident who appeared to give her hope and confidence in her own abilities as a parent. This resonates with Bermea *et al.*'s (2020) study where participants spoke of feeling secure with the range of support within the mother and child foster carer unit and the other young mothers who resided there.

The mother and child foster carer in this study was described as a positive support to the CEP. The foster carer watched the CEP grow in confidence as she helped her to

manage routines and supported her responsive parenting. The positive parenting support of mother and baby foster care were also found in previous studies (Scheble and Geiger, 2017). In this present study, the foster carer shared her concerns about the CEP's decision to continue in the relationship with her child's father. This was due to him having demonstrated abusive behaviours towards the CEP. This finding builds upon Radey *et al.*'s (2016) study, where carers shared the concerns that female CEP's romantic relationships were unhealthy.

5.4 Transitions (Macro/chronosystem)

5.4.1 Pregnancy

In all of the cases the CEP had some awareness of sexual health and relationship education within either primary or secondary school. However, four of the CEP were often unable to participate fully in some of the lessons because of school exclusion, mental health problems or their own distressing history of sexual abuse. This finding corresponds to Aparicio *et al.*'s (2019) small phenomenological study and the recommendations that sexual health services to CEP needed to consider they CEP's' emotional well-being needs and that services need to be delivered though taking a sensitive, trauma informed approach.

All the CEP in the present study considered they had sufficient knowledge about pregnancy prevention. Nevertheless, they still held inaccurate beliefs about how pregnancy could be prevented. This builds on Chase *et al.*'s (2006) UK study, who found that participants described sexual health and relationship education as not meeting their needs. Only one CEP disclosed being able to access sexual health education via her care placement. An appointment with a sexual health worker was made on her behalf, as the residential staff appreciated they not have sufficient knowledge. This corresponds to USA evidence that young people in care would benefit from timely, targeted sexual health and advice (Aparicio, 2015; Oshia *et al.*, 2018; King *et al.*, 2019) and that social care practitioners are reluctant to discuss sexual relationships as they lack knowledge on this subject (Chase, 2003; Love, 2005; Matta Oshima *et al.*, 2013; Aparicio, 2015; Albertson *et al.*, 2018; Rouse *et al.*, 2020).

Most of the pregnancies in this study were unintentional, which mirrors the findings by Chase *et al.* (2006) who found the majority of the participant's pregnancies were

unplanned. Previous research (Chase *et al.*, 2006; Craine *et al.*, 2014) discovered that CEP are often opposed to abortions. Two of the CEP struggled to decide whether to continue with the pregnancy due to relationship difficulties with their partner, but despite the lack of wider social support these CEP decided against terminating their pregnancy. Two CEP spoke of their pregnancies being intentional as they wished to establish a family. This finding was in keeping with research which described CEP as wishing to have someone of their own to love (Chase *et al.*, 2006; Pryce and Samuels, 2010; Albertson *et al.*, 2018).

5.4.2 Becoming a Mum

All the CEP made positive lifestyle changes during pregnancy or shortly after birth to enable their child to have a healthy future. Two of the CEP reflected on their children as having 'saved' them from addiction and mental health difficulties and expressed their children had given them an increased sense of purpose in their life. The idea of 'being saved' corresponds to the research of Bermea *et al.* (2018) and Rutman *et al.* (2001) who discovered becoming parents increased participant's sense of control from their previously destructive lives.

5.4.3 Being a good Mum

Throughout all the case studies the intrinsic motivation to provide better care than they had experienced for their children was evident. This finding resonates with existing literature (Barn and Mantovani, 2007; Chase *et al.*, 2009; Schelbe *et al.*, 2016; Broadhurst *et al.*, 2017; Aparicio *et al.*, 2018; Bermea *et al.*, 2018) of the participant's motivation to parent better than their own mother.

5.4.4 Parenting

Most of the CEP in this current research were isolated from positive extended family female role models to support their parenting practices. To enhance their parenting abilities, all of the CEP had voluntarily participated in the Family Nurse Partnership (FNP) programme. The Family Nurses sought to help the CEP to create positive environments to enhance their children's development, to promote the CEP own self efficacy by engaging the families in additional services in their local community and by involving their partners in home visits, where appropriate.

Two of the CEP spoke positively of engaging with young mothers parenting groups in their community, which provided further opportunities to improve their parenting skills and to reduce social isolation. This corresponds with the findings from the findings of Shelbe and Geiger's (2017) study who recognised the benefit of parenting classes in improving parenting skills and reducing social isolation. Four of the CEP in this present study did not engage in parenting classes and previous studies have indicated that CEP have been reluctant to attend group supports (Courtney *et al.*, 2011; Aparicio, 2017; Aparicio *et al.*, 2018). However, two of the CEP resided in remote rural areas which may have impacted on their ability to access local group parenting programmes. SW in this current study acknowledged many parenting groups had been cancelled because of staff shortages. Two CEP were adamant they did not want other agencies involvement and this mistrust of supportive services was evidenced in the literature (Chase *et al.*, 2003; Lanctot and Turcotte, 2018). Teenage mothers often encountered discrimination from peers and within their community (Yardley, 2008), which perhaps stopped some CEP in this study engaging in wider community activities.

One CEP who moved to group foster care, spoke positively of peer support and sharing of parenting experiences, which has been highlighted in other studies. (Radey *et al.*, 2016; Armfield *et al.*, 2021).

5.4.5 Stigma

The cultural norms and societal values (macrosystem) associated with the stigma of teenage pregnancy impacted negatively on the CEP. The CEP often spoke of the stigma they felt of being both a teenage parent and being care experienced. They appeared to feel they were frequently being judged within the community and by agencies, making them feel they had to prove themselves as good mothers. Other studies have also found CEP felt judged by services, causing the participant to feel a sense of self-blame (Rutman *et al.*, 2002; Mantovani and Thomas, 2014). Similarly, Bermea *et al.* (2018) found CEP engagement with services could be affected by societal stigma related to them being young mothers.

5.4.6 Rapid repeat pregnancy

Rapid repeat pregnancies were experienced by half of the CEP and this high incidence is similar to the findings of the USA studies (Bilaver *et al.*, 2006; Courtney *et al.*, 2007; Dworsky and Courtney, 2010; Putman and Hornstein, 2013; Aparicio, 2018). A further

CEP was planning a subsequent pregnancy as she felt she was unlikely to achieve any other life goal. This adds further credibility to other studies (Aparicio *et al.*, 2018; Bucknall, 2019) which evidenced that doubts about their ability to secure employment made them rapidly increase their family. One CEP disclosed that her partner's desire to expand their family over-rode the CEP's intention to recover from a previous miscarriage before conceiving again. In this case there was the possibility of coercive behaviour, in line with PettyJohn *et al.*'s (2021) findings, whose study discovered reproductive coercion of care experienced young women by older males was common.

5.4.7 Leaving care and setting up home

The macrosystem includes the cultural values and the economic conditions under which families live (Bronfenbrenner, 1976). Mullins-Geiger (2017) evidenced that despite having the right to stay until aged 21, most care experienced young people left care by aged 18. The CEP in this study had all left their care setting between the ages of 16-17. The CEP considered inflexible and rigid rules in the residential home, or foster care placement, influenced their decision to move. The CEP risk taking behaviours, importance of peers, increased autonomy and testing of adult relationships, which is normal to their stage of development, seemed to be unsupported. This re-enforces the findings of Biehal *et al.* (1996) and Dominelli *et al.* (2005) who concluded that participants were not scaffolded during adolescence to develop their increased sense of self efficacy within the care setting.

Having a secure base to return to (Bowlby, 1988) after they left care was not an option for the majority of the CEP. In this study, only CEP, who had been living with an abusive partner, was provided with a mother and baby foster care placement. Unlike literature that found young mothers in care felt judged and undermined by the foster carer (La Sala, 2020), this CEP identified her foster carer as a significant support.

Each case study identified that the CEP had experienced homelessness since leaving care and all CEP identified their challenges of securing a suitable tenancy for them and their family. This experience of homelessness is consistent with findings in other studies (Stein, 2006; Dworsky *et al.*, 2009; Pecora *et al.*, 2009; Shpiegel *et al.*, 2020). Most of the CEP in this study, two of whom were either in early or late pregnancy at the time, resided in homeless support units with other adults. These cases provided evidence that during the varying periods that the CEP lived in the homeless unit, this

timeframe actively contributed to their substance misuse, fears for their safety, exploitation and deterioration in their mental health. The SO (Mental Health Officer) for one CEP urgently supported the young woman to be re-housed due to her exploitation by males residing in there. There appeared to be no previous literature exploring CEP's experiences of residing in supported homeless accommodation.

Two of the CEP became homeless having left their tenancy due to their neighbour's anti-social behaviours. A further challenge highlighted during the present study was that 2 of the CEP were residing in an overcrowded small one-bedroom local authority property in an area of high deprivation with their toddler and partner, due to lack of suitable alternative housing offers in good areas. This is comparable to the findings of Schelbe *et al.* (2013) who found participants were anxious about their family's safety as their welfare housing offers were often in areas of high deprivation.

Social work staff in this study discussed the lack of available mother and baby foster carers, to support CEP, within the two Health and Social Care Partnership areas, and their frustrations about lack of suitable accommodation and resources to support CEPs' accommodation needs; this appeared to echo the findings from social work staff in Robert *et al.*'s (2019) study. Supported foster care placements appear to be a scarce resource in the areas. For the one CEP in this study who had been provided with a supported foster placement, this was sourced from another local authority area. The lack of foster care provision for young mothers and their babies was also a finding in USA-based literature (Dworsky and DeCoursey, 2009; Shpiegel *et al.*, 2020).

The researcher's field notes documented that 3 of the CEP lived in sparse conditions, despite a restricted budget being assigned to them by the local authority. Furniture was often achieved through taking out a loan, further reducing their disposable income. Professionals spoke of sourcing food parcels for some CEP and FNs and SW recognised some CEP needed support to complete forms to claim their additional benefits. FNs discussed the challenges of benefits being received in a timely way and the impact of benefit sanctions. This relates to evidence by Baker *et al.* (2019) whose work indicated that participants were living in poverty and also adds to Dominelli *et al.*'s (2005) finding of corporate parent's expectations of CEP to be able to successfully parent without receiving the basic resources.

All six of the CEP in this current study were not in employment or training, following the birth of their child, and all were impacted by poverty. Evidence of poverty and the increased strain on the CEP has been well established (Barn and Mantovani, 2007; Courtney *et al.*, 2012; Radey *et al.*, 2016). In addition to all of the CEP in this study not being in employment, most of their partners were either unable to gain employment or had insecure or reduced hour contracts. This finding reflects previous studies where both male and female CEP are affected by limited employment opportunities. Challenges of finding suitable employment and childcare to escape poverty is frequently illustrated in earlier studies (Aparicio *et al.*, 2015; Mendes, 2009; Levie, *et al.*, 2015; Combs *et al.*, 2018b; Dworsky and Gitlow, 2017; Baker, *et al.*, 2019; Schelbe *et al.*, 2020).

5.4.8 Plans for the future

In two of the cases the CEP had career aspirations for the near future. One of the CEP with low educational attainment, who had been excluded from school, was supported by her FN to consider her career options and had firm plans in place to attend college. The other CEP who reported being well supported by her secondary school during a period of poor mental health, remained motivated to attend university to further her education and had set a timeline to achieve her goals. Due to lack of extended family supports, local authority childcare provisions were sought to minimise the poor employment opportunities associated with lack of childcare as found in other studies (Dworsky and Gitlow, 2015; Dworsky and Gitlow, 2017; Schelbe *et al.*, 2020) and to enable the CEP to seek her career goals.

5.5 Conclusion

This study has made a significant contribution to the existing body of literature in relation to exploring how CEP are supported to reduce the challenges associated with both leaving care and becoming a teenage parent. The study has provided meaningful insight into the challenges faced by CEP living in Scotland and the support the CEP experienced in both leaving care and becoming a teenage parent. It provides further insight into the young people's experience of being a care experienced and a teenage parent in Scotland.

The bioecological framework for the study illustrated the importance of understanding the CEP experience of support within their community and social relationships. The complexity of the CEP's relationships with family, foster carers, partners, professionals and the impact of wider society and socio-economic and political policies interacted on multiple aspects of the CEP's life during their childhood and adolescence. The bioecological model provided a holistic approach that has widely influenced national policy and children's services practice (Houston, 2017). However, a criticism of the model is that insufficient attention has been given to the power differential in the relationship between the young person and professionals (Houston, 2017). This study illustrated at times, due to the CEP's fear of being judged, that it deterred the CEP's engagement with the very supports that could positively impact on their life.

The findings have reinforced some of the existing knowledge, mainly from USA literature, of the many challenges that CEP experience. Some early studies on CEP were conducted during the early 1990's, and although over 30 years have passed, the challenges faced have continued relevance for current CEP living in Scotland. The case studies and wider social work team's contribution have provided a multidimensional perspective on the range of CEP's experiences during this time of transitions.

The research has provided a specific focus on the experiences of CEP in Scotland using the themes of Trauma, Relationships and Transitions. It has highlighted the profound psychological impact that experiences of childhood trauma have had on the CEP. Related issues such as sexual abuse and childhood neglect included feelings of shame, self-blame and numbing of all feelings, with triggers re-igniting negative memories and stimulating fear. Associated experiences included mental health issues and engaging in risk-taking behaviours.

Transitions were inevitable due to the CEP leaving their care setting and setting up their own home alongside the implications faced by parenthood and becoming a mother. These life events created dilemmas for the CEP and major challenges for them to cope with, such as living with poverty or finding a suitable and safe living environment for themselves and their children. CEP also had to deal with the further stigma associated with their change in circumstances and experience of homelessness.

The relationships the CEP had with individuals and groups in their lives impacted on the level of social support available to them. These relationships included those with birth families, partner/father of their child and with the range of professionals and carers involved in their lives. Relationships with birth families were mostly either tentative or non-existent, which could often be complex due to childhood sexual abuse and neglect, and inadequate emotional support. The impact of the proposed GIRFE multi-agency approach for supporting families transitioning from GIRFEC with multiple and/or complex needs will require ongoing evaluation and review to ensure it is successfully implemented across Scotland.

Family Nurses supported the CEP's parenting skills and child's well-being. They also engaged with the child's multi-agency child protection and care plans. The Family Nurses acted as intermediates with a range of other services and agencies promoting access to services, including women's health services, mental health provisions, maximising their finances, early years' education and career services. The Significant Others in their lives attempted to support them with housing, mental health challenges, parenting skills and worked with other agencies to support them overcome the multiple challenges they faced.

Involvement with the Child and Family Social Workers during their pregnancy and post birth periods, resulted in most CEP expressing wariness of continued involvement with social work staff. Some CEP were reluctant to engage with ongoing supports due to their concerns of further scrutiny. These situations were also associated with their own childhood histories of being in care, deteriorating mental health, anxieties, fears and the stigma linked with being labelled an unfit mother. The challenges of social worker's dual role of supporting the CEP's needs whilst prioritising any child protection concerns appeared at times problematic for both the social work staff and the CEP. Child and family social workers also described their workload pressures, difficulties accessing some resources, the dual focus on protecting their child and the CEP's attachment style as having impacted on their ability to build a supportive relationship with CEP.

Despite these negative connotations, the CEP also shared plans for the future for themselves and children.

The researcher hopes the findings of this study will provide increased focus on the particular needs of CEP. The case studies have illustrated the challenges and supports CEP experienced as they set up their home and parented their child. Through these profound challenges, there was evidence of hope and aspirations for the future. Although these young women encountered many difficulties, becoming a mother was an important achievement in their lives.

Chapter 6. Reflexivity, implications and recommendations

This final chapter presents a summary of the researcher's reflexivity to identify how the researcher aimed to minimise any personal judgement or beliefs that may have incidentally affected the research. The challenges, strengths and limitations of the study acknowledged through ongoing reflection are outlined. Based on the key findings, implications for professional practice are proposed. Finally, key recommendations for practice, education, policy and future research are detailed.

6.1 Reflexivity

Reflexivity is essential in qualitative research as the researcher needs to be acutely aware of their role in undertaking the research. This activity is necessary to minimise the possibility of research bias by being specific about the researcher and their position (Lambert *et al.*, 2010). The epistemological view of the researcher is known to influence the methodology and methods chosen for the study (Gray, 2018) which in turn guides both the research processes and outcomes (Haynes, 2012). Furthermore, the relationship with the participants, the framing of the questions, the analysis and writing up of the research are all impacted by the researcher's views (Mason-Bish, 2019). As the researcher in this study, being reflexive involved examining my own beliefs and judgements that could have inadvertently influenced the findings during the data collection and analysis stages. I had to consider whether my political views, beliefs or other biases could have impacted the outcomes of the study.

Throughout data collection and analysis, I maintained a reflexive diary to explore my own personal values and experiences. Some of the CEP accounts left me with feelings of sadness for the difficulties they experienced in childhood, as well as feelings of admiration for how they managed some of their many challenges. The reflexive diary enabled me to critically consider whether my bias could have inadvertently influenced the study. I recognised my perceptions may have been skewed due to previously witnessing how socially isolated CEP struggle and sometimes fail to overcome their parenting difficulties. I was also aware of my desire to highlight the challenges the CEP have encountered. Whilst attempting to commence data collection and the thematic analysis with an open mind, my desire that the research may change policy and practice to further support the CEP had to be contained. I also recognised the need to

immerse myself in all participant's viewpoints and experiences to ensure I accurately reflected the findings from their perspectives. During meetings with my research supervisors, significant statements were shared and opinions were discussed and debated until agreement was reached. This process served to minimise bias and gain a wider viewpoint of the themes emerging from the qualitative data.

The benefit of some self-disclosure is that it helps the researcher facilitate an early connection with the participant and minimises the researcher being viewed by participants as the expert (Dickson-Swift *et al.*, 2007). However, self-disclosure can also create boundary challenges, with the possibility of the researcher being seen by the participant as a 'friend'. This has the potential to limit the extent to which the participant's sharing their experiences that were relevant to the study's aims (Dickson-Swift *et al.*, 2007). I was mindful of the extent of self-disclosure before commencing the research. I decided that I was only willing to share that I had also been an adolescent mother, in order to promote a connection with the CEP. No further personal information was shared with participants.

6.1.1 *Insider research*

Dodgson (2019) states that qualitative research is contextual. Therefore, the researcher must demonstrate how the study was conducted to enable the reader to understand the relevance of the research and the applicability of the research findings. As the qualitative researcher is often viewed as being the 'research instrument' (Stake, 1995) it is important that readers can understand the researcher's positionality in relation to what is being studied. This transparency enhances the quality of the qualitative studies.

The strengths and weaknesses of a qualitative researcher having an 'insider position' have been widely discussed (Savvides *et al.*, 2014; Hayfield and Huxley, 2015). Researchers have debated that having an insider status may provide additional advantages, including ease of access, rapport and impact (Hayfield and Huxley, 2015, p. 92), Others have considered that outsiders may observe and consider topics in more detail than an insider might overlook (Liu and Burnett, 2022).

My insider status within the health board area provided several advantages as a researcher. These advantages included easy access to the 'gatekeepers' (the two

local authorities and a health board area), my FNP colleagues' belief that I would act with a trustworthy and ethical approach, access to the CEP participants, the availability of secure data collection, and the ability to interpret the data due to my understanding of the current social and political context. I reflected on the potential benefits of my 'insider positioning' as a nurse and that my experience, communication skills and training on trauma and strength-based approach perhaps helped me to establish a rapport with the participants. However, any awareness of the researcher's insider position could also result in a 'social desirability bias' (Oppenheim, 1992; Latkin *et al.*, 2017). This can lead to the reporting of misleading research results, with the potential for participants to present themselves as a 'perfect parent' and perhaps fail to accurately reflect the challenges they have or are experiencing. During the data collection, social desirability did not appear to be an issue and the participants appeared to have sufficient trust in me to speak openly about the successes and challenges they encountered.

Grove (2017) discussed the difference in power dynamics between the researcher and participant. For qualitative researchers, developing a clear understanding of reflexivity can be challenging. Throughout the research process, I attempted to manage the different positions integral to my role as both a Family Nurse Supervisor whilst seeking to maintain an objective viewpoint as a researcher. This left me feeling a sense of dichotomy and the need to frequently consider what perspective I was taking. This feeling of trying to manage my own knowledge and experiences had the potential to influence how I was interpreting the data and the assumptions I was reaching. The support from my academic supervisors was valuable in helping me to accurately reflect the findings according to the participant's views during the data analysis stage.

6.2 Reflection on the PhD journey

On reflection, this study was fraught with numerous challenges which negatively impacted the smooth navigation through several stages in the research process. In addition, the strengths and limitations of the study are acknowledged.

6.2.1 Challenges

The researcher faced several challenges in the quest to complete this study within the specified timeframe. The first challenge faced in the early planning stage was related

to gaining ethical approval for the study. This process became lengthy and complex due to the vulnerable nature of the proposed study population. The ethics committee were reassured by the stringent and robust recruitment and data management plans to protect the key ethical principles relating to the vulnerability of the participants.

The process to recruit participants for the study became challenging due to the nature of the population. Although other CEP expressed interest to their family nurse in participating in the study, there was difficulty making contact with some of them due to changing contact details, moving accommodation and incarceration. Other recruitment issues related to the inability to interview kinship carers as a couple of CEP no longer had contact with these carers. A few 'significant others' who were the CEP's partners agreed to participate but were lost to the study. No reason was offered from a couple of partners, with another partner indicating that his poor mental health meant he felt unable to participate. A professional Significant Other that was identified by a CEP, had moved job and it took time to make contact with her which caused a delay in her recruitment to the study.

A concerning challenge for one of the CEP and the researcher related to the verbally abusive and threatening behaviour of a third party. This was the sibling of the CEP who was babysitting to allow the CEP to participate in the interview. This behaviour intimidated both the CEP and the researcher. Despite the CEP apparent shock at her sister's behaviour, the CEP agreed to remain in the study.

The researcher's learning associated with undertaking this research also proved to be a journey as a greater understanding of methodology and method and conducting data analysis was gained.

The Covid-19 pandemic was unprecedented and had major impact on the research study and the researcher's work life. With the possible forthcoming first lockdown, the focus group for the wider social work team was urgently brought forward with key precautions being taken. The researcher needed to ensure a safe environment and social distancing for the focus group, whilst also maintaining the momentum of focus group discussions. The researcher's work life changed as a result of the need to take on demanding interim roles within the NHS. Furthermore, major disruptions to the University included a six-month period of closure which impacted on the academic team's delivery of support.

6.2.2 *Strengths and limitations*

The strengths of the study relate to the innovative research design in this field of interest, the wide range of viewpoints obtained and the detailed thematic analysis and triangulation of data. In the literature available, this study appears to be one of the few studies in Scotland that captures an insight of the experiences of a highly disadvantaged population. The study focused on how CEP in Scotland are supported to reduce the challenges associated with both leaving care and becoming a teenage parent. It provides further evidence and gives voice to teenage CEP experiences that may further influence the future work of The Promise Scotland. In this respect, the study findings have made a significant contribution from a unique perspective to the body of literature concerning CEP living in Scotland. The research design adopted a case study approach with additional input from the wider social work team. This was a beneficial as it enabled the researcher to capture viewpoints and experiences from the CEP and also from the point of view from individuals who knew the CEP or worked within the CEP community of practice. This approach involved triangulation of viewpoints which provided meaningful insight into the range of challenges, support, facilitators and barriers relating to the situation from a wider perspective.

Limitations related to the research include the small-scale nature of the study. However, the researcher considers the findings may be transferrable to other CEP within Scotland. A further limitation is that all the CEP were engaging with Family Nurse Partnership (FNP) parenting programme. Therefore, the participants recruited may not be representative of CEP who are not involved with FNP. All the CEP recruited to the research continued to have their child remain in their care during the study. Thus, the study's findings may not be reflective of the experiences of those CEP who have had their child removed from their care.

6.3 Implications and recommendations

Subsequent findings have highlighted the significant implications for practice relating to the care experience of young parents. In addition, the study findings have informed the evidence-based recommendations detailed which endorse specific actions required for practice, policy, and future research.

6.3.1 *Contribution to knowledge*

Dissemination of the original study findings is a priority as it is needed to contribute to the current dearth of available evidence in this area. A publication strategy is planned for the dissemination of the experiences of CEP transitioning from leaving care and becoming parents in Scotland. The strategy includes dissemination of the findings at national, UK and international levels. This will include publications in relevant UK and international peer reviewed journals and at national and international conferences with a focus on vulnerable adolescents and CEP.

A wide range of health and social care disciplines interested in the study findings include social work, mental health, family nurse partnership and third sector groups. Due to limited available evidence, a representative from the Scottish Government has already requested an update on the original findings and case studies to inform future related policies and contribute to the development of related national guidance. In Scotland, dissemination of the published findings will contribute to the evidence framework of the Independent Care Review (The Promise, 2020).

These original study findings are timely and fill a much-needed gap in the current body of limited evidence. The findings will influence the future work and commitment from the Scottish Government (2022b) to Keep the Promise for care experienced children, young people and their families. Importantly, the publications and dissemination of the original findings will also have implications as to how vulnerable young people and their families are supported as they transfer from GIRFEC (Scottish Government, 2022) to the proposed Getting It Right For Everyone (GIRFE) initiative (Scottish Government, 2023).

6.3.2 *Implications for practice*

From a practice perspective, CEP require sensitive, trauma informed sexual health and relationship education that explores the myriad of issues related to young care experienced people's decision to choose early parenthood. There is a need to reduce the high incidence of unintended pregnancies in this population. Sexual health and relationship education needs to be designed specifically to their experiences, emotional well-being and educational needs. It should also be delivered in a setting where they feel able to engage. Foster carers, health workers and residential staff,

social workers and other trusted adults in the CEP life should be encouraged and supported to promote sexual health and relationships education in early adolescence. (Relates to transition theme)

The findings of this study suggests that some practitioners within health and social work services did not respond to the CEP in a trauma informed approach (NHS Education for Scotland, 2017; Scottish Government, 2022a). It is anticipated that since this study was conducted, practitioners in health, education and social care have been supported to continue developing their understanding of trauma informed and trauma enhanced practice. Ongoing evaluation of practitioners practice should be conducted in consultation with CEP to ensure practitioners and organisations support trauma recovery. Increased awareness of the impact of adversity and trauma for practitioners working with CEP in health, housing, education and social work services is essential to promote effective engagement with services. (Relates to shadows of childhood/relationship network theme).

Corporate Parents in their commitment to care experienced children and young people (The Promise Scotland, 2021) should plan services and support around the needs of the CEP and their child. Issues of poverty, access to mental therapies, parenting skills, housing as well as education and employment opportunities for CEP requires increased focus (Relates to transition theme).

Health and Social Care services should capture data on male and female CEP experiences, to ensure a positive change in outcomes are being met. (Relates to transition theme).

Building capacity within the children and young people's workforce to meet the CEP's needs through relational based practice is required for this disadvantaged population (Relates to relationship network theme).

A whole family approach to provide support to each individual in the CEP's family to ensure their individual needs and common goals are met is required (Relates to relationship network theme).

Independent advocacy for CEP would assist the CEP to ensure their voice was heard and rights upheld during child protection meetings (Relates to transitions/relationship network theme).

A strength-based and rights-based practice approach (as identified in the UNCRC, GIRFEC refresh and GIRFE framework) to build on the CEP motivation to be a good mother and to promote trust and positive, effective relationships with the CEP is required (Relates to transitions/ relationship network theme).

The children and young people's workforce need to be alert to the increased potential for IPV in this group (Relates to relationship network theme).

There is an urgent need to address poverty and provide flexible childcare provision. This is needed to mitigate the lack of support from family members and enable the CEP to participate in training, education and work opportunities (Relates to transition theme).

6.3.3 Recommendations

- Specific sexual health and relationships education and interventions are required to reduce the high incidence of unplanned teenage pregnancy, RRP and IPV in care experienced young people. These programmes and interventions must be designed to meet their specific experiences, emotional well-being and educational needs and delivered in a setting where they feel able to engage.
- Bespoke continuous professional development sessions are necessary for the wider team caring for CEP, to assist in supporting timeous solution-focused action plans. These are required to raise awareness and increase understanding of the experiences of CEP concerning their emotional, psychological and physical well-being that are linked to the impact of childhood-related trauma, relationships, transition to parenthood, leaving care and potential homelessness and living in undesirable accommodation.
- Sustainable, easily accessible, trauma informed, evidence based parenting programmes for both the CEP and their partners are required. CEP should be supported to consider how their own parenting experiences affects the parenting of their own children to build on positive, responsive parental behaviours, whilst providing guidance for less positive behaviours.

6.3.4 Policy

- Policy guidance is urgently needed to address poverty experienced by CEP and provide flexible childcare provision to improve their opportunities for employment and lifestyle.
- Policy guidance is needed to identify a minimum standard of appropriate accommodation for CEP. This is required to address the current inappropriate and undesirable accommodation offered which negatively impacts on their psychological well-being and quality of life. This will provide opportunities for improved lifestyle outcomes for CEP and their children.
- Policy guidance and funding are needed to support a range of initiatives with a focus on improving quality of life and opportunities for CEP. This could include training CEP to work with their peers with regards to education of sexual health and family planning and dealing with other issues such as accommodation and finances. There is also an ideal opportunity to transfer these findings to healthcare education to create an emerging practitioner who will be aligned with CEP needs.

6.3.5 Future research

Further research is essential to provide robust evidence to inform policy and influence practice to support CEP. Future research requires well designed large prospective and longitudinal mixed methods studies to further investigate important issues such as CEP psychological well-being, social support and parenting outcomes. Research designs need to include both quantitative and qualitative methodologies to provide meaningful evidence which will influence policy and practice. Quantitative methodologies using robust methods and analysis will result in findings with the potential to be generalisable to the relevant population. Gaining subjective experiences from CEP through qualitative methodologies is also essential and can provide rich, meaningful and valuable insight into their lived experiences. Using both research methodologies prospectively will enable the investigations of outcomes and experiences over time.

Specific research needs to focus on childhood and unresolved trauma, poor mental health and difficult relationships. Due to the childhood trauma and the poor mental health the CEP participants experienced in the pre and post-natal period, a large scale,

mixed methods designed study is needed to explore the impact and extent of mental health issues on CEP in the first year following birth and beyond. Several CEP's partners were also care experienced and had suffered unresolved trauma, poor mental health and difficult relationships with their birth families. The original findings revealed that the emotional support the female CEP gave to their partners had the potential to drain their own coping strategies; therefore, it would be beneficial to conduct a qualitative study to explore the experiences of male CEP and how their physical and psychological wellbeing and parenting needs are supported. This would address the scarcity of studies that have explored the experiences of teenage male CEP.

This original study identified a range of challenges that the CEP experienced as they transitioned from leaving care and becoming a teenage parent. This was in relation to their housing, parenting supports, intimate relationships, sexual health and family planning, social support, poverty, continued education and employment needs. In this respect, a comparative research study needs to be conducted to compare these outcomes to those of other vulnerable and non-vulnerable teenage parents. Therefore, a prospective, longitudinal study, using a mixed methods design will be appropriate to evaluate the impact of the Promise Scotland Plan and GIRFE on the long-term outcomes for teenage CEP.

Chapter 7. References

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Chapter 8. Appendices

8.1 Appendix 1. Literature search process

8.2 Appendix 2. Health Research Authority approval

Health Research Authority

West Midlands - Coventry & Warwickshire Research Ethics Committee

13 September 2018

Dear Ms Kayes

Study title: **Getting it right for teenage parents who are in or leaving local authority or kinship care.**

Thank you for your letter of 27/08/2018, responding to the Committee's request for further information on the above research and submitting revised documentation.

The further information has been considered on behalf of the Committee by the Vice Chair.

We plan to publish your research summary wording for the above study on the HRA website, together with your contact details. Publication will be no earlier than three months from the date of this opinion letter. Should you wish to provide a substitute contact point, require further information, or wish to make a request to postpone publication, please contact [redacted] outlining the reasons for your request.

Confirmation of ethical opinion

On behalf of the Committee, I am pleased to confirm a favourable ethical opinion for the above research on the basis described in the application form, protocol and supporting documentation as revised, subject to the conditions specified below.

Conditions of the favourable opinion

The REC favourable opinion is subject to the following conditions being met prior to the start of the study.

Management permission must be obtained from each host organisation prior to the start of the study at the site concerned.

8.3 Appendix 3. University of the West of Scotland approval

30/01/2018

Dear Susan Kayes,

Getting it right for teenage parents who are in or leaving local authority or kinship care., submission reference 1727, has been approved, with conditions, by the Health Nursing and Midwifery SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below:**

Title	Comment
Where will the proposed research take place?	NHS Lanarkshire
Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)	re VI- any images etc to be used would be best presented to the Ethics Committee for review as per 1st submission comments.
Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)	A reference list has not been provided.
Please explain how you will analyse, present/disseminate the data you intend to collect:	audio recorded AND scribed?
Please explain how you will analyse, present/disseminate the data you intend to collect:	It is assumed Susan will undertake audio transcription herself?
Please provide details below and how you propose to deal with such issues:	'participant ' 'client' or 'LAYP'- use consistent term of reference throughout.
Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:	It is NMC Code - and not the NMC Code of Professional Conduct.
Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:	'health staff' again use terms of reference consistently throughout this submission.
Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:	'Professional staff' consistent term of reference should be used throughout when describing this group.
Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:	spelling (permission).
Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:	In terms of confidentiality and in relation to the selection of the professionals - it is indicated that the managers will assist in this process (in order to select and allocate e.g. time back/replacement) - how can confidentiality be proposed?
What is the expected duration of participation in the study for each participant?	In the supporting literature - 50 minutes is cited. The information should be consistent. In the PIS for the Kinship/ Carers and professionals - under the section "What are the Benefits" - the students has indicated "Your Input will contribute...". This may be factually inaccurate as the researcher may not have the resources or authority to implement the findings. In addition, the student has indicated on the PIS for the LAYP - they have correctly used the word "may contribute". This is more realistic In terms of presenting their written information to potential participants - the student may consider standardising their literature.
What is the expected duration of participation in the study for each participant?	PIS states 1 hour.
Will informed consent be obtained from study participants?	On the Focus Group Participant's Consent form - the footer states "Patient Consent Form, Version 2, March 17". This is for the professionals and the kinship carers who are not patients. Consider amending this.

Will informed consent be obtained from study participants?

There is a PIS for each of the 3 groups. There is a consent form for the LAYP - but only one consent form for the professionals and kinship carers - is this intentional?

There is a consent form for the LAYP - however, there is no mention of audio recording - either in the PIS for LAYP or in the consent form.

In relation to the professionals - as it is the managers who are identifying them - it can only be assumed that the professionals will not feel coerced to participate. However, despite the fact there is a 2 week cooling off period - some staff may still feel obliged to participate.

In the PIS for LAYP - the footer states that it is V2 but the header contains information that it is V1. Similarly, the first question in the consent form refers to the date 14/9/17 in the PIS - this is incorrect. All the dates should be aligned to prevent potential confusion.

Please provide details of how you will obtain this consent and the information you will provide to potential participants to allow them to make an informed choice about whether or not to participate in your research.

'fully informed consent' should also be gained pre interview or focus group by researcher.

Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)

Consider consistency with headers, footers and headings. Moreover, version control is very important in respect of promoting the student's approach to quality information.

Please provide details below and how you propose to deal with this

It is unclear what the researcher means when she suggests that she will visit them as discreetly as possible? How will this be undertaken?

Please provide details below and how you propose to deal with this

How will permission be obtained from voluntary agencies for participation? and who will do this? (South Lan Council approval has been gained but await N Lanarkshire council)?

Please provide details below and how you propose to deal with this

again you interchange 'researcher' and health professional' 'Heath Practitioner'. Best to use one consistent term of reference throughout.

Please provide details below and how you propose to deal with this

NHS lone worker policy and management should be clear and explicit.

Please provide details below and how you propose to deal with this

'researcher' and /or 'health care practitioner'- use consistent term of reference throughout to describe 'researcher'.

The Chair must approve all changes before study commences. Please submit this information to the chair by email.

Good luck with your research.

Dr W MacKay

8.4 Appendix 4. NHS Lanarkshire Research and Development

Date
Enquiries to
Direct Line
Email

Dear Ms Kayes

Project title: Getting it right for teenage parents who are in or leaving local authority or kinship care

I am writing to you as Chief Investigator of the above study to advise that R&D Management approval has been granted for the conduct of your study within NHS Lanarkshire.

For the study to be carried out you are subject to the following conditions:

Conditions

- You are required to comply with Good Clinical Practice, Ethics Guidelines, Health & Safety Act 1999 and relevant UK and EU Data Protection legislation.
- The research is carried out in accordance with the Scottish Executive's Research Governance Framework for Health and Community Care (copy available via the Chief Scientist Office website: <http://www.cso.scot.nhs.uk/> or the Research & Development Intranet site: <http://firstport2/staff-support/research-and-development/default.aspx>)
- You must ensure that all confidential information is maintained in secure storage. You are further obligated under this agreement to report to the NHS Lanarkshire Data Protection Office and the Research & Development Office infringements, either by accident or otherwise, which constitutes a breach of confidentiality.
- Clinical trial agreements (if applicable), or any other agreements in relation to the study, have been signed off by all relevant signatories.

- You must contact the Lead Nation Coordinating Centre if/when the project is subject to any minor or substantial amendments so that these can be appropriately assessed, and approved, where necessary.
- You notify the R&D Department if any additional researchers become involved in the project within NHS Lanarkshire
- You notify the R&D Department when you have completed your research, or if you decide to terminate it prematurely.
- You must send brief annual reports followed by a final report and summary to the R&D office in hard copy and electronic formats as well as any publications.
- If the research involves any investigators who are not employed by NHS Lanarkshire, but who will be dealing with NHS Lanarkshire patients, there may be a requirement for an SCRO check and occupational health assessment. If this is the case then please contact the R&D Department to make arrangements for this to be undertaken and an honorary contract issued.

I trust these conditions are acceptable to you.

Yours sincerely,

Raymond Hamill – Senior R&D Manager

cc.

NAME	TITLE	CONTACT ADDRESS	ROLE
Dr William G. Mackay			Sponsor Contact
Jean Donaldson	Associate Director of Nursing		Local Field Supervisor

8.5 Appendix 5. Approval from Director of Nursing

Executive Director of Nursing,
Midwifery & Allied Health Professionals

Date
Your Ref
Our Ref

13 November 2017

Enquiries to
Direct Line
Email

Pending ethical approval, I hereby give permission for University of the West of Scotland PhD research student Susan Kayes, to undertake her study 'Getting it right for teenage parents who are in or leaving local authority or kinship care'.

Yours sincerely

Maria Docherty
Interim Executive Director of NMAHPs

8.6 Appendix 6. South Lanarkshire Council approval

8.7 Appendix 7. North Lanarkshire Council approval

I write to inform you that your Research Access Application has been successful, providing the terms and conditions of the Research Contract you signed are met. The contact person assigned to you for your research will be Sheena Campbell, Service Manager. You can contact Sheena on [REDACTED]

If you have any queries or require further feedback regarding the above please do not hesitate to contact me at the above telephone number.

Yours sincerely

Alasdair Macdonald Senior Officer

(Research and Management Information)

8.8 Appendix 8. Care Experienced (Looked After Young Parent) participation information sheet

My name is Susan Kayes. I am a student at the West of Scotland University and I am currently undertaking a research study as part of my PhD course.

My study wishes to understand how to support care experienced teenage parents who have been 'looked after' in their own home by their own parents or other family members, or 'looked after and accommodated' within foster care or a children's home in Scotland.

Before you decide to be involved or not, I need to be sure you understand why I am doing the study, and also what it will involve if you agree to take part. I am therefore providing you with the following information.

Why is this study being conducted?

Research suggests that young parents who have been in or are leaving care may face some challenges as they move to living away from their home and adjust to parenthood.

What do you want me to do?

I am interested in talking with you about what you found helpful or difficult during the time you were either expecting your baby, or in the early period following the birth of your child. I would hope to audio recorded our talk. I could visit you in your home, or if you preferred, we could meet in another place of your choice (e.g. health centre, school, friend's home). Our talk will take no longer than 1 hour.

With your agreement I would also speak with your Midwife, Family Nurse or Health Visitor. If there are any important adults in your life (this might be a friend, a partner or a family member) who you perhaps would like to add to your story, I would be happy to invite them join the study too.

Why have I been invited?

All teenage parents, male and female aged between 16-21, who have looked after and are expecting a child or have a child under the age of 2 years, have been asked by their midwife, health visitor or family nurse if they want to take part in this study.

What are the benefits to me?

There are no direct benefits to you, however by being involved in this study you may help to improve services support to teenage parents who have been in care.

Do I have to take part?

No. It is up to you whether you decide to take part in the study. There is **no** pressure to take part in the study. If you do decide to take part, you will be asked to sign a consent form. If you join you can still leave the study at any time and withdraw any information that you have provided.

When would we meet?

If you agree to take part in the study, I will contact you in 2 weeks time, using the phone or email your health worker shared with me, to check you still want to join. We can arrange a place that would suit you for us to meet. When we meet we can talk a bit more about the study, to check you understand what you would be expected of you and that this is something you definitely want to do. If you do want to take part, I will ask you to sign a written consent form.

What are the possible discomforts and risks? How will these discomforts and risks be reduced?

Taking time out of your day to meet with me may be difficult for you.

It may be upsetting discussing some of the difficulties that you may have experienced. You would be able to withdraw from the study at any point if you found it distressing. If you wanted additional support, with your agreement, the researcher would seek support services for you by talking with your GP.

Will my information be kept confidential?

Everything you tell me about your views will be anonymised. This means I will not tell anyone your name when I share your views and no information will be used which may identify you. Nothing that you say will affect the service you are receiving from agencies. The only reason that I would need to discuss your personal details with other agencies would be if you told me something that made me concerned about a child or vulnerable adult having been harmed, or being at risk of harm. I would then need to tell the social work department or police.

If you wish, the results of the research will be given to you once the study is ended. I will discuss with you how you would like me to send the anonymised study to you.

Who has reviewed this study?

The study has been reviewed by the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee and by the Coventry and Warwickshire Research Ethics Committee.

What if I have any further questions?

Please contact the researcher Susan Kayes on my email:

[Redacted]
[Redacted]

If you have any further questions you can contact the following people:

Academic Supervisors:

Dr Ruth Astbury (University of West Scotland): [Redacted]
[Redacted]

Professor Jean Rankin (University of West Scotland): [Redacted]
[Redacted]

Independent contact: Professor Debbie Tolson [Redacted] [Redacted] [Redacted] [Redacted]
[Redacted] [Redacted]

8.9 Appendix 9. Care Experienced (Looked After Young Parent) consent form

[REDACTED]
Lead researcher: Susan Kayes

University of the West of Scotland
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Getting it right for 'looked after' teenage parents: A case study.

Young Person's Consent Form. Phase 1.

	Please initial boxes below
I confirm that I have read the information sheet dated 27/08/18 (version 3) about the above study.	
I have had the chance to discuss this study and ask any questions.	
I have been given answers to all of my questions	
I have received enough information about the study	
I understand that my involvement is voluntary and that I can withdraw at any time without offering a reason.	
I understand that the responses I give will be kept confidential and will be anonymous.	

I agree that the information I give will be used by the research team only.	
I agree that the information I give will be held for research purposes for 5 years.	
I agree to be audio recorded during my interview.	
I agree to my anonymous quotes being used in publications	
I agree to my Family Nurse, Midwife or Health Visitor (please delete as appropriate) adding to my story of their involvement in my care.	
I agree to the researcher contacting any other adult individual that I identify as being important to my well-being (e.g. another family member, partner or friend)	
I agree to take part in the above study	

Name of Participant Date Signature

Name of Person taking consent Date Signature

8.10 Appendix 10. Health Practitioner's information sheet

Health Practitioner Participant Information Sheet –Phase 1 and phase 2 (v2 16/06/18)

Getting it right for teenage parents in care: a case study.

My name is Susan Kayes. As part of my PhD with the West of Scotland University I am currently undertaking a research study. The study aims to add to our understanding about how to support teenage parents who have been 'looked after' or 'looked after and accommodated' within Scotland.

Before you decide to be involved or not, I need to be sure you understand why I am doing the study and also what it will involve if you agree to take part. I am therefore providing you with the following information.

Why is this research being conducted?

Studies indicate that 'looked after' young parents face many challenges as they move to independent living and adjust to parenthood. I plan to explore 'looked after' young parent's perception of their support needs and the support they receive when making their parenting choices. I am also interested in the experiences of staff working in Children's Services and other significant individuals to gain further understanding of the looked after young parent's' story.

Why am I being invited?

You are invited to take part in the study because you have provided support to a 'looked after and accommodated young parents and their children.

If you feel that you fit the criteria for participation, you are warmly invited to participate in this study.

Do I have to take part?

No. It is up to you whether you decide to take part. There is no pressure to take part in the study. If you do decide to take part, you will be asked to sign a consent form. If you choose to take part in the study, you can leave at any time and withdraw any information that you have provided. A decision to not participate or to withdraw from the study will not affect your work or working conditions.

What do you want me to do?

Information will be collected for this research in two stages. You are invited to attend either Stage 1 or Stage 2 of the study.

Phase 1- Health practitioners currently working with the looked after parents, and any individuals identified as significant by the parents, will also be invited to attend an individual semi-structured interview. Ideally I would like to audio record the discussion. However, if you prefer I can arrange to have notes written instead

Phase 2- A closed focus group with a range of health professionals working within children's services will be asked to share their thoughts about issues relating to supporting 'looked after' young parents and their children. The focus group will be facilitated by the researcher. A maximum of 8 participants will be invited to a focus group and only staff supporting 'looked after' young parents in the Lanarkshire area will be attending.

What are the discomforts and risks? How will these discomforts and risks be minimised?

The risk might be a breach of confidentiality however the researcher will take all necessary precautions to avoid this. It may also be upsetting talking about any difficult issues. If you found it distressing, you would be able to withdraw from the study at any time. If you felt you needed any additional support with your permission the researcher would link with your GP.

What are the benefits?

Although there are no direct benefits to you to taking part in this study, this is an opportunity for you to share your experiences of supporting 'looked after' and 'looked after and accommodated' young parents in Scotland. Your input may contribute to the research knowledge base for understanding how best to support 'looked after' young parents.

How will my privacy be protected?

Your views will be documented using a false name to protect your anonymity. Any other details that may be disclosed will remain anonymous. This way you will be able to reflect your experiences without breaching confidentiality and privacy. Confidentiality would only be breached if it is disclosed a child or a vulnerable adult has been harmed or is at risk of harm. In these circumstances I would need to advise the appropriate statutory agencies in

accordance with the Adult Support and Protection Act 2007 and National Guidance for Child Protection in Scotland 2014.

Comments will be collated and reported in a general way. All information collected will be kept strictly confidential, and stored in accordance with the General Data Protection (2018) and the Data Protection Act (1998). Information obtained will remain confidential and stored on a password protected PC accessible only by the research team. All data will be kept securely for 5 years following the study and will then be destroyed.

What are the discomforts and risks? How will these discomforts and risks be minimised?

Although I have permission for you to participate in the study during your working time unfortunately I do not have the resources to provide support to make up for your time out of practice. I would hope to arrange to meet at a time and venue that would suit and would minimise your travel time and expenses.

To avoid a breach of confidentiality, there will be clear group guidelines, all participants will sign a confidentiality agreement and there will be careful facilitation of the focus group discussion.

It may be upsetting discussing some of the difficulties that you have experienced in your role. You would be able to withdraw from the study at any point if you wished, if you required additional support, with your agreement, the researcher could seek additional support for you by liaising with your GP.

What opportunity do I have to consider this invitation?

Once you have read this invitation I would be happy to clarify any points not understood.

How do I agree to participate in this research?

Once you have contacted me to let me know that you are interested in taking part, I will be in contact by phone or email after 2 weeks to make arrangements to agree obtaining your written consent and conducting the interview.

Will I receive feedback on the results of this research?

Publications from this project will be in the public domain but if you wish for an anonymised summary please email or phone the principle investigator as detailed below to arrange how you would like me to send the summary to you.

Who has reviewed this study?

The study has been reviewed by the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee and by the Coventry and Warwickshire Research Ethics Committee.

What do I do if I have concerns about this research?

Any concerns regarding the nature of this project should be notified in the first instance to the principal researcher listed below.

Whom do I contact for further information about this research?

Researcher Contact Details:

Principal investigator: Susan Kayes. PhD student. University of the West of Scotland
[REDACTED]

Or if you still need further information please contact the academic supervisors or independent advisor on their email or telephone number below:

Academic Supervisors:

Dr Ruth Astbury (University of West Scotland): [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Professor Jean Rankin (University of West Scotland): [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Independent contact:

Professor Debbie Tolson (University of the West of Scotland)
[REDACTED]

8.11 Appendix 11. Health Practitioner's consent form

Lead researcher: Susan Kayes
University of the West of Scotland

16/8/18 V2

Getting it right for 'looked after' teenage parents: A case study.
Health Practitioner Consent Form. Stage 1

	Please initial boxes below
I confirm that I have read the information sheet dated 16/6/18 (version 2) about the above study.	
I have had the chance to discuss this study and ask any questions.	
I have been given answers to all of my questions	
I have received enough information about the study	
I understand that my involvement is voluntary and that I can withdraw at any time without offering a reason.	
I understand that the responses I give will be kept confidential and will be anonymous.	
I agree the information I give will only be used by the research team	

I agree that the information I give will be held safely for research purposes for 5 years	
I agree to being audio recorded during my interview.	
I agree to my anonymised quotes being used in publications.	
I agree to take part in the above study.	

Name of Participant Date Signature

Name of Person taking consent Date Signature

8.12 Appendix 12. Significant Other's information sheet

Getting it right for teenage parents in care: A case study (v1 16/06/18).

My name is Susan Kayes. As part of my PhD with the West of Scotland University I am currently undertaking a research study. The study aims to add to our understanding about how to support teenage parents who have been 'looked after' or 'looked after and accommodated' within Scotland.

Before you decide to be involved or not I need to be sure you understand why I am doing the study and also what it will involve if you agree to take part. I am therefore providing you with the following information.

Why have I been invited to take part?

You are invited to take part in the study because a 'looked after' young parent has identified you as a potential eligible participant who provides him or her with support.

If you feel that you meet the criteria for participation, you are warmly invited to participate in this study.

Why is this research being conducted?

An extensive literature review has indicated that 'looked after' young parents face many challenges as they move to independent living and adjust to parenthood.

I plan to explore 'looked after' young parent's view of their support needs and the support they receive when making their parenting choices. I am also interested in the experiences of Kinship Carers and other significant individuals, to gain further understanding of the looked after young parent's' story.

Who has reviewed this research?

The research has been approved by the University of the West of Scotland. It has also been reviewed by the Coventry and Warwickshire Research Ethics Committee.

What will happen in this research?

Information will be collected for this research in two stages. You would only be invited to **Stage 1**.

Stage 1- Young looked after parents will be invited to participate in an individual semi-structured interview to explore what they find supportive and what they find challenging about being a young parent.

Health practitioners working with the parents, and any individuals identified by the young parents as significant to them, will also be invited to attend an individual semi-structured interview.

Ideally I would like to audio record the interviews however if you prefer I can arrange to have notes written instead

Stage 2- A closed focus group with a range of people working within children's services will be asked to share their thoughts about issues relating to supporting 'looked after' young parents and their children. The focus group will be facilitated by the researcher. A maximum of 8 participants will be invited to each focus group and only individuals supporting 'looked after' young parents in the Lanarkshire area will be attending.

Do I have to take part?

No. It is up to you whether to take part or not. If you do decide to take part, you will be asked to sign a consent form. After you have consented to part you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason. Your decision to not take part or your decision to withdraw will not affect any standard of care you would receive in the future. If you choose to take part in the **Stage 1** of the study, you may leave at any time and withdraw any information that you have provided.

Will my information be kept confidential?

Everything you tell me about your views will be anonymised. I will not tell anyone your name when I write down your views. No information will be used which may identify you. Nothing that you say will be shared with professionals that you are working with and it will not affect the service you receive from professionals. The only reason that I would need to discuss your information with other agencies would be if there was a concern about a child or vulnerable adult having been harmed or being at risk of harm. In these circumstances I would need to advise the appropriate statutory agencies in

accordance with the Adult Support and Protection Act 2007 and National Guidance for Child Protection in Scotland 2014.

If you wish, the results of the research will be made available to you once the study is completed. Please contact me by phone or email to let me know how best to send the anonymised results to you.

What are the discomforts and risks? How will these discomforts and risks be alleviated?

The risk might be a breach of confidentiality however the researcher will take all necessary precautions to avoid this. It may also be upsetting talking about any difficult issues. You would be able to withdraw from the study at any time. If you felt you needed any additional support, with your permission the researcher would link with your GP for additional support.

What are the benefits?

Although there are no direct benefits to you to taking part in this study, this is an opportunity for you to share your experiences of supporting 'looked after' and 'looked after and accommodated' young parents in Scotland. Your input may contribute to the research knowledge base for understanding how best to support 'looked after' young parents.

How will my privacy be protected?

Your views will be documented using a false name to protect your anonymity. Any other details that may be disclosed will remain anonymous. This way you will be able to reflect your experiences without breaching confidentiality and privacy. However, should it become apparent that an adult or child

Comments will be collated and reported in a general way. All information collected will be kept strictly confidential, and stored in accordance with the Data Protection Act (1998). Information obtained will remain confidential and stored on a password protected PC accessible only by the research team. All data will be kept securely for 5 years following the study and will then be destroyed.

What are the costs of participating in this research?

The main cost will be your time commitment to participate in the interview it is anticipated the interview would take no more than 1 hour of your time.

What opportunity do I have to consider this invitation?

Once you have read this invitation I would be happy to clarify any points not understood.

How do I agree to participate in this research?

Once you have contacted me to let me know that you are interested in taking part, I will be in contact by phone or email after 2 weeks to make arrangements to agree obtaining your written consent and conducting the interview.

Will I receive feedback on the results of this research?

Publications from this project will be in the public domain but if you wish for an anonymised summary please email the principle investigator as detailed below.

What do I do if I have concerns about this research?

Any concerns regarding the nature of this project should be notified in the first instance to the principal researcher listed below.

Whom do I contact for further information about this research?

Researcher Contact Details:

Principal investigator: Susan Kayes. PhD student. University of the West of Scotland

[REDACTED]

Or if you still need further information please contact the academic supervisors or independent advisor on their email or telephone number below:

Academic Supervisors:

Dr Ruth Astbury (University of West Scotland):

[REDACTED]

Professor Jean Rankin (University of West Scotland):

[REDACTED]

Independent contact:

Professor Debbie Tolson (University of the West of Scotland)

[REDACTED].

8.13 Appendix 13. Consent form for Significant Other

v1 16/06/18

Lead researcher: Susan Kayes

University of the West of Scotland

Email [REDACTED]

Work tel. no. [REDACTED]

Getting it right for 'looked after' teenage parents: A case study.

Significant Other Consent Form. Phase 1.

	Please initial boxes below
I confirm that I have read the information sheet dated 16/6/18 (version 1) about the above study.	
I have had the chance to discuss this study and ask any questions.	
I have been given answers to all of my questions.	
I have received enough information about the study	
I understand that my involvement is voluntary and that I can withdraw at any time without offering a reason.	
I understand that the responses I give will be kept confidential and will be anonymous.	
I agree that the information I give will be used by the research team only.	
I agree that the information I give will be held for research purposes for 5 years.	

I agree to be audio recorded during my interview.	
I agree to my anonymous quotes being used in publications	
I agree to take part in the above study	

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Name of Person taking consent

Date

Signature

8.14 Appendix 14. Social Work focus group participation information sheet

Getting it right for teenage parents in care: a case study (v2 16/6/16)

My name is Susan Kayes. As part of my PhD with the West of Scotland University I am currently undertaking a research study. The study aims to add to our understanding about how to support teenage parents who have been 'looked after' or 'looked after and accommodated' within Scotland.

Before you decide to be involved or not I need to be sure you understand why I am doing the study and also what it will involve if you agree to take part. I am therefore providing you with the following information,

Why is this research being conducted?

An extensive literature review has indicated that 'looked after' young parents face many challenges as they transition to independent living and adjust to parenthood.

I plan to explore 'looked after' young parent's perception of their support needs and the support they receive when making their parenting choices. I am also interested in the experiences of Children's Services staff and other significant individuals, to gain further understanding of the looked after young parent's' story.

Why have I been invited?

You are invited to take part in the study because your managers have identified you as a potential eligible participant working within local authority services and providing support to 'looked after and accommodated young people and their children.

If you feel that you fit the criteria for participation, you are warmly invited to participate in this study.

Do I have to take part?

No. It is up to you whether you decide to take part. There is **no** pressure to take part in the study. If you do decide to take part, you will be asked to sign a consent form. If

you choose to take part in the study, you can leave at any time and withdraw any information that you have provided. A decision to not participate or to withdraw from the study will not affect your work or working conditions.

What do you want me to do?

Data will be collected for this project in two stages. You are invited to join **Phase 2** which is a closed focus group with a range of professionals working within your employer's organisation, to share your thoughts about issues relating to supporting 'looked after' young parents and their children. The focus group will be facilitated by the researcher. A maximum of 8 participants will be invited to the group and only staff working in the Lanarkshire area will be attending. The group will meet for 1 hour. Ideally I would like to audio record the discussion. However, if you prefer, I can arrange to have notes scribed instead.

What are the discomforts and risks? How will these discomforts and risks be minimised?

Although I have permission for you to participate in the study during your working time unfortunately I do not have the resources to provide support to make up for your time out of practice. I would hope to arrange the focus group at a time that would suit and would minimise your travel time and expenses.

It may be upsetting discussing some of the difficulties that you have experienced in your role. You would be able to withdraw from the study at any point if you wished. If you required additional support, with your agreement, the researcher could seek additional support for you by liaising with your GP.

What are the benefits?

Although there are no direct benefits to you to taking part in this study, this is an opportunity for you to share your experiences of supporting 'looked after' and 'looked after and accommodated' young parents in Scotland. Your input may contribute to the research knowledge base for understanding how to work best when supporting 'looked after' young parents.

Will my details be kept confidential?

Your views from the focus group will be documented using a pseudonym to protect your anonymity. Your workplace or location will remain anonymous. Participants of the

focus group will be asked to agree to treat the group discussions as confidential. This way you will be able to reflect your experiences without breaching confidentiality and privacy. Comments will be collated and reported in a general way. All information collected will be kept strictly confidential, and stored in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (2018) and Data Protection Act (1998). Information obtained will remain confidential and stored on a password protected PC accessible only by the research team. All data will be kept securely for 5 years following the study and will then be destroyed. Confidentiality would only be breached if there were concerns a child or vulnerable adult may have been harmed or at risk of harm. The researcher in these circumstances would need to advise the appropriate statutory agencies, in accordance with the Adult Support and Protection Act 2007 and National Guidance for Child Protection in Scotland 2014.

What are the costs of participating in this research?

The main cost will be your time commitment during working hours to attend the focus group. It is anticipated approx. 1 hour of your time will be required.

What opportunity do I have to consider this invitation?

If you have any questions I would be happy to clarify any points not understood. Please contact me by email or by phone as detailed below.

How do I agree to participate in this research?

Please email me or phone me on the contact details below to express your interest to participate. I will be in touch by phone or email within a 2-week period to make arrangements to agree obtaining your written informed consent.

Will I receive feedback on the results of this research?

Publications from this project will be in the public domain. If, you wish for an anonymised executive summary, please email or phone the principle investigator as detailed below so I can arrange how I can send this to you.

Who has reviewed this study?

The study has been reviewed by the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee and by the Coventry and Warwickshire Research Ethics Committee.

What do I do if I have concerns about this research?

Any concerns regarding the nature of this project should be notified in the first instance to the principal researcher listed below.

Whom do I contact for further information about this research?

If you have further questions, please contact my Academic Supervisors or Independent contact as listed below.

Researcher Contact Details:

Principal investigator: Susan Kayes. PhD student. University of the West of Scotland

[REDACTED]

Academic Supervisors:

Dr Ruth Astbury (University of West Scotland): [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Professor Jean Rankin (University of West Scotland): [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Independent contact: Professor Debbie Tolson (University of the West of Scotland)

[REDACTED]

8.15 Appendix 15. Social Work focus group consent form

Lead researcher: Susan Kayes

University of the West of Scotland

Email [REDACTED]

My work mobile tel. no. [REDACTED]

Focus Group Consent Form. Phase 2 (v2 16/6/18)

	Please initial boxes below
I confirm that I have read the information sheet dated 16/6/18 (version 2) about the above study.	
I have had the chance to discuss this study and ask any questions.	
I have been given answers to all of my questions.	
I have received enough information about the study.	
I understand that my involvement is voluntary and that I can withdraw at any time without offering a reason.	
I will treat the group discussions as confidential.	
I understand that the responses I give will be kept confidential and will be anonymous.	

I agree the information I give will only be used by the research team.	
I agree that the information I give will be held safely for research purposes for 5 years	
I agree to being audio recorded during my interview.	
I agree to my anonymised quotes being used in publications.	
I agree to take part in the above study.	

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Name of Person taking consent

Date

Signature

8.16 Appendix 16. Semi structured interview questions for CEP

Semi-structured interview questions (v1 7/3/17)

Name and age of LAYP and child/ren

Are you in school/training/employment?

Please describe where you live?

Who do you live with?

Do you have your own tenancy?

In personal and social education classes in school, what did you think of the sexual health and relationship education?

Tell me about your how you felt when you discovered you were pregnant/your partner was pregnant?

Who were the first people that you told about the pregnancy? What was their response?

What did it/does it feel like meeting with your Midwife?

What is your experience of meeting with your Health Visitor or Family Nurse?

Can you describe to me what changes you had to make before the arrival of your child e.g. did you have to change working hours/claim benefits/make healthy changes?

What people were most supportive to you during your pregnancy? Were you surprised who offered you support and who didn't?

Other than the Midwife, Health Visitor or Family Nurse, where there any other agencies supporting you (e.g. Housing, Education, Young Person's Benefit advisor, Social Work, Throughcare worker, Who Cares, Loretto, Young Parent Groups, other health workers)? What is it like being involved with these health and other services?

Can you describe to me what the birth of your baby like?

Tell me what the early weeks of being a parent was like? Did anyone prepare you for what being a new parent would be like?

Do you have help from other adults or family members that help with childcare responsibilities?

When you have time to yourself, what do you do?

Who will support you to achieve your future goals?

How long have you been/were you in care for? Who cared for you?

Did you/do you have to move home before the birth of your baby?

Do you have a current partner? Is your current partner the parent of your child?

Does your child see his/her other parent?

Have you or your partner ever been involved with criminal justice services?

Is there anything else you'd like to tell me?

8.17 Appendix 17. Semi-structured Interview Health Practitioners

Semi-structured interview for Health practitioners. Phase 1 (v1 16/06/18)

Name

Place of work

Please describe your role?

How long have you been working with the LAYP?

Please tell me about your involvement supporting this LAYP.

Can you describe to me what changes you have seen in the LAYP since you started working with them?

Please describe any changes you feel the LAYP still needs support with.

What people were most supportive to the LAYP during pregnancy?

What people were most supportive to the LAYP following the birth?

Tell me what you feel the LAYP has achieved.

What did the LAYP find most challenging?

What difficulties do you know of that the LAYP has overcome?

Were there any other agencies supporting the LAYP (e.g. Housing, Education, Young Person's Benefit advisor, Social Work, Throughcare worker, Who Cares, Loretto, Young Parent Groups, other health workers)?

What is it like being involved with these health and other services? Do you feel you worked collaboratively to improve the outcomes for the LAYP?

8.18 Appendix 18. Semi structured interview of Significant Others

Semi-structured interview for Significant Others. Phase 1 (v1 16/06/18)

Name

Please describe how you know the Looked After Young Parent (LAYP)?

How long have you known the LAYP?

Please tell me about your involvement supporting this LAYP.

Can you describe to me what changes you have seen in the LAYP since he/she has become a parent or in planning for the birth?

Please describe any changes you feel the LAYP still needs support with.

What people were most supportive to the LAYP during pregnancy?

What people were most supportive to the LAYP following the birth?

Tell me what you feel the LAYP has achieved.

What did the LAYP find most challenging?

What difficulties do you know of that the LAYP has overcome?

Were there any other agencies supporting the LAYP (e.g. Housing, Education, Young Person's Benefit advisor, Social Work, Throughcare worker, Who Cares, Loretto, Young Parent Groups, other health workers)?

What is it like for the LAYP being involved with these health and other services? Do you feel they helped the LAYP?

8.19 Appendix 19. Focus group questions

V1 17/4/18

The focus group topics will be informed from the themes identified from the semi-structured interview with the looked after young parents (LAYP). It is anticipated that some of the following questions will guide the focus group:

How would you describe throughcare support to Looked after Young Parents (LAYP)?

Do you feel the LAYP you have been working with are able to access appropriate health and social care services?

How well do you feel LAYP leaving care are prepared for independent living?

How well do you feel LAYP are prepared for parenthood?

Can you give me an example of when with other services helped you to support LAYP?

Do you have any examples of challenges of supporting LAYP from other agencies?

Do you feel LAYP continue to have support from their carers or extended family?

How do you encourage LAYP to engage with your service?

Do you have any further reflections you would like to share about supporting LAYP?

8.20 Appendix 20. Example of significant statement and early coding

I'm thinking of going back in January. Back to college.
Plans for the future
And what are you thinking of doing
Social care
Oh, so a course in social care?
I'll be starting off with an NQ (National Qualification).
Plans for the future
So is this your own tenancy that you're living in?
Yeah.
How long have you had your tenancy for?
Almost a year
Transition
And who do you live with?
Eh my daughter and my fiancé
Relationship with partner
Ok –I'm just checking this is recording. So you've got your own tenancy you live here with your fiancé mmm and you've got your wee one here as well. Mm can you tell me, can you think back, I know this is quite a few years back, when you went to school did you get sexual health and relationship education?
We never really got taught much, basically we just got taught what certain things were. Just (inaudible) basically
You got what?
Basically just got told don't have sex basically.
Not to have sex (laughs)

Yeah basically (laughs)
And can you remember what age you were when you got it?
I was in primary 7 so about 11
Ok, so it started quite early on, they started telling you what... about puberty?
Yeah
So that was P7 and then you got to high school did they then later tell you about contraception?
Yeah. That was like 2 nd year we got told about that
And was it helpful or....?
Not really no.
What, what made it. Was it embarrassing or was it....
Yeah
Did you have boys in your class?
You also got relationship education. Can you remember anything about what forms a healthy, loving, relationship?
Aye
And was that helpful for you at all?
A wee bit aye. But no really. It basically just told you like a healthy relationship is basically kinda the relationship you have with yer maw and da
Relationship with family
Yeah. And was that difficult?
Yeah 'cause of what I went through. I never exactly had it.
Relationship with family
Oh.
So that must have been hard for you?
Yeah. Client seemed tearful momentarily.

If you just want to stop for a while just say, or if you want me to stop all together, that's absolutely fine to stop all together.
Shook head
So you didn't find it that helpful, it wasn't considering your situation at that time. Were you in foster care at that time?
Yeah I've been in foster care since my 3 rd birthday
So can you tell me what it was like when you found out you were pregnant? What was that like for you?
It was scary. Cause it wasn't something I thought would have happened. Obviously because I was battling my eating disorder so I thought it was something that would never happen
Feelings about being pregnant
So were you not having any periods at that time?
No. So that's what really scared me. Cause I wasn't having any periods or nothing because of how skinny I was
Mental health/Knowledge about sexual health
Yes
So when you found out what were the feelings ?
I was quite surprised. And scared at the same time like. Cause I didn't know what was going in, cause I'd just left my nana and papa's (home). Then I had to live with my pal's mum and that. Then it just went downhill.
Transition-Homeless
Mmm?
So obviously I was pure stressed with where I was meant to go and all that. It was scary. Cause it wasn't something I thought would have happened. Obviously because I was battling my eating disorder so I thought it was something that would never happen
Transition-Homeless/Mental Health/Feelings about pregnancy

So you were kind of wondering.... that was a big transition in your life as it was moving out of your grandparent's and then you had another really big change in your life with the pregnancy. So you were staying at your friend's house at that time?

Yep

I became really excited about it like knowing no matter what I've been through that I can be a better mum, so I got really excited about it

Being a good mother.

So you had quite a lot to deal with and then this wee one coming along. So the 1st person you told about your baby who was it?

My mum. Me and my mum weren't meant to be talking, But I text her 'going by the way you've got a grandchild on the way'. But she didn't reply back because we weren't allowed to talk. But my mum was the 1st person to know 'cause I thought I would rather tell my mum than anyone else first. So I told my mum.

Relationship with family

Ok So were social work saying you shouldn't be speaking to your mum?

No. I had a court case against my dad. And because my mum lives with my dad I wasn't allowed to speak to her. At all.

Relationship with family

So that was a really difficult time for you. And it was good news that you really wanted to share with her.

Yeah.

You really wanted to share that with her and she felt she couldn't respond. When did she respond to you?

A couple of months after. Cause I sent a picture of the scan. And that's when my mum replied back.

Relationship with family

She was really happy but at the same time she was kinda angry. Because she could nae stop it (the pregnancy) 'cause I did nae speak to her about it. So Mum was angry- but there was nothing she could have done 'cause my mum was younger than me, she was 15 when she was pregnant with Annie. (Pseudonym)

Relationship with family

Ok. So do you think she wanted something different for you? You said she struggled as a mother?

Yeah. My mum wanted us all to wait 'cause she didn't want us to go through what she did 'cause mum was a young mum.

Relationship with family